

Journal of EcoAgriTourism

Bulletin of Agri-ecology, Agri-food, Bioengineering and Agritourism

Vol. 14 (2018), No 2 (37)

Journal of EcoAgriTourism
ISSN: 1844-8577

Journal of EcoAgriTourism is a follow up, by translation in
English of "Revista de EcoAgroTurism"
ISSN 1841-642X, first issued in 2005

Selected papers from
the 7th Bioatlas Conference
25-26 May 2018

ISSN: 1844-8577

EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

Department of Ecobiotechnologies and Equipment for Food and Agriculture

Transilvania University of Braşov
Bd. Eroilor nr. 29, 500036, Braşov,
Tel & Fax: 0268-415326, Tel:
0268-413000/161

Journal's Director

Prof. Romulus GRUIA Ph. D.

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. eng. Liviu GACEU Ph. D. Habil.

Scientific Board

Assoc. Prof. Ganesh Bora, Ph.D., Mississippi State University, United States;
Prof. Maria Isabel Bernuga, Ph.D., University Castilla La Mancha, Spain;
Prof. Mark Shamtsyan Ph.D. State Institute of Technology, St. Petersburg, Rusia;
Prof. Miklos Herdon, Ph.D. Hab., University of Debrecen, Hungary;
Prof. Ray F. Iunius, Ph.D., Director Business Development SA, Switzerland;
Prof. Stefan Stefanov, Ph.D., University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria;
Prof. Valerii Sukmanov, Ph.D. Hab., University of Donuet, Ukraine;
Prof. Werner Hofacker, Ph.D., University of Applied Sciences, Konstanz, Germany;

Technical Board

Simona SOICA
Oana Bianca OPREA
Raisa SAMOILA
Raducu MICU
Bernadett DENES
Cristina RUSU
Nicoleta TINEA
Andrei APARASCHIVEI
Amalia ADAM
Luiza VOICILA

Published by:

Transilvania University Press
500091 Brasov, B-dul Iuliu Maniu 41 A
Tel: 0268-476050
Fax: 0268-476051
E-mail: editura@unitbv.ro
Co-editor: Romanian Society for Information Technology in Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism
www.rosita.ro/jeat
ISSN: 1844-8577

Center for Biodiversity in Agriculture and Forestry INCE/Romanian Academy-Research point ICDT/Transilvania University of Brasov
Romanian Society for Information Technology in Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism (ROSITA)

Tourism 2025: an industry of perspective

Tourism 2025 – tourism industry becomes larger and more diversified, including in Romania, and has the potential to start a strong economic growth. Tourism offers a vital context for certain collective actions by large or small industrial groups and for thousands of actions that individual enterprises will have every year. But it is necessary that more and more parts interested in tourism industry to be consulted over an enough long period of time (including academic environment) in order to assure that the developing process is on a solid foundation, based on Romanian reality and proved financing. There must be found formula for a real and strong support of interested parts, respectively a frame on which private sector assumes and, at the same time, ways are found to support public sector. It is vital to elaborate a frame-model of growth that will lead to make detailed investigations and consultations in order to test and, if it is necessary, to regulate this model in its final form. We mean a strong **professionalism in tourism industry** in order to finalize the national frame-plan of tourism on relatively short term, until the year 2025.

Without entering into details, we mention that there must be considered major forces that form the market of the world tourism, the distinct themes (but interconnected to national plans) that result from their consideration, all these being necessary to the study of the stipulated „growth cycle”. Intelligently and in harmony used, the industry wholly understanding inter-relations and interdependences within the „growth cycle”, the key themes allow tourism industry successfully face provocations and opportunities to come. Tourism 2025 aims to align industry in an intense way of growth, both at international level, and especially (we hope) as for Romanian tourism, that may have as original and authentic exponent, responsible tourism (ecotourism, rural tourism, agritourism, farm tourism and others).

Director of the publication,
Full Prof. Romulus GRUIA,
PhD, PhD supervisor

SUMMARY

Editorial : <i>Tourism 2025: AN INDUSTRY OF PERSPECTIVE – GRUIA Romulus</i>	
5	<i>CORN AND BUCKWHEAT FLOUR IN GLUTEN FREE BISCUITS</i> <i>C.M. CHERĂȚOIU, M. OGNEAN, C.F. OGNEAN, I. DANCIU</i>
10	<i>TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE VOCATIONAL TRAINING BY DECREASING PUPIL DROPOUT RATES</i> <i>I. CSEH-PAPP, T. WIWCZAROSKI, T. CSAPÓNÉ RISKÓ</i>
17	<i>THEORY OF BIO-HARMONISM</i> <i>R. GRUIA</i>
32	<i>RESEARCH OF THE ESTIMATION OF CALORIFIC VALUE OF BIOMASS</i> <i>GH.C. SPIRCHEZ, A.LUNGULEASA, C. CROITORU, R.FORFOTĂ, I. DUMITRACHE, N.R. SAMOILĂ</i>
36	<i>COMPARATIVE STUDY ON EUROPEAN LEGISLATION ABOUT HYGIENIC ENGINEERING AND DESIGN</i> <i>L. GACEU</i>
42	<i>RESEARCH REGARDING THE ANTIBACTERIAL EFFECT OF ESSENTIAL OILS EXTRACTED FROM: THYMUS VULGARIS, MALALEUCA AND OCIMUM BASILICUM</i> <i>GH. PUCHIANU, N.R. SAMOILĂ, A. MĂRCULESCU</i>
46	<i>STAGE OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL SUSTAINABLE TOURISM RESEARCH</i> <i>C. M. VERDUGO R. GRUIA</i>
52	<i>GREEN TEA, COFFE AND CHOCOLATE – TYPICAL SOURCES OF ANTIOXIDANTS</i> <i>L. POGAČNIK, N. POKLAR ULRIH</i>
56	<i>OPTIMIZATION OF TOURISM INDUSTRY PARAMETERS IN RELATION TO LANDSCAPE MANAGEMENT</i> <i>C. M. VERDUGO R. GRUIA</i>
65	<i>ROMANIA, DONOR OF FOOD AND DRINKING WATER IN THE 21st CENTURY EUROPE, BY ENGINEERING AND MANAGEMENT</i> <i>R.GRUIA</i>

CORN AND BUCKWHEAT FLOUR IN GLUTEN FREE BISCUITS

C.M. CHERĂȚOIU^{1*}, M. OGNEAN¹, C.F. OGNEAN¹, I. DANCIU¹

¹Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Food Industry and Environmental Protection, 7-9 Dr. I. Ratiu St., 550012 Sibiu, Romania,

*Corresponding author: cosminaoltean@yahoo.com

Abstract: Formulation of gluten-free biscuits were developed, based on flour mixture 50 % corn and 50% buckwheat with different levels of fat (coconut and palm oil) and sweeteners (sugar and stevia rebaudiana with erythritol). The purpose of this research was to identify which recipe lead to biscuits with proper characteristics and well accepted by the consumers. The results obtained increase the possibility to satisfy the demand for gluten free biscuits by substitute wheat flour with corn and buckwheat flour. Biscuits with palm oil and sugar (B1) had the best results at hedonic test.

Keywords: gluten free-biscuits, corn flour, buckwheat flour

1. Introduction

Celiac disease is a genetically-determined chronic inflammatory intestinal disease [1] induced by consumption of products containing gluten. A strict lifelong gluten-free diet is currently the only effective treatment for celiac disease [2].

Two main food groups are mostly used for replacing cereal containing gluten: cereals (maize, rice, sorghum and teff) and pseudo-cereals (amaranth, quinoa, buckwheat) [3]. Corn (*Zea mays* L.) is commonly used in the preparation of gluten-free products (GFP) alone or in mixture with others cereals or pseudo-cereals. Corn flour contains high levels of many important vitamins and minerals, including potassium, phosphorus, zinc, calcium, iron, thiamine, niacin, vitamin B6 and folate [4]. Buckwheat is used in GFP due to its potential health benefits. Two types of buckwheat are most usual known: common buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*) and Tartary buckwheat (*Fagopyrum tataricum*), the first one is generally utilized for obtaining GFP. Many of the health benefits of buckwheat have been attributed to its high levels of phenolic compounds and antioxidant activity [5]. Rutin and quercetin are the flavonoids responsible for antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects [6] and are also present in baked biscuits made from buckwheat [7].

Fat plays an important role in biscuit production and is recognized for functional, nutritional and sensorial properties [8]. Coconut oil contains mainly saturated fatty acids (~93%) with lauric

acid [9]. Coconut oil possesses antiviral, antibacterial and antiprotozoal properties due to the presence of lauric acid and capric acid [10]. Coconut oil contains less monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids so it is highly stable towards oxidation and because of that provides longer shelf-life for the food products which contains it.

Palm oil contains myristic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid, oleic acid and linoleic acid [11]. Palm oil represents a commercial alternative since 2004 due to the melting point (around 36°C) and it has been the non-hydrogenated oil of choice for making biscuits.

Stevia rebaudiana is a sweet plant and the sweet taste is due to steviol glycosides. Since 2011 steviol glycosides (E960) have been permitted for use as food additive as a sweetener in the EU [12].

Biscuits are very popular products all over the world with vast combination of texture and taste [13]. Three major ingredients are in biscuits: flour, sugar and fat. Comparative with other products the biscuits are characterized with low water content. Gluten free biscuits (GFB) are often based on pure starches resulting in a dry, sandy mouth-feel. So in this study the approach was to replace wheat flour with mixture of corn and buckwheat flour and to avoid the sandy mouth-feel.

The aim of this work was to develop GFB with good taste and appearance and also to determinate the influence of different types of fat and sugar on the final product quality. Gluten free biscuits prepared with a mixture of flours

and containing different proportion of palm/coconut oil and sugar/*Stevia rebaudiana* were sensory evaluated.

2. Materials and methods

Ingredients. The ingredients used for biscuits production were commercially available except the corn flour and palm oil which were kindly provided by Boromir Group from Sibiu. In the table below are presented ingredients and quantities used for formulation.

Table 1

Ingredients	Units	Quantities	Obs.
Flour	g	300	Corn flour from Boromir Group Buckwheat flour from Solaris Plant SRL
Fat	g	105	Palm fat from Boromir Group Coconut fat from SC Naturking SRL
Sugar /stevia rebaudiana with erythritol	g	45	Sugar from Agrana Romania SA Stevia rebaudiana with erythritol from Sly Nutritia SRL
Powdered milk	g	6	Dr. Oetker RO SRL
Baking powder*	g	3	Dr. Oetker RO SRL
Egg	g	50	Local market, fresh
Water	ml	90-100	Tap water

A mixture of flour, 50% corn flour+50% buckwheat flour was used to create four samples.

Table 2

Ingredients	B1	B2	B3	B4
Corn flour	50 %	50 %	50 %	50 %
Buckwheat flour	50%	50%	50%	50%
Palm fat	100%	100%	-	-
Coconut fat	-	-	100%	100%
Sugar	100%	-	100%	
<i>Stevia rebaudiana</i> with erythritol (Sweet&Safe)	-	100%	-	100%
Powdered milk	100%	100%	100%	100%
Baking soda	100%	100%	100%	100%
Egg	100%	100%	100%	100%
Water	100%	100%	100%	100%

Biscuit production. The ingredients were weighed according to specific recipes (table 1). The fat and the sugar were homogenized for 2

minute at speed 2 in a mixer Kitchen Aids. The eggs were homogenized with a hand blender for few seconds and then added to the fat and sugar composition. The time for blending was 1 minute at speed 4. After that, water and mixture of flour, powdered milk and baking powder was added. The blending time was 3 minute at speed 1. Following a rest time of 20 minute in the refrigerator, the dough was sheeted to a final thickness of 5 mm, rectangular shape L- 90 mm, l-30 mm. Dough pieces were placed on a baking paper in a tray and baked for 16 minute at 175⁰C in heated oven. After 30-40 min of cooling at room temperature, the GFB were placed in sealed plastic cassettes and stored at room temperature until further examination.

Physicochemical analyzes. Weight (w) of biscuits was measured as average of values of 3 individual biscuits with a digital weighing balance. Volume of biscuits was determined by using the formula $V=L*1*h$ (mm³). Density was obtained from ratio between weight and volume, after calculating volume. Textural analysis was done with a build-in apparatus using a 1 kg load cell and heavy duty platform at speed 1 mm/s. Texture analysis instrument consists in applying a perpendicular force to the sample (three points bend). Force is applied until the biscuit broke and the maximum force is achieved prior to failure. Average maximum force was calculated based on analysis of 3 samples. The moisture content for corn and buckwheat flour, for B1, B2, B3 and B4 was determined by drying samples at 130±2⁰C, 40 min in oven.

Sensory analysis. A group of 8 panelists analyzed samples. They complete a Hedonic test and gave notes from 1 (extremely dislike) to 9 (extremely like). Biscuits samples were served to the panelists in coded plastic plates. Water was served along with the samples for palate cleansing. Finally mean value was taken for each attribute of samples.

The physicochemical properties for corn and buckwheat flours were 12.75 and respective 10.77% moisture, 0.49 and respective 2.04% ash and 0.32 and respective 0.42 mL NaOH/100 g TTA . The mineral content was higher in buckwheat flour proving that buckwheat has multiple nutritional benefits (3) being healthier than refined corn flour. By mixing these two flours the nutritional profile was balanced. Acidity of corn and buckwheat flour had close values, lower than the acidity of semi white wheat flour and whole wheat flour, 3.2 and respective 5 ml NaOH / 100g [14, 15].

3. Results and discussion

The batter formulation of GFBs was a challenge, because of the lack of gluten network needed high attention in handling.

Four different recipe of biscuits (B1, B2, B3 and B4) were examined in the present study with variation of fat (palm fat, coconut fat) and sweetener (sugar and *Stevia rebaudiana* sweetener). The biscuits were tested for water activity (a_w) and moisture, breaking point (firmness), dimensions (width, length and thickness) and sensorial (hedonic test).

Fig. 1. Moisture of GFBs

The moisture content are presented in figure 1 and were specific to regular biscuits specified in literature, <5-6%. The moisture of GFB prepared with palm oil was lower than for GFB with coconut oil. Probably the fats were melted at different temperature and reduce water loss during baking in GFBs prepared with coconut oil.

The higher water activity (a_w) was observed for sample B4 (prepared with coconut oil and mixture of sweetener) and with highest water content too (see figure 2). Sugar seemed to control better the water activity of samples prepared with coconut oil.

We observed that small variation of moisture in biscuits could have a very high impact on water activities. We consider that for the safety of product with this formulation the final moisture of biscuits should be lower than 5%. Because the moisture of biscuits influence their hardness could be necessary to add some sweeteners which are able to reduce the water activity even at higher water content. Stevioside and erythriol from the formula used to replace sugar in biscuits

formulation had low affinity for water so are not able to effective control of water activity.

Fig. 2. GFB's water activity

The hardness of biscuits is equally important for producer and consumers. A hard biscuit could be handled easier and a low quantity of broken biscuits will be generated but for consumers hard biscuits will lead to oral injuries during eating. Also fragile biscuits could not be handled to be covered with butter, chocolate or other ingredients.

Fig. 3. Biscuits hardness

In figure 3 was presented hardness of biscuits. All samples have breaking point under 0.2. They are fragile and require special packaging for keep their shape. The most fragile is B4 which had the highest moisture and a_w . If we are looking at figure 1 and 3 we observed an inverse proportion between moisture and hardness, the highest moisture lead to lowest hardness.

Moisture of samples could have a high influence on biscuit's hardness. The regression coefficient for linear correlation between hardness and moisture is quite high ($R^2=0.7033$) but the number of samples is reduced. The fat used for formulation could also have a big importance because the biscuits prepared with palm fat had the highest hardness too.

Sensorial properties of biscuits were analyzed too. Corn flour present technological difficulties during handling and impart an unusual texture to products, exhibiting a dry crumbling crumb, resulting in poor mouthfeel and poor flavor. Buckwheat flour impart a specific taste (bitter) and specific aroma which are not well accepted by consumers which did not consume regular product with buckwheat. These were probably the cause of bad results for flavor and mouth feel during sensorial evaluation (Figure 4).

Fig.4. Sensory evaluation of GFBs

The highest values scores were obtained by biscuits prepared with sugar and palm fat. Coconut oil reduced also the sweetness of biscuits from sample 3, which were prepared with sugar too. The coconut oil and sugar replacers also reduced the scores for flavor, taste and mouthfeel while the smell was not influenced very much. For GFBs formulation palm fat and sugar seemed to be the best choice. If it is intended to obtain biscuits with low caloric values and low glicemic index (without sugar) more efforts should be done because the combination of erhytriol and stevioside was not very effective.

Colour is a determining factor in the appearance of biscuits and it can influence the consumer first impression. In Table 3 was presented the colour of samples. The colour of biscuits prepared with

palm oil is darker than coconut oil so the GFBs made with palm oil are a little bit an intense colour. These biscuits had also the lowest moisture content, probably during baking they lost water easier and faster and that led to higher temperature of biscuits and darker colour of them.

Table 3

Biscuits	B1	B2	B3	B4
Colour of biscuits				

Hedonic test reveals that GFBs with palm oil and sugar obtained the highest values and this can be explained by the usage of palm oil and sugar in most of the commercial biscuits.

4. Conclusions

4 sample GFBs were made from 50% corn flour and 50% buckwheat flour with palm oil/coconut oil and sugar/stevia rebaudiana with erytritol. Moisture for all samples was under 6% and could assure a long shelf life for biscuits. Much attention must be done when sugar is replaced with a mixture of stevioside from *Stevia rebaudiana* and erythriol because this mixture had a low ability to control water activity.

Combination of palm fat with sugar was most appreciated by the panellist. *Stevia rebaudiana* has a specific flavour and consumers are not used with it so for future it is wise to incorporate other aroma like cinnamon, vanilla, cocoa. The biscuits had a low hardness and the hardness seemed to be influenced by biscuit's moisture. For a good appearance of product a round form will be probably better than rectangular form. This form will also prevent breakage better than rectangular one because the lack o corners.

The dough obtained from corn flour and buckwheat flour had a very bad rheology because of the lack of gluten needed to provide structure. The structure of dough was provided mainly by fat and the dough was very hard to handle. To improve the dough structure could be useful to add fibbers (soluble and/or insoluble). The fibbers will also improve the nutritional aspects of biscuits.

Breaking point was very low for all samples, another reason for including of fibbers in recipe,

to create a solid bonding between ingredients or a more resistant matrix.

The quality of product is affected by the shape,

References

1. Jnawali, P., Kumar, V., Tanwar, B.: *Celiac disease: Overview and considerations for development of gluten-free foods*. Food Science and Human Wellness 5 (2016) 169–176
2. Churrua, I., Larretxi, I., Lasa, A., *Gluten-Free Diet: Nutritional Status and Dietary Habits of Celiac Patients*. In chapter 6 of book: Nutritional and Analytical Approaches of Gluten-Free Diet in Celiac Disease, by E. Simón et al., Springer Briefs in Food, Health and Nutrition, DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-53342-1_6
3. Lasa, A., Pilar Fernández-Gil, M., Bustamante, M. Á., Miranda, J.: *Nutritional and Sensorial Aspects of Gluten-Free Products*. In chapter 5 of book: Nutritional and Analytical Approaches of Gluten-Free Diet in Celiac Disease, by E. Simón et al., Springer Briefs in Food, Health, and Nutrition, DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-53342-1_5
4. Sabanis, D., Tzia, C.: *Effect of Rice, Corn and Soy Flour Addition on Characteristics of Bread Produced from Different Wheat Cultivars*. Food Bioprocess Technol (2009) 2:68–79 DOI 10.1007/s11947-007-0037-7
5. Wijngaard, H. H., Arendt, E. K.: *Buckwheat*. Cereal Chemistry, 83, 391–401 (2006).
6. Lukšič, L., Bonafaccia, G., Timoracka, M., Vollmannova, A., Trček, J., Nyambe, T. K. Melini, V., Acquistucci, R., Germ, M., Kreft, I. : *Rutin and quercetin transformation during preparation of buckwheat sourdough bread*. Journal of Cereal Science 69 (2016) 71-76
7. Wieslander, G., Fabjan, N., Vogrinčič, M., Kreft, I., Janson, C., Spetz-Nystrom, U., Vombergar, B., Tagesson, C., Leanderson, P., Norbäck, D.: *Eating cookies is associated with the reduction in serum levels of myeloperoxidase and cholesterol: a double blind crossover study in day-care centre staffs*, Tohoku J. Exp. Med. 225, 123e130.
8. Stauffer CE (1998) *Cereal Foods World* 43:120–126)
9. Prakruthi Appaiah, L. Sunil, P. K., Kumar, P., Gopala Krishna, A. G.: *Composition of Coconut Testa, Coconut Kernel and its Oil - J Am Oil Chem Soc* (2014) 91:917–924 DOI 10.1007/s11746-014-2447-9)
10. Bhatnagar, AS, Prasanth Kumar PK, Hemavathi J, Gopala Krishna AG (2009) *Fatty acid composition, oxidative stability, and radical scavenging activity of vegetable oil blends with coconut oil*, J Am Oil Chem Soc 86:991–999).
11. Atkinson, G., Karlshamn, A.: *Fats and oils as biscuit ingredients*, UK, Woodhead Publishing Limited, 2011
12. Morlock, G. E., Meyer, S, Zimmermann, B. F., Roussel, J. M.: *High-performance thin-layer chromatography analysis of steviolglycosides in Stevia formulations and sugar-free food products, and bench marking with (ultra) high-performance liquid chromatography*, Journal of Chromatography A, 1350 (2014) 102–111)
13. Morlock, G. E., Meyer, S, Zimmermann, B. F., Roussel, J. M.: *High-performance thin-layer chromatography analysis of steviolglycosides in Stevia formulations and sugar-free food products, and bench marking with (ultra) high-performance liquid chromatography*, Journal of Chromatography A, 1350 (2014) 102–111)
14. Schober T. J., O'Brien, C. M., McCarthy, D., Darnedde, A., Arendt, E. K.: *Influence of gluten-free flour mixes and fat powders on the quality of gluten-free biscuits*, Eur Food Res Technol (2003) 216:369–376 DOI 10.1007/s00217-003-0694-3
15. <https://lege5.ro/Gratuit/gqydimzy/normacu-privire-la-fabricarea-continutul-ambalarea-etichetarea-si-calitatea-fainii-de-grau-destinate-comercializarii-pentru-consum-uman-din-14062002>
16. <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocument/39731>

TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE VOCATIONAL TRAINING BY DECREASING PUPIL DROPOUT RATES

I. CSEH-PAPP^{1*}, T. WIWCZAROSKI², T. CSAPÓNÉ RISKÓ³

¹ Szent István University, Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences, Gödöllő, Hungary

^{2,3} University of Debrecen, Faculty of Economics and Business, Debrecen, Hungary

*Corresponding author: papp.imola@gtk.szie.hu

Abstract: *One of the criteria of economic development is a sustainable labour market, which is determined by the development of social consciousness and education. The acquiring of expertise increases the immaterial capital of the individual and also contributes to the reduction of social inequalities. Most of the current educational systems and policies are neither sustainable nor effective. They cannot reach their own stated educational goals and they are rather expensive. The outstanding problem of vocational training is the high dropout rate since vocational schools have become, in many cases, an educational sphere used as a catch-all for disadvantaged pupils. Dropping out is a complex problem, which cannot be solved only by the regulation of education. Regulation should involve prevention, intervention and compensation measures. The proviso of prevention, that teachers should identify pupils in danger of dropping out as soon as possible, is based on timely recognition of visible signs in such pupils. This study investigates possible ways to keep those pupils enrolled and active in vocational training programs - both with extremely high (agricultural) and low (economics) dropout rates. As a research question, we investigated whether by studying the backgrounds, attitudes, skills and competences of pupils, those pupils could be identified at the beginning who need and are worthy of special care. The results proved the assumption.*

Keywords: *dropout, vocational school, prevention, labor market.*

1. Introduction

The educational attainment level of the population of the European Union has been continuously increasing, although the continuous reproduction of a remarkable group with low educational attainment level can always be noted [12]. The number of people not finishing primary school before the age 16 is high, but the number of people not continuing their studies after primary school or starting secondary studies and that has been dropping out, for any reason, is even higher. The main reason for dropouts leaving their educational systems should be searched for in the school system which it is not prepared to accept and teach pupils with different problems. These pupils' abilities to learn soon stagnate in the education system, their basic abilities are not developed properly by the school. In such cases, these pupils become frustrated and their classmates may even ostracize them. Subsequently, they turn away from school and refuse to study. Another, more serious problem with pupils leaving school with only low education levels is that they will

probably face permanent exclusion from the labour market.

2. Theoretical background

The definition of a dropout is not clear, whether in Hungarian or in international literature. A dropout can refer to a status, i.e. when someone does not continue his studies. However, it can refer to an event, as well, since it can be linked to a certain time. Dropping out can even be interpreted as a process, since it includes the features of school leaving [7].

The Europe 2020 strategy sets out a target of reducing early school drop-out rates to less than 10 % and increasing the share of the population aged 30-34 having completed tertiary education to at least 40 % by 2020.

There is a new term introduced by the European Union: **early school leaving** (ESL). The term is clear: it is defined by the proportion of the population aged 18-24 with only lower secondary education or less and no longer in education or training. They are therefore those who have only achieved pre-primary, primary,

lower secondary or a short upper secondary education of less than 2 years (ISCED 0, 1, 2 or 3c short), and include those who have only a pre-vocational or vocational education which did not lead to an upper secondary certification.

Another indicator, applied mainly by the OECD, has come into view recently: the so-called **NEET**¹, which represents the share of young people who are not in employment, education or training, as a percentage of the total number of young people in the 15-24 age group. The indicator, which represents the percentage of endangered youth in the labour market, has been appointed by the Employment Committee (EMCO) as an indicator of the community's employment policy in 2010. It is more complex than that of ESL, since it focuses on the next step, successful labour market integration or draws attention to the danger of its failure. This indicator measures the percentage of youth where the transition from education to labour market is realised with difficulties or not realised at all, so the chance remaining on the margins of society for a lifetime and needing social care is increasing. In Hungary, this indicator also includes youths who have dropped out of the education system and not present in the labour market or adult education system.

A new proposition of the strategic documents of the European Union is the introduction of "**drop out vs. push out**" terms [13]. These terms distinguish whether pupils have dropped out of the education system or whether the educational system and its learning environment "pushed them out". In other words, pupils feel forced to quit school, since they felt that they could not be integrated into the educational programmes and into the greater societies they were having to learn in, especially as regards social norms and acceptable learning habits [5].

Dropping out of vocational schools **affects several social actors** (pupil, parent, teacher, institution, and governing body). There is a consensus among each of these actors that the number of dropouts has to be reduced, but their interests regarding avoiding and preventing them from quitting school.

It is common in most published studies (focusing on the nature of dropping out) that in terms of dropping out, the **pupil** is the main actor for whom dropping out means an escape from failures, unpleasant experiences and humiliations.

The child does not know the risks of quitting school. Even if the pupil has heard such stories from the parents, it does not affect the child's decisions, since the consequences of quitting school on the rest of one's life are not clear to the child. Dangers forecasted for the distant future do not affect their decisions [10]. In one survey, two thirds of former pupils named themselves as the person responsible for their dropping out. From one point of view, this finding is positive, since pupils recognise their responsibility and do not try to blame someone else. Acceptance of responsibility is one of the prerequisites for a responsible way of life in the future. However, from another point of view, it is not good to accept the role of the "scapegoat", as doing so can lead to the unjust conclusion which says: if pupils studied a little bit more and behaved better, the problems would be far less [10].

Fehérvári (2008) makes a distinction between two bigger groups of dropped out pupils. One group includes those youths who can be easily integrated back into the education system - with certain assistance - since they want to get a job and qualifications but somehow they wound up not learning in the right school and studying for the wrong profession. The other group includes those who do not want to finish their studies entirely. Most of them originate from poorly educated families. Their dropping out means that they probably will not climb higher even by one step on the social ladder than their parents. Dropouts cannot be considered as a homogenous group, thus a uniform method cannot be implemented to solve their problems.

Parents are also aware of the serious consequences of dropping out; yet, in many cases, actually appear to support their children's' quitting school. The reasons they most often give for their support is the claim that they only hear about emotional conflicts, problems, and school failures of their children once it has become too late. In other words, they miss any chance for intervention. Moreover, parents visit their children's' schools rarely or do not visit them at all, saving themselves from many inconveniences and, at the same time, from being able to prevent their child from making bad decisions. While the responsibility for the failure of parents-school communication cannot be passed entirely onto the parents, their partial responsibility remains obvious [11,16]. Some teachers explain away a child's low performance at school by pointing to the improper child-rearing practices of parents. Parents are aware of this attitude and this is the

¹ NEET is the abbreviation of Not in Employment, Education or Training

reason why most of them are hostile to the school and teachers, resulting in their avoiding visiting their children's schools.

Teachers also have responsibility in what is happening to children [2,8]. A child can fail, change classes or school. The teacher often identifies that a child has a problem, but since cooperating with the family, colleagues or experts takes time, the teacher does not intervene. The passive attitude of teachers is rather common [11]. Fluctuation of teachers in weaker schools is permanent [14]. Such schools often hire beginner teachers, but in a couple of years, the more talented teachers look for another job, leaving the schools weaker still. Thus these schools are being selected on the basis of the "quality" of teachers, as well. The per capita method of financing **schools** keeps schools interested in maintaining pupil enrolment numbers, but it does not mean obviously keeping them in a certain programme or class. Schools are more apt to release than to keep problematic children, or they exchange the most problematic children among schools, under a tacit agreement². The problem can be solved in a different way, as well. Such children can be taken out of a normal class and placed in a catch-up group, where they will not disturb the work of the other children and teacher any more. Actually, in such groups, progress in learning is rare. The traditional, ordinary operation of institutions requires scarce resources, less cooperation between teachers and institutions, less effort for preventing and managing conflicts. In most schools, neither pedagogical nor methodological renewal are common [1]. The human resource conditions of vocational schools do not favour the reduction of dropouts, since in many schools (lack of human resource) even delivering the professional courses in a proper way causes substantial problems. Hiring experts with non-pedagogic degrees (psychologist, socio-psychologist) is even rare [6]. Experiences show that vocational schools not only do not employ such experts; they do not even use their assistance [6, 15,16].

3. The empirical research

Based on the secondary research, it can be supposed that cooperation is needed by the concerned parties (family, school) in reducing dropout rates through prevention. The following

² Remark: Now it is not common through the reduction of the compulsory school age.

questions have been formed as research questions: If the supposition above is correct, is there any difference in the opinion of the concerned parties (parent, pupil, and head teacher) in the cases of schools with high and low dropout rates, as well as how the concerned parties see the school life of pupils.

The extreme labour shortage in the Hungarian processing industry and agriculture provides the basis and actuality of the survey. One of the possible ways of balancing the labour shortage is the prevention of dropout of vocational schools.

The objective of the questionnaires set up after studying the national and international literature was to collect the opinions of parents, pupils and head teachers per pupil.

Each questionnaire included 20-20 questions, and respondents could give their answers on a Likert scale 1-7.

The survey was carried out in the vocational schools (2 agricultural vocational schools with high dropout rate and 2 economic vocational schools with low dropout rate) of 2-2 large towns. Four schools were selected, on the basis of their geographical location and personal contacts, in 2017. The negative attitude of each school leader was conspicuous. The survey focused on the 9th grade class, but because of the improper attitude (pupil – parent – head teacher) only a small part of the questionnaires was appropriate to be processed and evaluated (5 pairs per school). It caused a further problem that for each child all the filled in questionnaires should have been available (parent, head teacher and pupil). Thus, the survey has been carried out on the basis of 60 filled in questionnaires.

4. Results

There were differences in the average values of the parents', pupils' and head teachers' answers in the cases of schools with high and low dropout rates. The smallest difference can be seen in the answers of pupils (economic vocational school: 4.85, agricultural vocational school: 4.60), then in the answers of parents (4.57 and 4.20). The difference was conspicuous regarding the answers of the head teachers (5.20 and 3.88) (Table 1). Results show that head teachers perceive the most clearly the differences among pupils in agricultural and economic vocational schools, while pupils perceive these differences the least. When processing the results, it has been revealed that there were some statements for all the three target groups, which received the

highest values independent of the dropout rate of the school.

These uniform statements:

- Pupils feel in both vocational school types that they have to learn too much theory. This statement received the highest value (7) in economic vocational schools, and a somewhat lower value (6.2) in the agricultural vocational schools.
- Parents believe that their children have friends in the school (6.1).
- Head teachers believe that pupils get personal recognition from their teachers; however, there are differences in the received average values (economic vocational school: 5.9, agricultural vocational school: 5).

Table 2 shows the different average values for the two vocational school types.

It is a rather clear difference between the two school types that one of the statements with the highest average values was that the parent had success at school in the case of economic vocational schools, while in the case of agricultural vocational schools with the highest dropout rate, the statement that the parent was anxious at school got the highest value.

It can also be stated that there were statements for all the three target groups which received the **lowest values** both in the economic and agricultural vocational school.

These uniform statements:

- Pupils believe in both vocational schools that they do not have family problems. (economic vocational school: 1.8, agricultural vocational: 2.1). This can indicate that parents hide this from their child or that the children are ashamed to admit it.
- On the basis of the parents' responses, they do not help their children in studying (economic vocational school: 1.6, agricultural vocational school: 1.8).

Average values of the responses for both school types can be seen in Table 3.

Independent of school type, the lowest value from pupils was received for the statement which says that there are family problems at home, while from parents for the statement which says that they help their children in studying.

Regarding the latter statement, pupils in economic vocational schools have the same opinion. In agricultural vocational schools, both from the side of parents and pupils, school failures are obvious, which is confirmed by the head teacher through recognising the diligence and interest of pupils towards theoretical classes.

In economic vocational schools, parents do not use punitive parenting practices for bad grades or absenteeism; however, based on the responses of head teachers, pupils do not miss classes unjustifiably.

All the three questionnaires included the statement: *Teachers often help pupils*. Regarding the responses of pupils, parents and head teachers, the difference was around 1 point both in the cases of agricultural and economic vocational schools. It is an interesting result that both pupils and parents rated the help of teachers the same, while it got a higher ranking from head teachers in both school types (Table 4).

The opinions on the help from teachers shows some differences regarding economic and agricultural vocational schools and the opinion of the head teacher shows the highest value.

There was another statement in each questionnaire: *The pupil willingly goes to his current school*. The average of the received values was almost 5, thus there is not any difference among the three actors and the two school types on this matter.

There was a rather big overlap between the questionnaires of the **parents** and **pupils**. One of the common statements: The pupil willingly goes to school, likes studying. Both parents and pupils had to evaluate this statement. The average of values was almost in case of both parties and school types. Consequently, in this matter, there is not any difference between the economic and agricultural vocational schools, and the responses of parents and pupils.

The responses were different concerning *school failures and success* (Table 5). Pupils believe they have less failures than their parents believe. Furthermore in agricultural vocational schools, parents evaluated school failures nearly 2 points higher than in economic vocational schools. The results are similar in the case of school success: pupils evaluated school success higher than their parents, but regarding the two school types, the average of values was higher in the economic vocational schools than in the agricultural vocational schools.

Regarding school failures and success, the results between the two school types are rather different. The **questionnaire of parents and head teachers** included 4 common statements, for which different evaluations has been received. *Parents rather regularly attend parents' meetings* in both school types, reading the responses of parents and head teachers (average value: economic vocational school: head teacher:

6.1, parents: 6.2. average value: agricultural vocational school: head teacher: 5.2, parents: 5.3. Only a slight difference can be noticed between the two school types.

Regarding the responses of parents, the average values for the statement: *Continuously checking the grades of pupil* are rather different in the two school types (economic: 6.3, agricultural: 3.9), while in the case of head teachers the averages are the same: 5. In the economic vocational schools, parents evaluated higher their checking role, while in the agricultural vocational schools, the evaluation of head teachers is higher.

Similar differences and averages can be seen regarding the *absenteeism of pupils*. In the case of parents, they are different (economic: 6.2, agricultural: 4) while for head teachers, the averages are the same: 5.

Considerably different results have been received in connection with *theoretical and practical classes* between **pupils and head teachers** and between the responses of pupils for the two school types.

In economic vocational schools, pupils do not believe they have too many *practical classes* (1.5), and the opinion of head teachers is similar: they perceive that pupils are interested in practical classes (5.9). In agricultural vocational schools, pupils believe they have moderately too many practical classes (3.4), while the head teachers perceive that pupils are interested in practical classes (5.1). Thus, in agricultural vocational schools, attitudes towards practical classes are perceived differently by the pupils and head teachers. The evaluation of *theoretical classes* also shows differences: pupils believe they have too many theoretical classes in both school types (economic vocational school: 7, agricultural vocational school: 6.2). Nonetheless, the interest of pupils towards theoretical classes has been evaluated by the head teachers as 5.1 in the economic vocational schools, and 2.9 in the agricultural vocational schools.

There is a considerable difference between the two school types: in the economic vocational schools, pupils believe they have too many theoretical classes and this opinion is the opposite that of the evaluation of head teachers.

This result can be reasoned by the discipline and diligence of pupils. The differences are similar between the responses of the pupils and head teachers in the agricultural vocational schools as well, which is also related to the behaviour of pupils.

In the questionnaire designed for parents, there was a question about the labour market status of the respondent. The differences are rather conspicuous, since the parents of economic vocational school pupils mainly work (80%) in their studied profession, while most of the parents of agricultural vocational school pupils (with high dropout rate) do not work in their studied profession (60%) and some of them (10%) are unemployed.

5. Conclusions

After studying the national and international literature on the dropout problems of vocational schools, the empirical research explored different results in the studied vocational schools with high and low dropout rates. The results hint that with studying the characteristics of pupils, the group threatened by dropout pupils could be identified.

The survey discovered that parents, pupils and teachers perceive the school life of children differently. Head teachers perceive the differences among the children the most clearly, while pupils the least clearly in the vocational schools with high and low dropout rates. It also has been explored that sometimes the evaluation of head teachers considerably differs from that of the parents or students - even in the same school. Consequently, it would be reasonable to focus on the evaluation of the head teachers when predicting a pupil's dropping out. Evaluation of the help from the teachers shows a slight difference between the two school types and the average of values of the head teachers stands out. Threatening problems can be identified even in the small sample size. On the one hand, school time memories of parents are rather different in the two school types. On the other hand, school failures can be identified from the perspective of both parents and pupils in agricultural vocational schools. Moreover, there are also considerable differences in the labour market status of the parents. Contrary to the statements found in published literature, pupils feel good at school, and the phenomenon of career choice constraint, as well as previous school failures, cannot be detected. Still, these results can even depend on the small sample size. Based on the secondary and empirical research, as a **summary**, it can be stated that the role of teachers is indisputable in the prevention of pupil dropout of vocational schools and prevention can be effective only through cooperation (teacher, parent, social

worker, psychologist, health visitor, child welfare specialist) and with the earliest intervention. Prospective practical outcome of the survey could be an action plan worked out by specialists

in education research, building on the opinions of head teachers, focusing on the prevention of pupils dropping out of vocational schools.

Table 1: The average (1-7) of questionnaire results filled in the different schools

	Opinion of parents	Opinion of pupils	Opinion of head teachers	Average
Economic vocational school	4.57	4.85	5.20	4.87
Agricultural vocational school	4.20	4.60	3.88	4.23
Average	4.39	4.73	4.54	

Source: Own research, 2017

Table 2: Statements with the highest average values (1-7)

Agricultural school	Economic school
Opinion of pupils:	
The pupil is aware of the employment opportunities of his profession 6.4	The parents are interested in what and how they study 6.1
Opinion of parents:	
The parent was anxious at school 5.8	The parent was successful at school 6.2
Opinion of head teachers:	
The pupil is interested in practical classes 5.1	The parent regularly attends parent's meetings 6.1

Source: Own research, 2017

Table 3: Statements with the lowest average values (1-7) for the two school types

Agricultural school	Economic school
Opinion of pupils:	
The pupil feels that he has failures at school 3.1	Someone helps the pupil in studying 2.1
Opinion of parents:	
The parent feels that he was supported by his teachers 2.8	The parent uses punitive parenting practices for bad grades or absenteeism 1.9
Opinion of head teachers:	
The pupil is interested in theoretical classes 2.9	The pupil unjustifiably misses the classes 2.1
The pupil is diligent 3	

Source: Own research, 2017

Table 4: Teachers often help pupils at school (1-7)

	Responses of parents	Responses of pupils	Responses of head teachers
Economic vocational school	4.9	5	5.9
Agricultural vocational school	3.9	3.8	5.1

Source: Own research, 2017

Table 5: Evaluation of school failures and success (1-7)

Failure	Opinion of parents	Opinion of pupils
Economic school	3.2	2.1
Agricultural school	5.1	3.1
Success	Opinion of parents	Opinion of pupils
Economic school	4.9	5.9
Agricultural school	3.1	5.2

Source: Own research, 2017

References

1. Cseh Papp, I., Csapóné Riskó, T.: *Agricultural vocational training and the labour market in Hungary*, Economic Affairs, 1, 2014, pp 1-10;
2. Davis, K. S., Dupper, D. R. : *Student-teacher relationships: An overlooked factor in school dropout*, Journal of human behavior in the social environment, 9(1-2), 2004, pp. 179-193;
3. Europe 2020 target: *Early leavers from education and training*, http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/pdf/themes/29_early_school_leaving.pdf accessed: 4 December 2015;
4. EUROSTAT [http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Glossary:Early leaver from education and training](http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Glossary:Early_leaver_from_education_and_training), accessed: 22 June 2016;
5. Fallis, R. K., Opatow, S.: *Are students failing school or are schools failing students? Class cutting in high school*. Journal of Social Issues, 59(1), 2003, pp. 103-119;
6. Fehérvári, A.: *Lemorzsolódás a szakiskolákban – egy empirikus kutatás tapasztalatai*. In: Szakképzés és lemorzsolódás. Szerk. Fehérvári A. Budapest: Oktatókutató és Fejlesztő Intézet, 2008, pp. 162–276;
7. Fehérvári, A.: *A lemorzsolódás és a korai iskolaelhagyás trendjei*. Neveléstudomány, 2015, 3: pp. 31-47;
8. Gilligan, R.: *The importance of schools and teachers in child welfare*. Child Family Social Work, 3(1), 1998, pp. 13-25;
9. Juhász, J., Mihályi K.: *A pedagógus kulcsszerepe a középfokú oktatásból történő lemorzsolódás megelőzését célzó jelző- és pedagógiai támogató rendszerben hazai és nemzetközi példák alapján*, 2015, Neveléstudomány 3: pp. 17-30;
10. Liskó, I. : *Kudarcok a középfokú iskolákban*. Budapest. Oktatókutató Intézet, 2003, 102 p;
11. Mártonfi, Gy. : *A lemorzsolódás problémája a magyar szakképzésben és szakképzéspolitikában*. In: Szerk. Fehérvári A.: Szakképzés és lemorzsolódás. Budapest. OFI., 2008, pp. 132–161;
12. Muiyiwa, B., Okeke, E. P.I: *Sustainable development and self-reliance: The role of technical and vocational education and training*. Journal of Educational Review. Jan-Jun 2017, Vol. 10 Issue 1/2, pp. 53-61;
13. Oomen, A., Plant, P: *Early School Leaving and Lifelong Guidance. ELGPN Concept Note No. 6* <http://www.elgpn.eu/publications/browse-by-language/english/elgpn-concept-note-no.-6-early-school-leaving-and-lifelong-guidance/>. accessed: 12 November 2015;
14. Széll, K.: *Iskolai eredményesség a hátrányos helyzet tükrében*. Educatio, 2015, 1: pp.140-147;
15. Vidal, E. I., Romero, C. S., Arredondo, S. C. : *The community dimension as a factor to prevent school dropout*. Journal for Educators, Teachers and Trainers, 8(1) , 2017, pp. 214-225;
16. Zoller, M.: *A társadalmi és tudásbeli esélyegyenlőtlenségek ördögi köre, Hátrányos helyzetű családok, fiatalok és iskolák Magyarországon* <http://rmsz.ro/uploaded/tiny/files/magiszter/2012/osz/04.pdf>, 2012, accessed: 2 September 2015.

THEORY OF BIO-HARMONISM

R. GRUIA¹

¹ Transilvania University of Brasov - Workstation of CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy; Corresp.Member of Academy of Romanian Scientist;
Email: ecotec@unitbv.ro ;

„The secret of changing is to concentrate all our energy not on the fight against the OLD, but on building the NEW”

Socrates
(470-399 BC)

Abstract: *The study starts from the hypothesis that a profound disturbing confrontation with the limits of the capacity to support the planet seems inevitable in this century. Though, first this crisis has solutions of ideational order and may coherently be fought against with a new theory, with a kind of global initiation at a new level of economic, psycho-social human and political development. There is proposed a diagnose demarche of the reality perceived at present, in a new approach, the ideas, principles and concepts of numerous scripts being gathered in a new coherent theory that defines a special method to analyze and synthesize information processing, offering solutions through „bioharmonization” mechanisms and sustaining, complementarily to other ideas, the direction of economic and socio-cultural development towards Knowledge Society and even towards Conscience Society. The paper objectives have in view, from empiric observation up to scientifically elaborate analyses and with cultural-philosophical nuances, to establish the principles and methodology of the Bio-Harmonism Theory, the action manner as bases to interpret and find solutions against today’s world disharmonies, including with applications in a transition period and to establish the favorable frame in order to find equilibrium elements by contributions to contemporary reconceptualization supported by science, technology and intelligent management.*

Keywords: *bioharmony, fractal, information, integrative, knowledge.*

1. Introduction

Today perceived reality, besides life beauty and joys within mankind achievement context, we become more and more aware, and more and more of us do it, that things do not only go towards a happy direction, but there appear more and more deep disharmonies. Since the year 2000, contemporary global society has been in a period of paradigm passing, dominated by a theoretic (and not only) cleavage from postmodern paradigm (of methodological individualism and programmed deconstruction) towards a trans modern paradigm centered on frontier integration and spiritualization, both political ones, and cultural, scientific etc. ones, having as a dominant a constructionist model based on global negotiation of interpretation.

Such a model is based on the method of *constructionist-fractal analyses* that paradigmatically identifies certain cultural,

epistemic or social axioms in concordance with the proposed paradigmatic model [8,19,36,39,50]. Among the identified axioms, the more important for the proposed demarche are: *the ontological presupposition* (transdisciplinary knowledge by the I, E, S ontological triad, with the representation of the supreme archetype), *the gnosiological presupposition* (with the signification of the idea of „reality” through the new paradigm of physics) and *the semiotic presupposition* (reality is a „sign” of existence, by maintaining consciousness within the patterns of a reality map).

In ontological presupposition, in conformity with the constructionist-fractal model, Meta-Universe is a fractal hierarchy of the *supreme archetype* representation on different existence levels. Transdisciplinary knowledge aims a multidimensional approach of language unity, under the form of a constructionist (i.e. a negotiation of interpretations). It is not that the

world itself is a construct, but the image (map) is such a construct (Sandu, A., 2011).

Fractal thinking allows science be constructionistically approached, namely by „fragments” which, through certain mechanisms may be „linked” and thus finalize the puzzle of the given system (the map). At the same time we point out **integronic thinking**, with the dynamics of multiple integrations in a variable, adaptable succession and that, in special conditions, leads to emergence, to the coming out of a superior order new, no matter the typology of the given complex system [28]. In essence, the *Perceived reality* approaches by twinning fractal thinking and the integronic one give birth to a new theory

that is proposed by the paper. We consider that this theory may be a necessary „brick” for the transaction towards the types of human society described by the specialty literature, namely: *The Knowledge Society* and then, *The Conscience Society* [1, 4, 16, 43, 52, 54].

For such an approach, it is essential to be aware of the world evolution in the past, in the present and the future hypothesis (fig.1), especially that another world is foreseen, with a new vision, because as father Stăniloae used to say (quoted by Munteanu, Fl., 2015) „today's mankind is theologically worn out”, which imposes in itself a new approach.

Fig. 1. Stages of mankind evolution

A first observation shows us that we are making for a time of intense planetary compression. It is very likely that within a lifetime from now, the world may become an „overheated pressure cooker” in which the human family is crushed by combined merciless forces of the world population growth, of a destabilized global climate, of reduced reserves of non regenerating energy and of in growth pollution. We therefore observe that the circle

has closed and there is no way out. These forces are so merciless, and the stress they lay upon our world is extreme, that human civilization will either come down in chaos or will spirally rise in a process of profound transformation [3]., which sustains the opportunity for new theories with potential to counteract a new disastrous (disharmonic) denouement to appear.

The **Bio-Harmonism Theory** has the valence to contribute to a positive scenario by an

approach from a new angle, able to sustain the perspective desire, the one towards the Knowledge Society. This one, as it is known, progressively replaces the industrial society, which one has replaced, at its turn, the agrarian one, the last ones being centered on material value production. The knowledge society is the one where INFORMATION means power, in the most general meaning – no matter if it is about the political, the economic, the financial one, Information (I) getting, mastering and superior valorizing being thus this society's keystone [52]. Information (I), with all its forms and meanings, up to the most abstract and even untouchable ones, such as love, truth and primordial information, constitutes in fact the profound conceptual axes of the present theory too.

2. Conceptual and pragmatic methodology

The approach manner in elaborating the theory sums up many concepts that are to be found in the zone of *harmonized inflexion between analyses and syntheses*, as a principle, respectively between *fragmentation* and *aggregation*, or between: FRACTAL and INTEGRONIC.

The methodology of FRACTAL analyses - a fractal („broken”, „fractured”) is a fragmented or snapped geometric figure that may be divided in parts, so that every part of these ones (approximately at least) may be a miniature copy of the entire [39,56]. there may be easily found fractals in nature, in biologic reality of the *Living and Life in its whole* („bio-”, „the bios”), in society and art, becoming the *analyses* bases of processes and phenomena, including the non linear ones (example: agricultural and urban *modules* in ecosystem structures).

The applied methodology, by the INTEGRONIC demarche (integronics, as a science of system coexistence, based on the General Theory of Integration - Henstock,R.,1991, Bartie,R.G.,2001) studies processes of multiple integration and their composing elements (respectively integrated systems), thus representing the component of *synthesis* processes of the described theory [26]. The integronic dynamics consists of a flow of successive integrations that, under special conditions (syncretic, synchronic, synergic ones) lead to emergent effects, with the emergence of

the superior order *NEW*. (example: the bounce from *Intelligence* to *Wisdom*).

3. Debates and arguments

May there really be a unifying theory of many concepts in the harmonization idea? Or we are rather talking about a chimera? Following Stephen Hawking's logics of principle (2014), there seem to be three possibilities: (a) There really exists an integrated and unitary theory that will be finalized only when there will exist a mathematical model plausible enough from all the points of view, that may render reality abstract and bioharmonize things, processes and phenomena at all levels; (b) A doubtless finalization will not be reached, but there remain only a number of ideas, concepts and principles that more and more precisely describe things; (c) There exists in fact no bioharmonization theory, so that aspects and events accidentally happen.

There would be people to sustain the third variant, considering that the one behind events would be God, who „knows” what to harmonize and what not to.

Others would support the second variant in the idea that there always exists a degree of uncertainty. But we strongly believe that the first variant is to be sustained, given the *Reality perceived today*, respectively the model of the *Living Planet*, climate changes etc., that cannot be contested, and the convergence of many concepts and triumph of human reason „*not to saw off the bough on which we are sitting*” and to save life and civilization on Terra, are priority and saving. And these ones not anyhow, but by creativity, maximized efficiency, equilibrium and harmony, all these imposing to formulate a bioharmonism theory.

In short, „bioharmonism” basic ideas refer to the awareness and approach on deeper and deeper steps of the axes „*simple - complicated - complex*”, i.e. from order (linearity) to disorder (nonlinearity), successively following: - the planetary structure and definition of Bio-Harmonism Theory; - theory specificity and general objectives; - bioharmonism and new ontological frame; consolidation through concrete steps in remodeling reality by bioharmonism (acting upon disorder, solving its causes, in conflict situations, aiming harmony); establishing the theory pragmatic frame (exemplification of certain applicable directions).

3.1. The new conceptual approach and definition of the idea of Bio-Harmonism

Numerous concepts, principles and rules that have appeared along time show deep preoccupations concerning decoding the mysteries of the living world and life in general,

in its amazing and little understood complexity, especially in relation to man and to society, to the evolution of human civilization [2,4,6,18,22,]. Among all these, in our opinion, 4 conceptual groups have a major impact in the processes of systemic harmonization, having as a common factor the Living (*bio*) and the Complex Life (fig.2).

CONCEPTUAL ELEMENTS FOR A NEW APPROACH MANNER OF THE WORLD ARE LIVING IN

Fig. 2. Conceptual groups that lead towards the coherence of the Bio-Harmonism Theory

Before describing the theory, it is opportune to analyze a series of aspects that

aim the semantics and definition of the concept of „BIO-HARMONISM“:

BIO- (BIOS-) – „life, living being“. ◊ Gr. bios „life“ > Fr. bio-, Germ. id., Engl. id., It. id. > Rom. bio-; (1). The world fundamental mark at the scale of the present development embodying the living and life after Nature's nonlinear model; (2). In informatics BIOS is low level software, being the first program that scrolls when the computer starts.

HARMONISM -

- *initial meaning*: HARMONISM s. v. *Fourierism*. = FOURIERISM -. French socialist utopist doctrine from the first half of the 19th century, that criticizes the capitalist structure and stipulates the creation of the socialist society by peaceful propagation of the ideas concerning the new form of social production organization; falansterianism, garantism. [Pron. *fu-ri-e*. / < Fr. *fouriérisme*, cf. *Ch. Fourier* – French utopist socialist]. Noun Fourierism.

- *the present meaning*: HARMONISM, in the meaning of the present theory of the 21st century = *Idea* based on methods and means to put into concordance the parts with the entire, so that the elements (of value ones, of hierarchy ones, etc.) may match and be in concordance with Reality's balanced diversity and with holism on integrated systemic levels.

We are therefore speaking about a new concept that represents a *totally different harmonism* (we mention that we do NOT speak about the idea of „NEO-HARMONISM” because it is NOT a new utopist harmonism with preponderantly social and collectivist valences), so that, by joining the

prefix „*BIO-*,” as a particle put before the word with the present meaning of „*HARMONISM*” to form another word with an original semantic aura, namely: **BIO-HARMONISM**, with the definition from the below case.

BIO-HARMONISM is a concept with a large meaning regarding *Reality's* balanced diversity and society's holistic organization, based on putting the parts into concordance with the entire, in the idea to understand the world (as a part and as a whole) in relation to Nature's complex model, having the *Living* („*bio*”) as essential mark and *Life* with contemporary connections and economic and socio-cultural models.

The concept of Bio-Harmonism may develop a theory applicable to today's world, becoming aware of Reality in a specific manner. Therefore, the **bio-harmonist dynamics** methodologically refers to the new approach, by *turning over the present reversed pyramid*

towards the pyramid of the future decade sustainable model. In fact now it is covered a transition period from the biologic-informational society and the one of the 4th industrial revolution towards the Knowledge Society, with bioharmonized cycles and flows (fig.3).

BLOCK SCHEME OF BIOHARMONISM CYCLES

Fig. 3. *Man's influence by the bioharmonization idea upon systemic elements and cycles at local and individual, group or national and global level or the one of the civilization in its whole*

From the complexity of what has been related there results the coherence of certain concepts and fact situation concatenation that sustain the

idea of Bio-Harmonism and the theory it is developing:

BIO-HARMONISM THEORY (BHT) refers to a series of concepts that put into concordance and in a new order the creation of humanity (that has got to a crucial moment) with the nonlinear „planetary model”, by paradigm change concerning the ontical triad, contouring a new economic and socio-cultural model, taking as a mark the *Living and Life* in its complexity („*the bios*”), in a *harmonization* dynamics based on methods and means of analyses and synthesis by fractal and integronic models, tending towards systemic efficacy and dynamic equilibrium, necessary in order to understand and factually achieve, in a first period, the *Knowledge Society* and, on long term, the transition towards the *Society forerunning the Conscience Society*.

We need to mention that, in order to get an appropriate solution, the Bio-Harmonism Theory that has been described in synthesis above, must be modeled at all three demographic levels: individual, population (ex.: nation), civilization (the whole planetary globe), or administrative: local, regional, global. *Bioharmonization* has in view system networks at every level. For „macro” levels, networks and hubs are relatively easy to be followed while at individual level (where it is difficult to change mentalities) there are also taken into consideration social and psychological relations, with afferent biotransformations.

3.2. Bio-Harmonism Theory specificity and conceptual mechanism

First of all, in order to contour a coherent theory, we start from the need to generate a new ontological frame [13,30,31,35]. Thus, as a consequence of **Information (I)** overwhelming role in relation to Substance (S) and Energy (E), it comes out that the triad Substance-Energy-

Information is more and more confirmed as existence fundamental matrix. *The analysis of the concomitant „refinement” of the three dimensions (I, E, S, but also relation to Space-Time) in principle represents the bases of the HARMONIZATION process.* The process allows ordering elements that thus get the potentiality to model *Reality (with all its nuances)* in a megaproject. As modeling aspect, the mentioned process may be associated to the swinging dynamics between two natural tendencies [44]., analyses and synthesis, respectively: **analyses** - generating bifurcations, of "schisms" through which the number of classes in which *Reality* is formally divided increases and **syntheses** – seen as a unification process, of restriction of the number of these classes.

The principle of „analyses and syntheses” has a peculiar specificity in the bioharmonic approach by applying *fractal methods* and, respectively, *integronic* ones (table 1).

Table 1 Typology of the analyses and synthesis methods
In bio-harmonism theory

ANALYSES: - fractal principles and methods <i>Fractal and constructal model</i>	SYNTHESES: - integronic principles and methods <i>General integronic model</i>
<p>Fractals are ANALYSES extraordinary forms and models created with the help of mathematics equations. A fractal intuitive definition shows that a fractal is a fragmented or broken geometric form that may be divided in parts, so that every part of these ones may be (approximately at least) a miniature copy of the whole.</p> <p>The word „fractal” has been introduced by the</p>	<p>The future provocations presuppose to consider the entire („general picture”), to holistically understand things, to unify classes and make bioharmonized models, i.e. the cooperation of parts when the entire acquires new, unexpected properties, so that, through successive integrations (having as a result optimization, efficiency etc.), <i>emergency</i> is released, appearing the New of superior order, i.e.</p>

mathematician **Benoit Mandelbrot** in the year 1975 and comes from the Latin word „*fractus*”, meaning broken or fractured.

Complementarily, the **constructal law** [7] refers to a universal phenomenon from nature: generation of running configurations. Both through living organisms and through lifeless physical structures circulate different fluids: water, air, sap, blood, electric and thermal flows. In their transit, fluids tend to flow easier, on higher access ways. The law says that, „*in order that a macroscopic system of finite size may survive in time, its configuration must evolve so that it may offer the best access for the streams that are flowing through it*”.

- As fractal examples that may be analyzed in the bioharmonization idea there are nonlinear processes and phenomena: **Sierpinski Triangle**, **Koch's snowdrop**, fractals from nature, fractals and chaos theory etc.
- Analyses through **Quantum Physics**, Mandelbrot's **Fractal geometry**, Thom and Haken's **Synergetic**, Bak's **Theory of self-organized criticism** and others lead to reformulate Reality from a new angle.

If we analyze „information”, because the problem is not its lack, but its approach and processing manner (!), maybe the fractal and constructal principles are to be also found in the informational flows and networks. In fact, there is first aimed a new thinking manner, of formative, educational process, „**Mind Building**”, that becomes human creativity resource and capitalization.

Bioharmonization extracts certain ideational and methodological elements offers by the **Complexity paradigm** with its nuances of chaos and order [13,43].

The approach level of **bioharmonization analyses** slides from microcosms to macrocosms. To this effect, it becomes relevant the example that: after the principles of the Complexity science, decoding the human brain is the first step for Universe decoding.

At „macro” level, global disorder practically imposes the genesis of an approach of disciplinary integration that leads to the fact that a new point of view, a new Reality is born, that becomes more and more „visible” by

integronic dynamics.

As for example, the process of SYNTHESIS is of interest in the bioharmonist development, also offered by the **Ecoemergetic Theory** [24] as a methodological implementation of problem based on the eco-energetic analyses or of the eMergetic method [49], of the concept of cultural energy [12], the one of energetic externality [48], all of them complementary with the approach focalized on the Information (I) direction from *integronic processes*, first of all applied in management and in biology (genetics).

The general objectives of the complex system management (of the type of Environment-Economy Systems, of ecosystems, of agro ecosystems, of the agro-forest-pasture space, of agro-rural or urban systems etc.) have in view to elaborate and develop a model of broad management, that may lead to optimized efficiency and efficacy of the zone where there are integrated different types of organizations and especially economic units with a strong impact upon natural and social environment.

There is distinguished a management model applicable to the concept of sustainable development. There is taken account of the **biological** (including biodiversity) and **ecological** administration of the territorial landscape in function of its **geographic** nature (i.e. in a „*bio-eco-geo*” scientific demarche), integrated in perspective models, as for example those of **modular agriculture** (Gruia, R., 2010). Practically such models aim to follow modalities to achieve punctual objectives, such as for example food products got through methods and techniques of the **ecosanogeneses concept** [23], but also necessary resources, financing sources, achievement deadlines of the objectives, etc., everything in conformity with applied management at enterprise level. There are pre established objectives that take into consideration to apply a management based on the programmatic of piloting organizations integrated in themselves (see organizational capacity), but also successively, in the business environment (socio-economic) and in the surrounding environment. This dynamics imposes therefore a manner of „piloting” the system that takes shape by *multiple integrations in special conditions*, generating original models of **integronic management** [28].

In genetics, the integronic process is relevant, especially in **biocenosis / community genetics**

<p><i>bioharmonization model</i>, based on „models of the Truth” (paradigms), generated in fact since the middle of the 20th century (example: Romania may have a policy strategic bases for the next hundred years, the idea to be an equilibrium bridge between Orient and Occident).</p>	<p>[24] where multiple integrations of „the association of genofunds” of the biocenosis composing species tend to dynamic equilibrium and where genetic cohesion may decode a biocenosis „heredity”.</p>
---	--

From the *bio-harmonism model* of principle based on a series of guiding ideas of wide echo [29,40,47] there comes out the idea that Information (**I**) is the bases of LIFE genes on the planet („Living Planet”), but also the *program* that has guided evolution on the planet, especially species evolution towards intelligence. It becomes clearer and clearer the idea that all these have had their origin in a **PRIMORDIAL INFORMATION** and a **UNIVERSAL PROGRAM** with existence from Universe origin that suggests that we are living in an Informational and Programmed [44]. Universe. More than that, in this context, there becomes plausible the idea that Information (I) and Program (P) characterize all Cosmos and that at *Multiverse* origin there might be, besides matter / substance (S) energy (E) too, first of all intrinsic Information to „creative intelligence”.

The fact that Primordial Information and Universal Program have led to MAN’s coming out, an intelligent being, demonstrates the fact that they have carried since the beginning the mark of a triadic (I,E,S) and Trinitarian (the Holy Trinity in Christianity) creative intelligence, which structurally and functionally configured Divinity meaning and „perception”. To simplify: **CREATIVE INTELLIGENCE** is the spring through which *Primordial information* as structural element, in its continuous dynamics of *Programs*, generates an infinity of Information (I) types and forms, leading by „*condensation / rarefaction*” (in fact complicated processes described by astrophysics, cosmology, but also in parapsychology) to forms of concentrate, **dense information** that *de facto* represent Energy (E) and **hyper concentrated information** that in the last analyses represent Matter or Substance (S).

Premices regarding paradigma changes: INTEGRATION OF SUSTAINABILITY ELEMENTS

Fig. 4. In the present the Reality diagnose shows the model of an inverted pyramid

As it has already been mentioned, the Bio-Harmonism Theory has INFORMATION as basic reference, i.e. **in essence** in any system, we „**bioharmonize**” **information**, no matter its typology, being aware of its infinite omnipresence in space and time through its capacity to explain and the **capacity to integrate in a harmonious system** all the known scientific data. *The general concept of information* presupposes in fact an „*ensemble of information*”, with emergent character, especially found in **bioharmonization processes** (with fractal and, where applicable, integronic dynamics), that evolves towards an indestructible link. (Oprîş, T, 2006; Munteanu, Fl., 2007 and others), so that the axes may be specified:

Information - Program - Telefinality.

In short, we speak about „**causality and telefinality**”, i.e. the causal determination goes little by little, and every event is explained by the intervention of certain previous causes. The *telefinalist* determination links events in long chains that begin from the origin of a program and go until reaching certain logical final objectives [68]. **Pragmatically**, we mention that Bio-Harmonism Theory mainly follows processes and mechanisms of harmonization between the *Living Planet* model with economic action, with technical creation and with psycho-social implications, in essence contouring the

understanding and taking the *Living and Life* complexity as a model, i.e.: conceptual, doctrinarian and ideological „bioharmonization” of the *Present reality* (examples being already mentioned: bioeconomy, biotechnologies etc.).

3.3. Objectives and principles of Bio-Harmonism Theory in relation to Reality

As a specification, *The Perceived Reality* is what an enough large group of people feels concerning elements that may be felt by the 5 senses, to which is added the world we are not existing in (not touched by human desires and intentions) and which is formed of those entities that are at the bases of the dependence chain and which thus do to depend on anything, practically becoming that “something” that does not disappear when you do not believe in it any more [61,67].

The reference to Reality generates 3 elements for the human being[5]: - Knowledge (no matter its level, it representing the reference to reality mechanism itself); - Man’s action in the world; - it provides the living experience. That is why there may be imagined the *first steps in remodeling reality through Bio-Harmonism Theory*, i.e. to reconsider Reality approach manner (fig.4).

Fig. 5. Step by step application of the theory principles in the present Reality, the transition one towards the model with potential to achieve bioharmonization mechanisms at all levels

In the given situation, in order to start the bioharmonization process, a new approach becomes obligatory by **inverting the present pyramid** towards an „optimized” order that may induce sustainability mechanisms on dynamic equilibrium principles and harmonization (fig.5).The **BIOHARMONIST POLICY** examines bioeconomic, social and info-cultural holistic models [9, 11, 34, 41, 45, 46, 51, 55, 57, 58, 59, 62] and makes legislative projects that aim to eliminate obstacles from the developing way, in the idea to guarantee equilibrium between *Environment, Society and Economy*, taking into account cultural, democratic values – man’s liberty and rights, as well as a high sustainability level in relation to natural resources, biodiversity and health of the living beings and especially of human population (fig. 6).

Normalization of the economic and socio-cultural model towards a real sustainable development also leads to making evident the objectives of the Bio-Harmonism Theory:

- **Establishing principles and methodological achievement** of certain harmonized socio-cultural managerial models (bioeconomy), that reflect in essence the present transition of the biologic-informational society and knowledge sum up (based on multidisciplinary principles,

interconnection and holism, on frontier sciences -biotechnology, bioeconomy and others – and on multiculturalism), towards the direction of understanding and applying elements specific to Knowledge Society.

- **Polyvalent and concentrated action against the disharmony of the present reality**, of the disequilibrium, of dismantling disturbing factors and finding solutions for the dynamic equilibrium of complex systems of economic, social, cultural and moral type in relation to Nature model, to biologic and cultural diversity, at planetary, regional and local level, with conditions and interests specific to the 21st century.
- **Finding elements of equilibrium of his own essence** by reconceptualization of the idea of adaptation, of evolution, of high human quality, also by putting in concordance by „resuscitation” humanity values gravely affected in certain societies (honesty, common sense, meritocracy, honor, man’s individual rights and liberties etc.), through a harmonization process of the ontic triad and perfecting by knowledge.

SIMPLIFIED STRUCTURE OF THE NEW REALITY MODEL ON BIOHARMONISM PRINCIPLES

Fig. 6. Structural and functional relations in the present Reality model
In bioharmonic approach

Facing an international competition, the European socio-economic model or its different variants have a growing future, there being in debate solutions to respond those provocations (Werner, 2006). Even if the last decade has complementarily brought Europe a number of provocations, we consider that also Bio-Harmonism Theory may bring its contribution, developing a theoretic model with polyvalent applicability that aims at multidimensional socio-economic development. It is a new approach to Reality with remodeling potential of the development and integration both at individual and social level, respectively local and regional, which allows generating an objective globalization model [13,20,21,25,53,65]. Investments and economic growth installment, environment, European integration, demography,

migration, unemployment, living standard, education, health, etc., approached by „bioharmonist key”, have increasing chances to have on long term balanced and viable solutions, taking into account present disharmonies (disharmonies with Nature, demographic, economic disharmonies, etc.).

Many of the **present disharmonies** are shown in the paper *Awakening Earth*, in which Duane Elgin (1993) describes humanity's near future in terms of maximum hardness and worry [33,37,60]. In this context, the contribution of bioharmonist theory is put into evidence both by the diagnosis of economic and socio-cultural disharmonies and by evolution gloomy scenarios [69] in the context of reducing 21st century natural resource contribution and climate changes (fig.7).

Fig. 7. *Growth limits in a finite world*

From the inventory of theory applications there result a series of ideas that are to be found in information processing by bioharmonization processes, aiming to find specific solutions for a society based on knowledge. More concretely, bioharmonism

may be achieved only concomitantly with evolution towards equitable knowledge, which imposes reaching aims that need a large *set of values* that may represent basic **principles** of the theory, among which we remind the most important ones in table 2.

Table 2. *Basic principles of bio-harmonism theory*

Nr.	PRINCIPLE
1	Liberty – liberty to innovate, creativity means on long term humanity existence
2	Universal access at information and equal access at education

3	Sustainable development and economic and social harmonization
4	Protection of Life and Environment at local, regional and global level
5	Accepting biologic and cultural diversity in globalization conditions and more and more stressed demographic dynamics
6	Support of the principles of progressist liberal democracy
7	Stimulation of human quality – performance, morality, meritocracy and others.

The application of the principles of Bio-Harmonism Theory is a consequence of following present reality diagnoses and the theory objectives. The world being in change, in rehabilitation, in reconceptualization creates opportunity to different theoretic and applicative demarches to bring their contribution to problem solving, which also makes opportune the contribution of the *bioharmonic doctrine and ideology* afferent to the theory and, implicitly, to the transition from the present Biologic-Informational Society to the *Knowledge Society* and, in a longer perspective, the transition towards the *Conscious Society*.

Conclusions

1. BIOHARMONISM is an integrated theory referring to putting human creation in agreement and in a new order with the „planetary model”, by reorientation towards new economic and socio-cultural models, taking the *Living and Life* a mark, after Nature’s nonlinear model, in a *harmonization* based on analyses methods and means of fractal type and synthesis ones based on integroneic dynamics, with tendency towards equilibrium and efficacy regarding systemic reorganization, having as an aim the contribution at finding *Knowledge Society* achievement ways, in a first stage, and, on long term, the transition towards the *Society previous to the Conscious Society*.

2. *The concomitant „refining”* analyses of the dimensions of the existence fundamental matrix (I-E-S) in the idea to find balanced solutions, representing the basic mechanism of the **bioharmonization process**, that allows element ordering so that there may be modeled megaprojects of *Present Reality*.

3. The new theory, by the *reversed existential pyramid*, that has Information (I) at its bases and Substance (S) on the top, induces a new perfectly equilibrated and of maximum temporal intensity and stability vision in the process of configuring the conceptual model offered by *bioharmonism*, in which in essence we are „bioharmonizing” an

„ensemble of information”, with emergent character that evolve towards an indestructible link: „*Information - Program – Telefinality*”, i.e. an axes that may put in agreement Reality fragmentary structural elements, in harmonized inflexion from fractal and integroneic in relation to the ontic triad.

4. The Bio-Harmonism Theory also applies the mechanism of pyramid reversing to present reality, concerning ideational contribution to sustainable development (as a rule accepted by world’s governments), bringing ENVIRONMENT to the fore, that by sustaining ECONOMY with equilibrated natural and social resources (principles of Roegien bioeconomy), *de facto* fights disequilibrium and avoids entropy, more precisely enormous consumption of natural and social resources in conditions of reduced efficiency and pollution.

5. The most important application of the theory is **political bioharmonism**, where there are to be found all three element of reality in the new order (*environment / natural resources and biodiversity at pyramid bases, i.e. to the fore, absolutely necessary to sustain society and economy*), which confers the political demarche the advantage of the direct impact upon the other present Reality plans and marks, by generating a *bioharmonic doctrine and ideology*.

References

1. Afgan N.H., Carvalho, Maria G., 2010: The Knowledge Society: A Sustainability Paradigm, Cadmus, (www.cadmusjournal.org/), 2 Oct.2010, 17 pp.
2. Albrecht, K., 2007: *Inteligența socială. Noua știință a succesului*, Ed. Curtea Veche, București.
3. Bache, M.C., 2000: Anima mundi - Ecological crisis and death of the ego of the species: speculation on the future, The Journal of Transpersonal Psychology, Vol.32, Nr.1, 25-32.

4. Baltasiu, R., 2002: Elemente de Sociologie. Națiune și capitalism – Considerații de sociologie românească și weberiană, Editura BELADI, Craiova.
5. Bulai, A., 2017: Fundamentele sociale ale cunoașterii, Ed. Trei, Libris.ro, 29-38.
6. Bădescu, I., Baltasiu, R., Bădescu, C., 2011: Sociologia și economia problemelor sociale, Editura Mica Valahie, București.
7. Bejan, A., Lorente S. 2010: The Constructal Law of Design and Evolution in Nature, Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B Biol. Sci., 365 (1545), 1335-1347.
8. Bejan, A., 2016: The Physics of Life: The Evolution of Everything – Adrian Bejan, Editura St. Martin's Press, ISBN 978-1250078827, ISBN 1250078822 (- Teoria (sau legea Constructală, 1996).
9. Bell, D., 2001: The End of Ideology. On the Exhaustion of Political Ideas in the Fifties, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass.
10. Cherry, K., 2018: What Is Sociocultural Theory?; sursa: <https://www.verywellmind.com/>
11. Choo, C. W., Bergeron, P., Detlor, B., & Heaton, L., 2008: Information culture and information use: An exploratory study of three organizations. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science & Technology*, 59(5), 792-804.
12. Cox, G.W., Atkins, M.D., 1979: Agricultural ecology, in *Agricultural Systems from Elsevier*, 731 pp.
13. Cramer, F., 1993: Chaos and Order: The Complex Structure of Living Things, New York ed by D. I. Loewus. VCH Verlagsgesellschaft Weinheim, 1993. ISBN 1-56081-812-3 (New York), 249 Seiten, Preis: DM 48.
14. Cronin, B. and Davenport, E., 1993: Social Intelligence. *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology (ARIST)*, 28, 3-44.
15. Dogan, M., Pelassy, D., 1993: Cum să comparăm națiunile: sociologie politică comparativă, Alternative, București.
16. Drăgănescu, M., 2007: Societatea conștiinței, Institutul de Cercetări pentru Inteligență Artificială al Academiei Române, ISBN 978-973-0-05307-4 în sursa: <https://www.scribd.com/>
17. Elgin, D., 1993: . Awakening Earth - Exploring the Evolution of Human Culture and Consciousness, William Morrow and Company, Inc., New York, 373 pp.
18. Ginman, M., 1988: Information culture and business performance. *IATUL Quarterly*, 2(2), 93-106.
19. Gîrlea, O., Cogut, S., 2013: Fractalii între științele reale și cele umaniste, *Gazeta SF. Revistă electronică de artă și literatură speculativă*, Nov 1.
20. Goleman, D., 2007: *Inteligența socială*, Ed. Curtea Veche, București.
21. Goleman, D., 2008: *Inteligența emoțională*, Ed. Curtea Veche, București.
22. Granovetter, M., 1985: Economic Action And Social Structure: The Problem Of Embeddedness. *American Journal of Sociology* 91, 481-510.
23. Gruia, R., 1998: Managementul ecofermelor, Editura Ceres București, ISBN 973-40-0425-5, 62-85.
24. Gruia, R., 2000: Genetică și ameliorare animală, Ed. Universității Transilvania Brașov, ISBN 973-9474-73-X, 71-75.
25. Gruia, R., 2006: *Integrative Management and Informational Connections*, HAICTA 2006-International Conference on: Information Systems in Sustainable Agriculture, Agroenvironment, and Food Technology, University of Thessaly, Volos, Greece, Sept., 20-23.
26. Gruia, R., 2009: *Theory of Ecoemergent Integrations (General Theory of Ecological Emergence Integration)*, The 2nd International Conference on Environmental and Geological Sciences and Engineering – sub egida World Scientific and Engineering Academy and Society –WSEAS, Proceedings ISSN: 1790-2769, ISBN: 978-960-474-119-9, Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania, September 24-26, 168-172.
27. Gruia, R., 2010: Modular agriculture – paradigm of globalization dynamics within the context of climatic and scientific changes, *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*, "Gheorghe Asachi" Technical University Iasi, ISSN 1582-9596, Vol.9, nr.12, 1601-1606.
28. Gruia, R., 2013: Bazele managementului și direcțiile viitoare de evoluție, Ed. Lux

- Libris Brasov, ISBN 978-973- 131-230-9, 137-197.
29. Hawking, St., 2014: Teoria universală, Editura Humanitas București 123-140.
 30. Hawking, St, Mlodinow,L., 2012 a.: Marele plan, Editura Humanitas București, 31-49.
 31. Hawking, St, Mlodinow,L., 2012 b.: O mai scurtă istorie a timpului, Ed. Humanitas București, 19-24.
 32. Henstock,R.,1991: The General Theory of Integration, Clarendon Press Oxford Science Publication, 1991. ISBN: 9780198535669, 274 pp.
 33. Kuhn, Th., 2008: Structura revoluțiilor științifice, Ed. Humanitas, București (trad. Bogdan Radu, Studiu introductiv, Mircea Flonta).
 34. Ilescu, A.P., 2002: Introducere în politicologie, Editura All, București.
 35. Lipton, B.H., 2017: Biologia credinței, Editura For You București, 139-182.
 36. Lorenz, W., 2011: Fractal Geometry of Architecture: Fractal Dimensions as a Connection Between Fractal Geometry and Architecture, în Ascheron, Claus (ed.), "Biomimetics - Materials, Structures and Processes. Examples, Ideas and Case Studies, Series: Biological and Medical Physics, Biomedical Engineering", Springer Verlag, Heidelberg Dordrecht London New York.
 37. Lovelock,J., 1987: Gaia: a new look at life on earth, Oxford University Press.
 38. Mandelbrot, B., 1999: A Multifractal Walk Down Wall Street, SCIENTIFIC AMERICAN, February.
 39. Mandelbrot, B., 1982: The Fractal Geometry of Nature, Freeman and Company, New-York,1982, ISBN 0-7167- 1186-9.
 40. Mihăescu, L., 2015: Teoria Primară, Ed. Premius București, ISBN 978-606-93843-2-9, 34-54.
 41. Miroiu, Mihaela (ed.), 2012: Ideologii politice actuale. Semnificații, evoluție și impact, Polirom, Iași.
 42. Munteanu,Fl., 1999: Asupra unei triade ontologice INFORMATIE + ENERGIE +MATERIE cadrul științific pentru studiul interacțiunii MINTE - MATERIE , *Centrul Pentru Studii Complexe*, (sursa: <http://www.csc.matco.ro/altele1/OMINT E.htm>).
 43. Munteanu, Fl., 2015: Semnțe pentru altă lume, Ed. Princeps București, 137-192.
 44. Munteanu, Fl., 2016: Studiu asupra triadei ontologice Informație + Energie + Materie, cadru științific pentru studiul interacțiunii Minte-Materie, Centrul pentru Studii Complexe, Centru UNESCO, 15 pag.
 45. Nonaka, I., 1994: A Dynamic Theory of Organisational Knowledge Creation. *Organization Science*, 5(1), 14-37.
 46. Patapievici,H.R., 2004: Discernământul modernizării, Ed. Humanitas București, 75.
 47. Petre, R.A., 1996: Modelul simplificat al structurii Univesului în <http://www.spiritus.ro/>
 48. Pillet,G., 1986: Energy externality - A Concept for Understanding and Predicting the Role of the Free Environment Economic Process, M.Miata and K. Matsui: Energy Decisions for the Future , IAEE/IEE Japan, Tokyo, , 603-618.
 49. Pillet,G., Odum,H.T.,1987: Externalities in Environmental Macroeconomics, in Pillet and Murota: Environmental Economics - The Analysis of a Major Interface, L. Leimgruber , Geneva, 129-153.
 50. Pitkänen, M., 2015: Geometric Theory of Harmony în http://tgdtheory.com/public_html/, 36 p.
 51. Pîrvulescu, C., 2002: Politici și instituții politice, Editura TREI, București, Ediția a II-a revizuită.
 52. Popa, I., 2004: Societatea Cunoașterii, rev. Management, nr.2/2004.
 53. Rucker, R., 1987: Mind Tools: The Five Levels of Mathematical Reality, Boston, Houghton Mifflin.
 54. Sabău, G., 2001: Societatea cunoașterii o perspectivă românească, Ed.Economică, București.
 55. Stănciugelu, Șt., 2016: Liberalismul periferiei, Editura Tritonic, Partea I - Gramatica fractală în istoria europeană a ideii liberale, ISBN: 606-749-166-1, 2-30.
 56. Skjerve, E., Glatte, E., 2006: *Fractal phenomena and fractal analysis in epidemiological studies*, The Norwegian

- School of Veterinary Science, Proceedings of the 11th International Symposium on Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics.
57. Țăranu, A., 2005: *Doctrina politice contemporane*, Editura Fundației Pro, București.
58. Toffler, A., 1995: *Powershift. Puterea în mișcare*, București, Editura ANTET.
59. Ungureanu, I., 1991: *Paradigme ale cunoașterii sociologice*, Humanitas, București.
60. Wallerstein, I., 1992: *Sistemul mondial modern*, Meridiane, trad. Dorel Abraham, Ilie Bădescu, Mihai Ghibernea, București.
61. Wilson, E.O., 2015: *Cucerirea socială a Pământului*, Humanitas, București.
62. Werner, W., 2006: Which Socio-economic Model for Europe? *INTERECONOMICS* January 2006, Volume 41, Issue 1, pp 4–23.
63. Doctrina politice în <http://www.politicaromaneasca.ro/>
64. *Green economy*, from Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia.
65. The_Blue_Economy in : <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki>
66. Ciocurile haemiltoniene in <https://en.wikipedia.org/>
67. Ce este "realitatea"? Cum o definim? : <http://www.scientia.ro/>
68. <http://energetica.ga>
69. <https://www.google.ro/>

RESEARCH OF THE ESTIMATION OF CALORIFIC VALUE OF BIOMASS

GH.C. SPIRCHEZ^{1*}, A.LUNGULEASA¹, C. CROITORU²,
R.FORFOTĂ¹, I. DUMITRACHE¹, N.R. SAMOILĂ

¹Dept. of Wood Industry, Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania

*Corresponding author: cosmin.spirchez@unitbv.ro

Abstract: Biomass has played and plays an important role in the potential's energy economizing. Biomass resources play an important role in the planet's economy, although often biomass is only used for raw material production in the woodworking industry but can be an excellent energy material with the potential to produce energy through conversion or direct combustion processes. According to more recent researches, the highest inferior calorific value for cereal energy product is obtained for sunflower lighters 17070-17370 kJ/kg, which have a moisture content of 5,9 -6,2%. Determination of the calorific value of wood materials and biomass of lignocellulosic materials is the energy determination of the fuel, lived for the purpose of assessing the amount of energy contained in biomass.

Keywords: biomass, calorimeter bomb, value calorific, wood

1. Introduction

In 2017, the estimated contribution of wood biomass to the European Union energy supply amounted to 20000 PJ.

This contribution was about two-thirds of total renewable energy production in the European Union.

For bio-energy, the following trends were observed:

- The heat: In 2014, the production of biomass heat was about 1500 PJ.

- Electricity: Electricity production from biomass amounted to 90 PJ in 2000 and increased to 116 PJ in year 2014.

- Fuels: The current contribution of biofuels is about 25 PJ, almost negligible in total bio-energy production. The production and use of biofuels has increased rapidly over the past ten years. Bio-diesel production has risen from 80 ktonne in 2003 to 780 ktonne in 2014. Ethanol production in the European Union rare from 48 to 216 ktonne over the same period.

To date, six European Union member states want to implement tax programs to support the use of biofuels (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Spain, Italy, Sweden). Under these tax schemes, biofuels are partially exempt from taxes compared to fossil fuels used for transport.

In Romania, an energy consumption of 34.9 Mtoe (million tonnes of oil equivalent) is projected by 2020.

Biomass covers more than 60 % of total renewable energy sources, 190-200 PJ/year.

At present, much of the energy needed by mankind is produced from fossil fuels.

Fossil fuels, according to research conducted by the European Union, damage the environment.

The greatest danger of using fossil fuels is the harmful emissions that are eliminated in the atmosphere. The extraction processing and use of fossil fuels emit 98% of the total carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, which negativ influences both the evolution of living microorganisms and human life.

Wood has a high energy capacity and can be delivered at a much lower to energy consumer than fossil fuels.

2. Biomass-important energy source

Biomass is a renewable energy source, as it grows year after year, it is widespread in the world and presents low costs composed to fossil fuels.

The biomass resources from which the fuel material is produced may include wood and wood

waste, agricultural cereals and waste resulting from their production.

Biomass is one of the forms of renewable sources that can be converted into solid, liquid and gaseous fuel, and which can generate both heat in the form of heat by combusting it and electricity through conversion processes.

Biomass is plant form is a complex compound and varies from one species to another. It encompasses all forms of vegetable matter that grow on land, water, as well as substances produced by biological development.

Biomass takes part in the carbon cycle in nature by using carbon dioxide. Carbon dioxide participates both in photosystems processes during growth, but is also the component that causes a complete burning.

Biomass is a friend of the environment. Carbon dioxide is observed by plants during growth and forms a closed circuit.

3. Materials and method

The installation used to determine the calorific value of wood biomass was the XRY-1C explosive type burner produced by Shanghai Changji Geological Institute in China (fig.1).

The method of determining the calorific value of wood material refers firstly to the preparation of the raw material, the to the actual determination and ultimately to the final result.

The test sample 1 binds to the cotton yarn 2 and put in the crucible of the bomb 3. Connect the spiral nickel wire 4 to the sample and the cotton yarn, the place the protective cap 5 correctly.

Fig. 1. Calorimeter bomb

The crucible is connected to the calorimetric bomb cap 6 by 2 electrodes 7 and 8, which continues with the electrical coupling bomb of the calorimetric bomb 9 and 10.

By bombing cap, the bomb 11 is coupled through the stator 12 to the oxygen cylinder, introducing 3 atmospheres.

The test contains three distinct periods (fig.2).

Fig. 2. Three distinct period at calorimeter bomb

The initial period aim to determine the the temperature variations of the water in the

calorimetric vessel due to the heat exchange with the outside before the combustion.

The main period start with the ignition of the sample and consequently increases the temperature of the water in the calorimetric vessel.

The final period aim to determine the average temperature variation of the water in the calorimetric vessel due to heat exchange with the outside.

For *fraxinus excelsior*, $m_1 = 0,6600$ g, $U = 0\%$, gross calorific value is 19008 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 18370 kJ/kg, $m_2 = 1,1180$ g, $U = 10\%$, gross calorific value is 16238 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 15987 kJ/kg, $m_3 = 1,2640$ g, $U = 20\%$, gross calorific value is 13788 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 13285 kJ/kg, $m_4 = 1,2770$ g, $U = 50\%$, gross calorific value is 6436 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 5179 kJ/kg.

In fig.3 is presented variation calorific value for *fraxinus excelsior*.

Fig. 3. Variation value calorific for *fraxinus excelsior*

For *acer pseudoplatanus*, $m_1 = 0,851$ g, $U = 0\%$, gross calorific value is 18802kJ/kg, net calorific value is 18336 kJ/kg, $m_2 = 0,960$ g, $U = 10\%$, gross calorific value is 16805 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 16618kJ/kg, $m_3 = 1,006$, $U = 20\%$, gross calorific value is 15041 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 14668 kJ/kg, $m_4 = 0,945$ g, $U = 50\%$, gross calorific value is 9749 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 9166 kJ/kg.

In fig.4 is presented variation valorific value for *acer pseudoplatanus*.

Fig.4. Variation value calorific for *acer pseudoplatanus*

4. Conclusions

- Energy is the basis of all human activities and its evolution can not be interrupted combustion is one of the most important thermo-chemical processes of energy production;
- At present, all countries in the world are strengthening their investments in alternative energy generation, which is projected to reach 20% of the total energy used in Europe.

Acknowledgements: Transilvania Unoversity of Brasov, Project nr. 8063/2.07.2018 (The program of quality evaluation of briquettes from sunflower seed husk).

References

1. Abassi, S.A, Nipanay, P.C., Schaumberg, G.D. Bioenergy potential of eight common aquatic weeds, *Biological Wastes*, vol.34, No.4, pag.359-366, 1990.
2. Gavrilescu, D Energy from biomass in pulp and paper mills, *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*, pag.537-546, 2009;
3. Juran, M. Calitatea produselor, Ed. Tehnică, București, 1973;
4. Lako J., Hanesok J, Yuzhakova T. Biomass-A source of chemicals and energy for sustainable development,

- Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, vol. 7(5), pp. 499-509, 2009;
5. Lăzăroiu G, Mihăescu L. Combustion of pitcoal-wood biomass briquettes a boiler test-facility, Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, pp 595-601, 2008;
 6. Lunguleasa A. The calorific power of wooden biomass, Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov-Series II, vol.2(51), pp.65-70, 2010;
 7. Moya R., Tenorio C. Fuelwood characteristics and its relation with extractives and chemical properties of ten fast-growth species in Costa Rica, Biomass and Bioenergy, vol.56, pp.14-21, 2011;
 8. Nielsen NPK, Gardner D. Importance of temperature, moisture content a species for the conversion process of wood residues to fuel pellets, Wood Fiber vol.41, pp 414-425;
 9. Prasertsan S., Sajjakulnukit B. Biomass and bioenergy in Thailand: Potential , opportunity and barriers, Renewable energy , vol.31 , Nr.5, 2006;
 10. Rahmann A, Masood MA Influence of size and shape in the strength by briquettes, Fuel Process Technology, vol.22, pp125-145,2013;
 11. Roser D., Asikainen A. Sustainable use for Forest Biomass for Energy, Springer Series in Wood Science, 2006;
 12. Sjostrom E. Wood chemistry, Academic Press, Helsinki, 2006;
 13. Teuch O, Hofeanuer A, Troger F, From J. Basic properties of specific wood based materials carbonised in a nitrogen atmosphere, Wood Science and Technology, Springer, vol.38, nr.3, 2004;
 14. Uslu A, Faaji A.P.C, Bergman P.C.A Pre-treatment technologies, and their effect on international bioenergy supply chain logistics. Techno-economic evaluation of torrefaction, fast pyrolysis and pelletisation, Energy, vol. 33(8), pp. 1206-1223;
 15. Walkowiak, M., Bartkowiak M., The kinetics of the thermal decomposition of the willow wood (*Salix viminalis* L.) exposed to the torrefaction process, Drewno (wood), vol. 55(187), pp.37-50;
 16. Wang G.J., Luo Y.H., Deng J., Pretreatment of biomass by torrefaction, Chinese Science Bulletin, vol. 56(14), pp. 1442-1448;

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON EUROPEAN LEGISLATION ABOUT HYGIENIC ENGINEERING AND DESIGN

L. GACEU¹

¹ Transilvania University of Braşov, Departments of Engineering and management in Food and Tourism, CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy
E-mail: gaceul@unitbv.ro

Abstract: *The aim of this study is to present the main European legislation connected with hygienic design (EHEDG). The study shows that all regulations and directives, except the machinery directive, arise from consumer protection and therefore from food law. The legislation does not provide design details, but is supported and expanded by non-normative standards and EHEDG-guidelines.*

Keywords: *hygienic engineering and design legislation*

1. Introduction

The food industry is the largest manufacturing in Romania. It is a market of 10 billion euros with almost 200,000 employees.

Sanitary and Veterinary National Authority and for Food safety (ANSVSA) <http://www.ansvsa.ro/> ANSVSA is responsible for food safety and food hygiene across Romania. It works with local authorities to enforce food safety regulations and have staff who work in Romanian meat plants to check that the requirements of the regulations are being met. It also commissions research related to food safety.

The Framework Directive EC 1935/2004, the Machinery Directive EC 2006/42, Good Manufacturing Practice EC 2023/2006 and the Food Hygiene Regulations EC 852/2004 are all embodied in Romanian legislation.

EHEDG representative in Romania was established in 2016 with specific roles, as:

- identifying areas where knowledge of hygienic design is insufficient;
- filling the existing gaps and lack of know-how by practical guidelines and education;
- offering expertise, networking and further development in the fields of hygienic engineering & design and safe food production;
- preparing scientific and technical guidelines on all aspects of state-of-the-art hygienic design requirements in accordance to EU legislation;
- developing test methods in order to identify and reduce hazards of equipment used in food production;

- strengthening the participation in standardisation bodies like CEN, ISO, DIN, JIS, 3-A, NSF etc.;

- strengthening the cooperation with the EU (i.e. food contact material directive, BAT, traceability and other EU-Projects) as well as with other organisations;

- encouraging research and development in the field of hygienic design;

Legislation in this context is play a very important role and is under continuous changes in the last decades.

2. European legislation in conection with hygienic design

The legal requirements for the food industry are described generally in the Codex Alimentarius, in the European Legislation on Hygienic Regulations and in the Machinery Directive.

There are several EU-regulations dealing with hygiene aspects, but mostly with food safety :

REGULATION (EC) No 178/2002 ,
REGULATION (EC) No 852/2004,
REGULATION (EC) No 853/2004,
REGULATION (EC) No 854/2004.

This package it is called „Hygiene package“

In addition there are have specific Legislations in different EU member states.

There are supportive regulations for the food industry, they so called C standard, which are giving detail information's. The standards EN 1672-2 and EN ISO 14159 on Hygienic requirements describe the content on Examples.

Both standards are based on EHEDG document 8, Hygienic Equipment Design Criteria.

Furthermore, the following standards and recommendations must be taken into account when manufacturing food processing machines:

Guidelines and certification of equipment and components of EHEDG. www.ehedg.org

Guidelines and certification of equipment and components of 3-A for the USA and exports to the USA. www.3-a.org

Certification of equipment and components of the NSF for special products in gastronomy. www.nsf.org

Codex Alimentarius

All 28 EU member states and the EU are member of the Codex Alimentarius commission, which continue the Codex.

The central frame of the document is: "Assurance that food will not cause harm to the consumer when it is prepared and/or eaten according to its intended use."

Created in 1963 by FAO and WHO to develop food standards, guidelines and related texts such as codes of practice under the joint FAO/WHO Food Standards Programme.

Beside the Assurance that food will not cause harm to the consumer when it is prepared and/or eaten according to its intended use, for example the development of a HACCP system or the introduction of random checks, the Codex Alimentarius includes product-specific standards that meets the requirements on production processes, identify microbiological risks and regulate the labelling of the product provided to the consumer.

The Codex is considered worldwide as the de facto binding, created by the Food and Agriculture Organization and World Health Organization. It provides a largely secure collection of views and insights of the state of the associated science.

Fig. 1. *Codex Alimentarius – basic texts*

Regulation (EC) 178/2002 on the hygiene of foodstuffs

The basic general food law is formulated in the Framework Regulation (EC) 178/2002 for foodstuffs, and contains, mainly:

- Basic hygiene principles;
- Food & feed business operator: legal responsibility for ensuring product safety;
- Unsafe foodstuffs may not be placed on the market;
- Traceability;
- Consideration of long-term, cumulative effects;

This regulation also regulated the establishment and functions of the European Food Safety Authority. This EU agency cooperates with national authorities to ensure food safety, to ensure that unsafe

food is not placed on the market, to ensure traceability and to achieve long-term cumulative effects.

Assurance of quality and safety is an essential need for the continued good reputation of foodstuffs. The correct hygienic design and maintenance of food production systems is considered as a prerequisite to fulfill these requirements. (fig. 2)

Regulation (EC) 852/2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs contains:

- primary production (Annex I - articles, fittings and equipment must be able to be cleaned and, where necessary, to be disinfected);
- Annex II (describes the surfaces that all components are thoroughly cleaned and, if necessary, disinfected, that contamination is excluded as far as possible and that the equipment and the immediate environment can be adequately cleaned);

- analysis of potential food safety risks and determination of Critical Control Points (Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points - HACCP);
- HACCP based on principles of Codex Alimentarius;
- control and documentation requirement during the whole production process;
- registration is mandatory for all food manufacturing establishment.

Risk assessment - HACCP is taking in consideration the following aspects: conduct hazard analysis; determine critical control points (CCP's); establish critical limit(s); establish system to monitor CCP's; establish corrective action; establish verification procedure; establish documentation

Fig. 2. Connection between different regulation & directive for assuring Food Safety

Other regulation in the same are: **Regulation (EC) No 853/2004** of the European Union lays down specific hygiene rules for food of animal origin for food producers. It is a key part of the 2004 European Union hygiene package, a set of legislation on food hygiene.

Regulation (EC) No 854/2004 of the European Union provides for special rules for the official control of products of animal origin intended for human consumption.

Regulation (EC) 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs: determining limits for safe food; food safety criteria for best before date (BBD); process hygiene criteria during manufacturing

Annex 1 to **Regulation (EC) No. 2073/2005** is replaced by the text in the Annex to **Regulation (EC) No. 1441/2007**

Regulation (EC) 1935/2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food

This regulation it lays down harmonized rules with respect to packaging materials and objects such as bottles and containers that may come directly or indirectly into contact with food.

The purpose of the regulation is to protect and ensure human health and the interests of consumers that the products used throughout the EU can be sold.

The Regulation defines 17 groups of materials and articles, from cork and glass to plastics and textiles, to which individual measures can be adopted. Those specific measures may include, for example, purity criteria and a list of the substances used.

Requests for use of a new substance should be submitted to the national authority, which then forwards the applications to the European Food Safety Authority for comments.

The materials used for packaging must be marked with the words "for food contact", and a corresponding logo, for example, a coffee machine, a wine bottle or a spoon. Measures must be taken for traceability.

The national authorities may prohibit the use of a particular material when they come with detailed reasons to the conclusion that the use of this material could endanger human health

With this Regulation, the use of "active" and "intelligent" packaging is admitted that extend the shelf life of a food and can give

information on its freshness, provided they do not affect the composition of the food.

The Regulation does not apply to antique materials like antique pottery vessels and coating materials such as the materials covering cheese rinds, prepared meat products or fruits, which form part of the whole food or can be consumed with this.

Requirement on materials intended to come into contact with food:

- no human health hazards;
- no indefensible modification of food composition;
- no detraction from organoleptic food properties;
- no misdirection of customers;
- use “for food contact” or the symbol;
- traceability on all manufacturing and distribution steps.

Other regulation in this direction are:

Regulation (EC) 2023/2006 - good manufacturing practice for materials and articles intended to come into contact with food;

Regulation (EU) 10/2011 - Plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food, revokes Directive 2002/72/EC.

Directive (EC) 2006/42 Annex I 2.1. Foodstuffs machinery and machinery for cosmetics or pharmaceutical products

The Machinery Directive does not cover all possible critical points, but rather gives an common overview in regard to basic requirements for hygienic design.

Machinery intended for use with foodstuffs or with cosmetic or pharmaceutical products must be designed and constructed in such a way that the risk of infection, disease or contamination is excluded.

The following requirements must be observed: materials in contact with, or intended to come into contact with, foodstuffs or cosmetics or pharmaceutical products must satisfy the conditions set down in the relevant Directives. The machinery must be designed and constructed in such a way that these materials can be cleaned before each use. Where this is not possible disposable parts must be used;

Machinery manufacturers who design their machines according to these standards and the Machinery Directive are considered to be fulfilled in this area can declare that their machines are in accordance with the requirements.

Both regulations for carrying out risk assessment over a system show to ensure that all relevant hazard situations and possible risks are taken into account that all the results of this analysis are used in the design of the machines, and that the appropriate documentation has been linked to each project has been reported.

In addition, the EHEDG guidelines 8 criteria and the EHEDG guidelines 13, hygienic design of equipment for open processing provide additional advice for the design. The design principles of these guidelines are comparable to the CEN standards, and in some cases the examples used are the same. There are some small differences in the definition of product range, but the design of the equipment should be such that they are easily cleaned within a reasonable time. Ultimately, each machine must be cleaned, and depending on the overall cleanability of a machine and its components, this can be time-consuming. For this reason, it is much cheaper for food processors to invest in machines that are quick and easy to clean than to buy cheaper machines with time-consuming cleanability, which may cause spoilage of the product or contamination caused by product residues and / or detergents.

For machines which do not comply with the "easy to clean" requirements of the Machinery Directive and the corresponding standards, CE conformity is not valid. The only question is who decides whether something is cleanable or not? For this, EHEDG offers certification for different devices. This is a voluntary agreement that the equipment complies with the Machinery Directive. EHEDG is working on new certification systems and guidelines to improve the machines for more efficient cleanability

Design requirements that must be observed:

Materials:

(a) materials in contact with, or intended to come into contact with, foodstuffs or cosmetics or pharmaceutical products must satisfy the conditions set down in the relevant Directives. The machinery must be designed and constructed in such a way that these materials can be cleaned before each use. Where this is not possible disposable parts must be used;

(b) all surfaces in contact with foodstuffs or cosmetics or pharmaceutical products, other than surfaces of disposable parts, must:

- be smooth and have neither ridges nor crevices which could harbour organic materials. The same applies to their joinings,

- be designed and constructed in such a way as to reduce the projections, edges and recesses of assemblies to a minimum,
 - be easily cleaned and disinfected, where necessary after removing easily dismantled parts; the insidesurfaces must have curves with a radius sufficient to allow thorough cleaning;
- c) It must be possible for liquids, gases and aerosols deriving from products as well as from cleaning, disinfecting and rinsing fluids to be completely discharged from the machinery (if possible, in a 'cleaning' position);
- (d) machinery must be designed and constructed in such a way as to prevent any substances or living creatures, in particular insects, from entering, or any organic matter from accumulating in, areas that cannot be cleaned;
- (e) machinery must be designed and constructed in such a way that no ancillary substances hazardous to health, including the lubricants used, can come into contact with foodstuffs, cosmetics or pharmaceutical products. Where necessary, machinery must be designed and constructed in such a way that continuing compliance with this requirement can be checked.

Technical file for machinery - 2006/42/EC contains the following chapters:

- general description of the machinery;
- overall drawings, accompanied by all calculation notes, test results;
- certificates etc. required to check the conformity with the health and safety requirements;
- documentation on risk assessment demonstrating the procedure followed;
- standards and other technical specifications used;
- technical report giving the results of the tests carried out;
- copy of the instructions for the machinery;
- internal measures for serial production;
- implemented to ensure that the machinery remains in conformity with the provisions of this directive.

The instructions for foodstuffs machinery and machinery for use with cosmetics or pharmaceutical products must indicate

recommended products and methods for cleaning, disinfecting and rinsing, not only for easily accessible areas but also for areas to which access is impossible or inadvisable.

Conclusions

All regulations and directives, except the machinery directive, arise from consumer protection and therefore from food law.

The basic principle is that everyone is self-responsible and has to perform risk assessment to assure food safety.

The framework of the legislation does not provide design details, but is supported and expanded by non-normative standards and EHEDG-guidelines.

In order to offer help to the industry in these questions, EHEDG has developed and published a variety of practical guidance documents on adequate hygienic design in different areas of food production equipment and machinery, as well as on the food manufacturing infrastructure. Titles available are listed below, while others are currently in progress to complement the EHEDG document series. The following list of guidelines is regularly updated and completed by new documents in various language versions: <http://www.ehedg.org/vodii/>

References

1. H. L. M. Lelieveld, John Holah, Domago Handbook of Hygiene Control in the Food Industry, Elsevier, ISBN 978-0-0-08-100155-4
2. EHEDG Document No. 2, Third edition (2004). A method for the assessment of in-place cleanability of food processing equipment.
3. EHEDG Document No. 5, Second edition (2004). A method for the assessment of in-line steam sterilisability of food processing equipment.
4. EHEDG Document No. 7, Second edition (2004). A method for the assessment of bacteria tightness of food processing equipment.
5. EHEDG Document No. 4 (1993). A method for the assessment of in-line pasteurisation of food processing equipment.
6. EHEDG Document No. 15 (1997). A method for the assessment of in-place

- cleanability of moderately sized food processing equipment.
7. EHEDG Document No. 19 (2000). A method for assessing
 8. the bacterial impermeability of hydrophobic membrane filters. EHEDG Document No. 8, Second Edition (2004). Hygienic equipment design criteria.
 9. EHEDG Authorised Institutes <URL: <http://www.ehedg.org/index.php?nr=17>. Accessed 23 June 2011.
 10. BS EN 1672-2:2005 + A1:2009 (2005). Food processing machinery. Basic concepts. Hygiene requirements. BSI, UK.
 11. European Parliament and Council (2006). Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on machinery, and amending Directive 95/16/EC (recast). Official Journal of the European Union OJ L 157, 9.6.2006, pp. 24 - 86.

RESEARCH REGARDING THE ANTIBACTERIAL EFFECT OF ESSENTIAL OILS EXTRACTED FROM: *THYMUS VULGARIS*, *MALALEUCA* AND *OCIMUM BASILICUM*

GH. PUCHIANU¹, N.R. SAMOILĂ¹, A. MĂRCULESCU¹

¹Transilvania University of Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism
Corresponding author: raisa.samoila@yahoo.com

Abstract: For the testing of antibacterial action, essential oils extracted from the following plants were used: *Thymus vulgaris*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Malaleuca*. The antibacterial action of essential oils was tested after isolation and confirmation of different bacterial strains in food following laboratory examination: *Salmonella typhimurium* isolated from poultry carcasses and *Escherichia coli* β positive glucuronidase isolated from telemea cheese.

The sensitivity of isolated microorganisms to the action of essential oils has been assessed in accordance with the standard CLSI, M100 - S18, 2008, according to the diameter of the inhibition area. It has been observed that the essential oil of *Thymus vulgaris* is the most active with moderate sensitivity to *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Escherichia coli* β positive glucuronidase. To the essential oil of *Ocimum basilicum*, moderate sensitivity to *Salmonella typhimurium* and resistance to *Escherichia coli* β positive glucuronidase was found and for *Malaleuca* was found moderate sensitivity for *Escherichia coli* β positive glucuronidase and resistance to *Salmonella typhimurium*. Through the active principles contained, the tested essential oils exert a moderate bactericidal action.

Keywords: essential oils, antibiogram, antibiotic.

1. Introduction

Intensive livestock production has led to a significant increase in the use of antimicrobial agents, both for therapeutic and prophylactic purposes, and for stimulating growth. Any use of these antimicrobial agents is a public health issue, the reckless use of antibiotics is considered to be the main reason for the occurrence of bacterial resistance.

The resistance phenomenon of bacteria to antimicrobial agents may become a major problem as a consequence of their intensive and erroneous use. Repercussions on human health are the emergence of multi-resistant pathogens that can be isolated from animal food and resistant microorganisms that infect animals and produce zoonoses [3].

The presence of microorganisms in food is of particular importance for quality, sanity and freshness. Generally, micro-organisms are those that reduce the nutritional value of the product, or make it inedible, either by their pathogenic action or by the degradation and production of toxic

metabolites. Bacterial, fungal, parasitic, viral, and prionous infections were among the infectious agents capable of disease. For this reason, it is necessary for food industry operators to take all measures to prevent food contamination with different microorganisms by implementing the HACCP system in order to identify early sources of microbiological contamination.

A possibility of reducing the number of microorganisms in food is the use of inhibitory substances which, however, in high doses have negative effects on the health of consumers (e.g. nitrites, nitrates, etc.), which is why the identification of alternative possibilities is absolutely necessary.

Such a possibility may be represented by essential oils obtained from different plants, recognized to have an inhibitory effect or even a bactericidal effect on the development of microorganisms, while at the same time influencing the health of the consumers [3,4].

2. Materials and method

For the testing of antibacterial action, essential oils extracted from the following plants were used: *Thymus vulgaris*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Malaleuca*.

The antibacterial action of essential oils was tested after isolation and confirmation of various bacterial strains in food as a result of laboratory examination.

The species of susceptible microorganisms tested and the food from which these were isolated were as follows:

Table 1. *Microorganisms and food from which they were isolated*

No.	Microorganism	Food from which it was isolated
1.	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Poultry carcasses
2.	<i>Escherichia coli</i> β positive glucuronidase	Telemea cheese

For the isolation of *Salmonella* bacteria was used standardized working methodology, according to 6579/2003 AC / 2006 "Food and feed microbiology - Horizontal method of research of *Salmonella* spp."

The principle of the method consists in the bacterial isolation from food and identification on the basis of cultural, microscopic, biochemical, serological characteristics, the diagnostic methodology requiring the passage of four successive phases:

- pre-enrichment in non-selective liquid media: buffered peptone water;
- enrichment in liquid selective media: Rappaport-Vassiliadis medium with soy (RVS broth) and Müller-Kauffmann tetracyclated / novobiocin broth (MKTTn broth);
- isolation and identification: from the cultures obtained following inoculation of RVS and MKTTn, two selective mediums are inoculated: xylose-lysine-deoxycholate agar (XLD agar) and Rambach medium.

Selective media were transplanted into a nutrient broth, which was incubated for 24 h +/- 3 h at 37° C +/- 10 C, after which the biochemical confirmations were carried out: the sugar fermentation test - TSI, urea decomposition test and L-lysine decarboxylation test. The isolated strains were sent for confirmation and typing at the Institute of Hygiene and Public Health Veterinary (IISPV).

The TBX medium (5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl β -D-glucuronate) was used to isolate *E.coli* positive to β -glucuronidase, a solid medium which contains a chromogenic ingredient for β -glucuronidase enzyme detection.

The principle of the method consists in making decimal dilutions, then inoculating two Petri dishes with TBX medium from each consecutive decimal dilution, incubating for 18-24h at 44 ° C

± 1 ° C, then examining to detect the presence of colonies which, after their characteristics may be considered to be *E.coli* positive to β -glucuronidase.

Typical *E.coli* positive β -glucuronidase colony-forming units (UFCs) are counted in each plate containing more than 150 typical ufc and total less than 300 ufc (typical and non-typical) from two consecutive serial dilutions (total 4 plates), after which the microbial load of the examined food product is calculated using special calculation formulas. Confirmation was made using the Vitek 2 Compact.

The sensitivity of isolated microorganisms to the action of essential oils has been assessed in accordance with the standard CLSI, M100 - S18, 2008, according to the diameter of the inhibition area. For this purpose the diffusion method has been used, the principle of which is based on the inhibition of the development of a microbial culture in contact with various essential oils on appropriate culture media.

The culture medium used the Müller-Hinton special medium, which allows the development of most pathogenic bacteria without antagonistic effects against antibiotics or essential oil components.

It is also isotone with the blood which can be added to cultivate particular species, from a nutritional point of view (e.g. streptococci). The pH of the medium was 7.3 ± 0.1 (fig.1). Prior to sowing the Mueller-Hinton medium, the pure culture of the microorganism was transplanted in the nutrient broth which was to be tested after having previous serial decimal dilutions of 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} in sterile physiological saline. Dilution was performed to obtain frequent colonies, but not confluent (fig.2).

Fig.1 *Mueller – Hinton Medium*

Fig.2. *Nutrient Broth*

For the sowing of the Mueller-Hinton medium, the method of flooding the medium with 1-1.2 ml dilution (a 10^{-3} dilution generally used) was used with a Pasteur pipette, after which the suspension was dispersed throughout the surface by repeated slopes.

The transplantation was performed on the surface of the selective culture media used for the isolation of Salmonella and E. coli bacteria, Rambach medium (Figure 3) and TBX medium (Figure 4).

Fig.3. *Rambach Medium*
Typical colonies of Salmonella

Fig.4. *TBX Medium*
Typical colonies of E. coli

The sown culture medium was placed on the thermostat with the cap of the plate semi-open for 20-30 minutes, after that the microspheres impregnated with essential oils were distributed by means of a pre-flared tweezers, taking care that they were at approximately 15 mm from the periphery of the medium and about 30 mm from each other. The plates were covered with the cap, after which they were left on the table for 15-20 minutes for pre-diffusion in such a way that the essential oils diffused into the medium. The plates were then placed on the thermostat for a period of 18-24 hours, after that the results were interpreted.

3. Results and discussions

Interpretation of results consisted in assessing the size of inhibition areas induced by essential oils. Their diameter is directly proportional to the sensitivity of the germ in the sense that the more essential oil is more active, the inhibition area is more extensive. It was appreciated that sensitive microorganisms to the inhibition area of greater than 6 mm, moderately sensitive microorganisms which the inhibition zone was 2-5 mm and resistant for microorganisms which the inhibition zone was ≤ 2 mm or even absent.

Table 2. *Sensitivity of microorganisms isolated to the action of tested essential oils*

Microorganism	Essential oil								
	<i>Thymus vulgaris</i>			<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>			<i>Malaleuca</i>		
	S	MS	R	S	MS	R	S	MS	R
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>		x			x				x
<i>Escherichia coli</i> β positive glucuronidase		x				x		x	

It is observed that the essential oil of *Thymus vulgaris* is the most active, with moderate sensitivity to *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Escherichia coli* β positive glucuronidase. To the essential oil of *Ocimum basilicum*, moderate sensitivity to *Salmonella typhimurium* and

Fig. 5 Müller – Hinton Medium
Salmonella typhimurium

resistance to *Escherichia coli* β positive glucuronidase was found, and for *Maleluca*, moderate sensitivity was found for *Escherichia coli* β positive glucuronidase and resistance to *Salmonella typhimurium* (Figures 5 and 6).

Fig. 6 Müller – Hinton Medium
Escherichia coli β positive glucuronidase

Conclusions

Due to the active principles contained, the essential oils tested have an obvious bactericidal effect. The use of essential oils can prevent food poisoning by bactericidal action on toxigenic food pathogens. Essential oils tested can be used for incorporation into various foods to prevent the development of microorganisms, helping to increase conservativity and increase food safety.

References

1. Gaceu L., Aspects regarding electrochemical detection of the antioxidant activity for subcritical extracts from *pleurotus ostreatus*, *Journal of EcoAgriTourism* Vol. 13, no.1 2017, ISSN: 1844-8577, pp.53-57;
2. Gaceu L., Comparative study regarding the antioxidant activity of subcritical extracts from *vitis semen*, *mustard* and *polygonum cuspidatum*, *Journal of EcoAgriTourism* Vol. 13, no.1 2017, ISSN: 1844-8577, pp.48-52;
3. Puchianu G., Criterii microbiologice de siguranță alimentară și igienă a prelucrării – Alimente de origine animală. Editura Universității Transilvania din Brasov. ISBN 978-606-19-0097-8, 2012;
4. Puchianu G., Mărculescu A., Uleiurile esențiale și valoarea lor antibiotică. Volum de rezumate. Al VII – lea Simpozion de Etnofarmacologie cu participare internațională. Etnofarmacologie și Sănătate, Brașov – Șirnea , 23-24.06.2018;
5. Tomar U.S., Daniel V., Shrivastava K., Panwar M.S., Pant P., *Comparative evaluation and antimicrobial activity of Ocimum basilicum Linn. (Labiatae)*, *J. Global Pharmacol. Technol.* 2010, 2, 49;
6. Varga E., Bardocz A., Belák A., Maráz A., Boros B., Felinger A., Böszörményi A., Horváth G., *Antimicrobial activity and chemical composition of thyme essential oils and the polyphenolic content of different Thymus extracts*, *Farmacia*, 2015, Vol. 63, 3, p. 357-361;
7. Vlase L., Benedec D., Hanganu D., Damian G., Csillag I., Sevastre B., Mot C.A., Silaghi-Dumitrescu R., Tilea I., *Evaluation of Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activities and Phenolic Profile for Hyssopus officinalis, Ocimum basilicum and Teucrium chamaedrys*, *Molecules* 2014, 19(5), 54905507;
8. Wannissorn B., Jarikasem S., Siritwangchai T., Thubthimthed S. *Antibacterial properties of essential oils from Thai medicinal plants*, *Fitoterapia*, 76, 233236., 2005;
9. Zhang X., Guo Y., Guo L., Jiang H. , Ji Q., *In Vitro Evaluation of Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activities of Melaleuca alternifolia Essential Oil*, *Hindawi BioMed Research International*, Volume 2018.

STAGE OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL SUSTAINABLE TOURISM RESEARCH

Eng. C. M. VERDUGO BERNAL MSc.¹, R. GRUIA^{2*}

¹Escuela Superior Politécnica de Chimborazo, Ecuador

²Transilvania University of Brasov - Workstation of CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy; Corresp.Member of Academy of Romanian Scientist;

*Corresponding author: contact: ecotec@unitbv.ro

Abstract: This paper is an approximation to the current state of research on the social science of tourism, considered as such at the time of the 1960s because of its high contribution to economic and, therefore, socio-cultural and environmental dynamics. It is evident the study of evolution, advances, conceptions and the different modalities of world tourism, some historically known while others are emerging modalities that are evolving along with the change of demand preferences due to local and global conjunctural situations.

Keywords: tourism stage, theoretical and practical research, sustainable tourism.

1. Introduction

Tourism is one of the productive sectors that generate economic benefit, but it also affect natural environments. However, it has the potential to contribute to a more sustainable practices (Hunter, 1997) when: "The natural capacity of resources is used for a productive sector under the scheme of regeneration of the same natural resources, where the contribution of people and communities, customs and lifestyle is recognized, accepting that tourism it must be managed under an environment of equitable participation in economic development guided by the wishes of local people and communities in the host zones "(Eber, 1992).

The application of the philosophical postulates of sustainable development in tourism is one of the broad debates within sustainability since it has generated an evolution in terms of its application as a tool for conservation, falling mainly in the universal dissatisfaction created by the interactions between tourism companies, visitors, the natural environment and host communities (Murphy, 2005). Talking about the practical field of tourism, nowadays many new modalities of tourism are showing up on the world stage, some of them about created necessities in human being (Verdugo, 2016). This could be a good situation for tourism business but at the same time the activity causes many impacts on the environment and its elements, that is why many stakeholders

are practicing a responsible management of tourism.

2. Objectives

The papers shows up a general objective which is *Present the current state of the theoretical-practical research of Sustainable Tourism*, even though the research has specific objectives: a). *Review basic concepts of the tourist field, and its relationship with sustainability*; b). *Analyze how to bring tourism theory to practice*; c). *Review the current modalities of world tourism*; d) *Know the main tourist certifications in the world and in Ecuador*.

3. Material and Methods

This study is non-experimental in nature, based on review of secondary, descriptive and analytical sources. It was achieved through revision of secondary sources with a diachronic and synchronic analysis method and some interviews were conducted with experts in the practical field of tourism and its emerging modalities in the current globalized world.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Theoretical research of necessary concepts for tourism

A. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The origin of the concept of development as such is a term used by Old civilizations to denote an acceptable individual and social standard of

living, with exceptions from territories where religion or the socio-political situation have influenced the creation of singular ideologies (Robert Nisbe, 1995).

After the Second World War, the word development was justification for national policies in different countries. The sociologist Alain Touraine (1995) said the idea of development seems to have disappeared from the social mind and the market and religion face each other. The American sociologist Robert Nisbet (1991) says: "The idea of progress maintains that humanity has advanced in the past - starting from an initial situation of primitivism, barbarism or even nullity - and that it continues and will continue to advance in the future" (1980: 24).

a). Approaches

DEVELOPMENT APPROACH	DETAIL
1. Modernization (1945-1965)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Economic, political, sociological and psychological sciences converge. ➤ "The Alliance for Progress" are applied in the Third World.
2. Economic Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The Americans Nurske (1953), Lewis (1955) and Baran (1957): accumulation of capital and industrialization. ➤ Rosenstein (1961) investment of physical capital. ➤ Lewis (1958), Fei (1964) and Ranis (1971): modern industry will absorb agriculture. ➤ Whitman: redistribution of income and creation of a new dominant elite in the backward regions.
3. The sociological contribution to modernization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Durkheim: modify traditional structures without breaking the social equilibrium. ➤ Roles (family, work and citizenship). ➤ Government's consent, there would be an educated class whose 'status' is linked to modern occupational careers.
4. Dependence (1965-1980)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Latin America, the mid-60s, social change and broke with modernization. ➤ the guerrillas (Cuban and Guevara model) ➤ Rise the group of <i>Non-Aligned countries</i> ➤ Dependence-Marxist theory of capitalism (Cardoso, F. 2005).
5. Environmental Approaches to Development (1970-1990)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Development models that use natural resources as inexhaustible sources of economic income. ➤ Emergence ecodevelopment, (1970 to 1990). ➤ UN Conference (Stockholm, 1972), link between economic, social and environment.
6. Basic needs and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 70s Basic Needs (Paul Streeten) education, health, because they

development on a human scale (1975-1980)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ contribute to increase labor productivity. ➤ Streeten writes: (1989).satisfaction of basic human needs is more important than reducing inequality. ➤ The Neoliberal: In the 80's, IMF and WB assume the design of the economic policies of the Third World countries – external debt non-payment.
---	---

Source: Theory for development, 1986
Prepared by: Verdugo, C. 2018

Current stage of theoretical research and practical activity in the field of global sustainable tourism.

Tourism as a commercial activity has always been characterized by its high global demand in general terms, since it offers the possibility of occupying leisure time that everyone has in greater or lesser quantity during the work or academic year, tourism formally when organizing the first ventures of travel agencies, in 1841 Thomas Cook organized the first planned tour of history and set precedent of the tourist package (Hamilton, D & Douglas, J. 2005).

The world has undergone a globalization process due to major changes in the economic, social and environmental spheres, in this sense, tourism stakeholders emphasize the importance of this productive sector as a "responsible business" (Santana, A. 2008), which is capable of generating foreign exchange, employment and regional development, becoming an engine of development in territories eager to become financially dynamic thanks to the use of the natural and cultural resources they harbor (Vargas Martínez, Castillo Néchar & Zizumbo Villareal, 2011).

B. CONCEPTIONS OF TOURISM

Tourism, which being a human activity is addressed from different disciplines and perspectives (Hall, 2009). The different disciplines that study tourism, analysed as a science since the year 1970, when social scientists began to develop research in local and national tourism and its impacts on destinations. Thus, sociology and anthropology with research by MacCannel (1999) and Smith, V. (1977), respectively, were the strengths of the investigative process.

Although it is true, tourism must be analyzed fundamentally from the economy an also analyses perspective of Anthropology, producing a variety of anthropological events in tourist

destinations that produce social impacts directly affecting the natural and social environment. (Burns, 1999).

On the other hand, sociology is one of the disciplines that put into practice the analysis mainly of tourist leisure. "(Martínez Quintana, 2006: 65).

As a consequence, tourism geography is born, another way of looking at it is from social research. (Shaw & Williams. 2002)

C. CONCEPTUALIZING SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

"The natural capacity of resources is used for a productive sector under the scheme of regeneration of the same natural resources, where the contribution of people and communities, customs and lifestyle is recognized, accepting that tourism it must be managed under an environment of equitable participation in economic development guided by the wishes of local people and communities in the host zones "(Eber, 1992).

In this sense, sustainable tourism aims to be a positive and proactive approach to the management of development through tourism, trying to guarantee the long-term viability and quality of natural, cultural and human resources (Bramwell & Lane, 1993; Hughes, 1995; Sharpley, 2000; Swarbrooke, 1998).

4.2. Practical Tourism

A. TOURIST CERTIFICATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE ENTERPRISES IN THE WORLD

- European Charter for Sustainable Tourism in Protected Areas (CETS) that not only involves the protected area itself, but also the companies whose headquarters are in the space, and the companies that economically exploit the area.
- ISO 14000, standards whose objective is to promote standardization by protecting the environment, minimizing the harmful effects that can be caused by the company's activities.
- Blue flag, its criteria group the quality of bathing waters, information and environmental education, environmental management and safety, services and facilities.
- European Ecolabel (ECOLABEL) promotes products that reduce adverse environmental effects, contributing to an efficient use of resources.

- Biosphere Responsible Tourism, developed by the Institute of Responsible Tourism based on sustainability, environmental protection and cultural social enrichment.

B. CURRENT TOURISM MODALITIES

Traveling is one of the most rewarding activities for the human being, it is intimately related to pleasure and quality of life, and it is also a meeting point between different cultures that allow the development of moral, intellectual and emotional values. Without forgetting the influence it has on the economy of the regions where this activity takes place, it also represents an interesting social phenomenon that mobilizes a large part of the world's population in different modalities:

- **Sun and beach tourism** (traditional and predatory); **Meeting Tourism** (companies that send their workers to meetings, conferences); **LGBT tourism** ("gay community"); **Nature Tourism** ecotourism, natural areas and local cultures); **Health tourism** (medicine and wellness, surgeries); **Cultural tourism** (religion and gastronomy, but material and immaterial heritage.

a). Other types of tourism

- ▲ *Black tourism* (visiting places where there were tragedies;
- ▲ *Red tourism* (visiting places related to Communist Party of China (PCC));
- ▲ *Gastronomic tourism* (experiencing the typical cuisine of a country);
- ▲ *Spiritual tourism* (boom that practices yoga, meditation, vegetarianism and different forms of alternative therapy);
- ▲ *Geotourism* (geological heritage); *Slow tourism* (originated in Italy in 80's, local gastronomy against the fast-food);
- ▲ *Funeral tourism* (visiting cemeteries where famous people lie);
- ▲ *Tourism Hipster* (young middle-class urban planners, especially interested in vintage items, "organic" foods and "authenticity");
- ▲ *Virtual tourism* (Online reservation systems, know a place without needing to be there.

1. Types of non-conventional tourism:

- (1). War tourism (active war zones).
- (2). Tourism shark (diving with sharks).
- (3). Atomic tourism (Chernobyl museum, Hiroshima).

- (4). Tourism "Tolkien"(places of filming "The Lord of the Rings" and "The Hobbit").
- (5). Marijuana tourism (Netherlands, Amsterdam, cannabis coffees).
- (6). Sex tourism (not agree that it is framed as a tourism modality due to the whole chain of social problems that it entails (Soto, J. 2017)
- (7). Narcotourism (excursions to the Tepito neighborhood, full of drug sellers, criminals)

2. Current Problems of Tourism

World tourism, and the problems of high demand

By 2020 it is expected that 1600 million tourists will travel around the world. It is called "The Tourism Time Bomb."

There are three potentially stages:

- 1) An increase in prices in the big cities most demanded by tourists, especially hotels;
- 2) Emergence of waiting lists is more usual, places cannot support massive crowds;
- 3) The appearance of new tourist destinations, due to the saturation of others.

UNWTO (2017): tourism should be a means of development supported by five basic principles:

- (1). Generating inclusive economic growth;
- (2). Creating decent jobs and contributing to social improvements.
- (3). Watching over the environment and the conservation of nature
- (4). Respecting people diversity, identities and material and immaterial cultures
- (5). Fostering peace, a fundamental requirement for the development and progress of humanity.

Tourism-phobia and security

There are anti-tourism campaigns in many destinations, the so-called "turismofobia". Critical movement that has spread like wildfire, messages against this industry and concrete attacks against "unwanted" visitors in some European capitals.

Challenges of the tourism sector in 2018

- (1). Guaranteeing the safety of travelers.
- (2). The ways to reach potential customers (70% of travel decisions in a social network).
- (3). Visitors move more by events (sports, cultural.) than by visiting destinations.
- (4). Opinions matter and increasingly (Booking, Tripadvisor).
- (5). New technologies have arrived for travelers.
- (6). Quality more than quantity.
- (7). Compete doing something unique.

C. EMERGING DESTINATIONS

(UNAM, 2015) Emerging tourism encompasses very interesting proposals,

innovative formats and destinations that for years were considered unthinkable by large companies and large segments of the public.

Bhutan (Himalayas), Maldives (Indian Ocean), Santorini (Greek island), Boston (museums, monuments, history, movie sets, whale watching), Biarritz (golf courses, spas and surfing), Puerto Rico (Beaches, gastronomy), Kenya (Mombasa and Nairobi), Mauritius (beach, warm temperatures), Macao (Asian metropoly), Iron (Spain Islan and volcanic geography), Montreal (Quebec, jazz, Grand Prix of Formula 1), Copenhagen (families riding bicycles), Malta (architecture, history and paradisiacal beache), Cambodia (The country of the floating villages, Bulgaria (Slavic and Thracian heritage), Chiang Mai (more than 300 temples), Naples (authenticic Neapolitan pizza was invented at the beginning of the 18th C.)

D. TOURIST MODALITIES ECUADOR

Ecuador is a country possessing four exuberant natural regions worthy of being exhibited touristic, however it is mentioned that despite having nature to interpret, it still lacks a developed tourist plant because the current one is incipient. The mentioned regions have been named as the four worlds of Ecuador and are: Galápagos, Costa, Andes and Amazonia within which the tourism modalities legally recognized by the Ministry of Tourism of Ecuador (MINTUR) have been established based on the annual demand that arrives from other countries and even from the interior of the Ecuadorian territory, this rests in the Integral Plan of Tourist Marketing of Ecuador.

According to PLANDETUR 2020 of Ecuador, the main current tourism product lines of Ecuador are grouped into 11 product lines under the concepts of General Circuits, Sun and Beach, Community Tourism, Cultural Tourism, Theme Parks, Ecotourism and Nature Tourism, Tourism of Sports and Adventure, Tourism of Health, Agroturismo, MICE-Meetings, Incentives, Conferences and Exhibitions; and Cruises.

a). Criteria for application by destinations and use of sustainability indicators

The monitoring and management of the application of the strategic bases (programs and projects) in each one of the defined tourist destinations and those defined in the tourist territorial planning program of the Plan, should be done based on the monitoring indicators for sustainable tourism on cross-cutting measures.

♣Public Sector considers financed projects with public funds as they are integrated within the regional tourist destinations and under of specified product lines.

♣Private sector it will allow to focus tourism projects and companies according to the regional destinations and the tourist products.

♣Community sector: their traditional non-tourist economic activities will have a reference on the tourism product lines.

F. TOURIST CERTIFICATIONS IN ECUADOR

Certifier Rainforest Alliance (Alianza para Bosques):

The support for the implementation of good tourism practices is received from the international conservation organization

Rainforest Alliance, thanks to the financial support of the Multilateral Investment Funds of international enterprises.

Smart Voyager

It is a travel certification company, which works in Ecuador under the motto that allows travelers to recognize in them an active concern for the sustainable management of natural, cultural and social resources.

Smart Planet

It is a certification program for companies that seek an environmental balance in their activities. They advise companies in: reduce the ecological footprint, management systems, renewable energies, and awareness of consumer.

Tourcert

With the support of the Austrian Development Agency (ADA) by training the local population and sensitizing them on social and ecological issues, it ensures that sustainable tourism structures continue to develop independently.

G. COMMUNITY TOURISM IN CUADOR

1. Entrepreneurship in the four tourist worlds of Ecuador

AMAZONIA

Kapawi

Kapawi Ecology is an award-winning community ecotourism enterprise in the Rainforest that offers experiences with Achuar indigenous nation.

COAST

Mashpi Lodge: A bubble of luxury among the clouds, where contemporary design moves in harmony with nature.

HIGH LANDS (SIERRA)

CORDTUCH Puruhua Rzurku: It is the legal office in which eleven indigenous communities of the Chimborazo Province came together to promote community tourism (Guadalupe, A. 2016).

GALAPAGOS

In Santa Cruz Island, where giant turtle tortoises live freely, several families of farmers, fishermen and artisans have organized hosting tourists in their homes.

Conclusions

Tourism is a very important part of the cultural and social development of the heritage, which concerns the territorial integrity and the competition of the activist.

Tourism is one of the most important motors of economics in receptor countries, so it can help in crisis times going from a complementary activity into a main activity holding the national economy.

Authorities must guarantee, conserve and promote the natural and cultural heritage, the raw material of tourism.

It is the responsibility of the tourism industry to ensure that it interacts with stakeholders by providing training about tourism modalities.

Ecuador requires an effective plan to activate tourism and link all stakeholder and infrastructure necessities.

Acknowledgements

A special recognition to Professor Romulus for his guidance, knowledge and understanding and all local informants from the city of Riobamba in Ecuador who could contribute with relevant information.

References

1. Rojas, G. (2015). *Desarrollo sostenible: origen, evolución y enfoques*. (Documento de docencia No. 3). Bogotá: Ediciones Universidad Cooperativa de Colombia. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.16925/greylit.1074>
2. Valcárcel, M. (2006). Departamento de Ciencias Sociales, Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú, Lima *Apuntes del CENES*

- ISSN 0120-3053 Volumen 35 - Nº. 62 julio-diciembre 2016. Pg. 15-52
3. Douglas, J. & Hamilton, H. and Brandon, H. *Thomas Cook: the holiday-maker*. Stround Editorial- Gloucestershire: Sutton Pub., 2005.
 4. Santana, A. *Estudios perspectivas en turismo. El turismo cultural. ¿Un negocio responsable?* Version on line ISSN 1851-1732. tur. v.17 n.4 Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires oct-dic. 2008.
 5. Soto, J. (2017). Notes from Wenesday, 16 Agosto 2017. *Turismo y el impacto de la explotación sexual*. www.nuestroturismo.com
 6. *Constitución de la República del Ecuador* book. (2008). Ecuadorian Government. Quito-Ecuador Pg. 12.
 7. 1960: *La década del prodigioso despegue del sol y playa* (2015). Notes from Saturday, 13 jun 2015 Galicia España. www.lasprovincias.es
 8. *Geoturismo sostenible en la red de espacios naturales protegidos de la comunidad autónoma del país Vasco*. (2015). Gobierno Vasco. Ministerio de medio ambiente y medio rural y marino. Pg 11.
 9. Cardoso, C. (2014). *Sosteniendo al turismo o turismo sostenible (TS). Reflexiones teóricas. Estudios y perspectivas en turismo*. versión On-line ISSN 1851-1732. Estud. perspect. Tur. vol.23 no.2 Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires - June. 2014.
 10. Mara, R. (2007). *Observatorio de innovación del turismo. Factores determinantes de competitividad para destinos turísticos en el marco de la sostenibilidad*. EMBRATUR. Ministerio do Turismo. Brasil. Revista académica volumen II – Número 1. Marzo 2007 pp. 12-16
 11. Orozco, J.; Machado, J.; Tierra, C. (2011). Escuela Superior Politécnica de Chimbozo. Management Enterprise Faculty. *Plan de negocios para la comercialización de mermeladas en la Asociación Quilla Pacari en la provincia de Chimborazo, ciudad de Riobamba, parroquia Calpi, comunidad san francisco de Cunuguachay*. Riobamba-Ecuador. Pg. 22.
 12. Nisbe, R. (1995). *Conservadurismo*. Aliansa Editorial. First Edition. Goverment and Politics. Pg. 50.
 13. Touraine, A. (1995). *Production de la société* (1973). Social and human science. USA. Pg. 22
 14. Gilbert Ritz (2002), *Desarrollo y Desarrollo Rural: Enfoques y reflexiones*. Archivo de noticias, July 26, 2016. Cisepa.pucp.edu.pe
 15. Dos Santos, T. (2004). *Economía y sentimiento popular*. América Latina en Movimiento. Note: 13 february. 2004. <https://www.alainet.org/es/active/10630>
 16. Mouzakitis, A. (2017). *Hipotesis and Theory*. Published: 20 March 2017. Doi: 10.3389/fsoc.2017.0003. *Modernity and the idea of progress*.

GREEN TEA, COFFE AND CHOCOLATE – TYPICAL SOURCES OF ANTIOXIDANTS

L. POGAČNIK¹, N. POKLAR ULRIH¹

¹ University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Food Science and Technology, Jamnikarjeva 101, Ljubljana, SLOVENIA

*Corresponding author: lea.pogacnik@bf.uni-lj.si

Abstract: With appearance of new trends in a healthy lifestyle, people are searching for alternative sources of nutrition with a high content of antioxidants. Recently, green tea, coffee and chocolate have become known sources of nutritional antioxidants, and their effect has been extensively studied. The aim of the study was to compare antioxidant capacity (AOC) and total phenolics (TP) of green tea, coffee and chocolate of different origin and to study the influence of preparation procedure on the consumable antioxidants. AOC was determined by DPPH• assay, TP by Folin-Ciocalteu assay. Among green tea samples matcha tea infusions possess the highest AOC and TP. The antioxidants' content in tea infusions can be increased by extending the extraction time and/or by increasing the water temperature. Most of antioxidants are extracted by 100 mL of water, whereas matcha tea antioxidants are extracted to a bigger extent with higher amounts of water. As for coffee, the biggest influence on AOC and TP can be assigned to the preparation procedure; preparation of espresso coffee with higher water pressure giving more than the double values compared to the filter coffee. Furthermore, the higher amount of water results in higher AOC and TP, whereas the addition of milk does not have noticeable influence. Among chocolate samples the highest AOC and TP were determined in raw cocoa, followed by dark chocolate and milk chocolate, whereas the white chocolate showed negligible AOC and TP. The results show that the antioxidants' content strongly depend not only on a source but also on the preparation procedure.

Keywords: antioxidants, green tea, coffee, chocolate

1. Introduction

Variety of food is important in terms of providing essential nutrients in the human diet. With the emergence of new trends in a healthy lifestyle, people are looking for alternative sources of nutrition with a high content of antioxidants. The antioxidants, which allow the organism to defend against the oxidative stress, environmental pollution and other toxic substances play an important role in the healthy human nutrition. Herbs, vegetables and fruits provide many bioactive substances that act independently and synergistically and prevent the development of chronic and oxidative stress - related diseases. The biggest spectra of antioxidants are found in fruits and vegetables, namely green tea, cocoa, red and purple fruits/vegetable and orange vegetables [1]. Because of its sensory properties and socio-cultural factors, green tea is one of the most common drinks in the world and a source of variety of antioxidants, particularly polyphenols

[2]. It is produced from *Camellia sinensis* leaves that have not undergone the oxidation process used to make oolong teas and black teas. Green tea can contain up to 30% polyphenols in dry matter. Catechins, the most prevalent antioxidants in green tea, can contribute up to 10% dry matter [3]. Matcha belongs to green tea family, but it is produced in another way [4], resulting in higher levels of epigallocatechin gallate, and higher antioxidant capacity [5].

Brewed drink prepared from roasted coffee beans, which are the seeds of berries from the *Coffea* plant, among which the most commonly grown are *Coffea canephora*, *Coffea arabica* in *Coffea liberica*. Coffeic acid and chlorogenic acid are the main polyphenols in green coffee [6]. However, it was found out that roasting increases antioxidant capacity by factor 30 – production of melanoidins by Maillard reaction [7, 8]. Cocoa and cocoa products also belong to foods that are extremely rich with antioxidants (e.g. epicatechin) [9]. Cocoa solids are a mixture of many substances remaining after cocoa butter is

extracted from cacao beans. They are a key ingredient of chocolate, chocolate syrup, and chocolate confections, whereas the fatty component of chocolate is cocoa butter.

2. Materials and Methods

Instrumentation

The absorbance was measured with a spectrophotometer (Hewlett-Packard, model HP-8453, USA).

Chemicals

Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was purchased from Fluka, Germany. Trolox (6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid), chlorogenic acid (3-(3,4-dihydroxycinnamoyl) quinic acid) and DPPH[•] (2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl radical) were from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany. Methanol, ethanol and Na₂CO₃ were from Merck, Germany.

Preparation of green tea samples

The infusions were prepared by using 1,6 g of three different samples of tea (macha, green tea leaves – Sri Lanka and green tea in bags - India). Different preparation procedures were tested:

- Water temperature (70 and 100 °C)
- Duration of extraction (1, 3, 5 and 10 minutes)
- Volume of added water (100, 200, 300 and 400 mL)

Preparation of coffee samples

Coffee samples from different origin (Guatemala, Brasil and mixture of South American coffee) were used in our experiment. The grains were all from *Coffea Arabica* species. For each sample, 15 g of each type of milled coffee grains was used to prepare a filter and espresso coffee. The experiment was performed with different volumes of water (100 mL and 200 mL) and also with addition of milk (10 mL).

Preparation of cocoa and chocolate samples

For this research, two samples of dark chocolate (85% and 70% cocoa), two samples of milk chocolate (25.6% and 31% cocoa), one sample of white chocolate (0% cocoa) and a sample of cocoa powder (100% cocoa) was used. Approximately 4 g of each sample was extracted three times with 30 mL of hexane to remove lipids. After air-drying in a hood to remove residual hexane, the defatted material was extracted two times with 5 mL of acetone, water, and acetic acid in a ratio 70:29:1 (v/v/v), respectively. The solids were removed by centrifuging for 10 min at 6000 RPM.

Total phenol assay using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent

The total phenolics (TP) were determined spectrophotometrically using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent [10]. For preparation of calibration curves the reaction mixtures contained 725 µL standard solution of chlorogenic acid (31,0 - 220 µM) in 2% acetic acid and.

To this 125 µL Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (freshly diluted in water; 1:2) was added. After exactly 5 min, 125 µL 20% Na₂CO₃ (in water) was added. The solutions were mixed well and kept in the dark at ambient temperature for 1 h, to complete the reaction. Absorbance at 746 nm was measured against a blank sample that contained the corresponding amount of the solvent. To determine TP of the samples, they were 10-times diluted with 2% acetic acid and analysed as described above.

With all of the samples, the assays were carried out in duplicate, and the data are given as means (±SD). The TP of the samples is expressed as chlorogenic acid equivalent.

DPPH[•] scavenging capacity assay

The effects of antioxidants were evaluated through their antiradical activity. The decrease in DPPH[•] concentration shows a linear correlation with the antioxidant capacity (AOC) of a sample [11]. The reaction mixture was prepared as follows: 0.081 mM DPPH[•] (in methanol) was prepared fresh each day and kept in the dark to prevent its decomposition. For the reaction mixture, 70 µL standard solution of trolox (14.0-1000 µM) in 2% acetic acid, and 1 mL methanol solution of DPPH[•] were mixed.

The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured using a UV-Vis spectrometer at 517 nm after 1 h. To determine the AOC of the samples they were 10-folds diluted with 2% acetic acid and analysed as described above. With all of the samples, the assays were carried out in duplicate, and the data are given as means (±SD). The AOC using the DPPH[•] assay of the samples is expressed as trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC).

3. Results and discussion

Green tea

The recent study conducted by Štravs [12] aimed to compare AOC and TP in green teas of two different origin as well as matcha tea. Different methods of preparing tea infusions were studied. The basic tea infusion was prepared with 1.6 g tea sample and 100 mL of tap water at 70 °C and the samples were extracted for 3 minutes. Afterwards, the parameters of tea preparation (temperature, extraction time, amount

of water) were changed and AOC and TP were compared. The study confirmed that macha tea contains the most potent antioxidants, their amount being more than the double of the ones consumed by the regular green tea (in leaves or bags) (Fig. 1). We also showed that some preparation methods of the tea infusion have a significant effect on the AOC and TP. Longer extraction time showed a positive effect on both parameters. Same effect was observed when green teas were prepared at higher temperature (100 °C) and with lower amount of water. The prolonged time after preparation of the infusions showed no specific effect on the TP and AOC. Based on the overall results, the study concluded that macha tea infusions have the highest AOC and the highest content of TP. The AOC value and the content of SF are easily increased by extending the extraction time or increasing the water temperature in preparation of green tea infusions.

Coffee

Within the study of Cordin [13] we compared the content of TP and AOC in coffee from South America (Guatemala, Brazil, Rio Verde - Brazil) and Barcaffè coffee, which is a mixture of coffee grains from South America and is widely consumed in Slovenia. Coffee was prepared as espresso and as filter. We also prepared them with two volumes of water (150 mL and 300 mL) and with addition of milk (10 mL). The results show that the preparation method, the amount of water and the addition of milk affect the content of TP and AOC in coffee drink. The average TP content in espresso coffee is 20.5 mM and in filter coffee 7.4 mM, the average AOC in espresso coffee is 20.0 mM and 16.1 mM in filter coffee. By using a larger amount of water, the total content of TP and AOC increases with both methods of coffee preparation. The addition of milk resulted in slightly increased TP content and reduced AOC. Our results also show that the origin of coffee has no significant influence on the content of TP and AOC, more important is the process of its preparation.

Green tea vs. coffee

It is interesting to compare the amount of antioxidants consumed by regularly consumed drinks in our society. Our results show, that the highest amount of antioxidants is consumed by 300 mL filter coffee and by the same amount of macha tea (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) of green tea and coffee

Espresso coffee contains higher concentration of antioxidants, but due to its lower volume, the totally consumed antioxidants are less. Macha tea on the other hand is a very good source of antioxidants since the milled leaves of green tea are consumed and not removed before drinking as it is the case at regular green tea. That is also the reason why the green tea in leaves or tea in bags is a less rich source of antioxidants compared to macha.

Cocoa and chocolate

In the study of Gotal [14] the content of TP and AOC in the dark chocolates (85% and 70% cocoa), milk chocolates (25.6% and 31% cocoa), white chocolate (0% cocoa) and in the raw cocoa (100% cocoa) were determined and compared. From the defatted samples, extracts were prepared with a mixture of acetone and 2 % acetic acid solution 70:30 (v/v).

Fig. 2. Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) in correlation with mass fraction of cocoa (w_{cocoa})

The highest TP expressed as chlorogenic acid equivalent was determined in the raw cocoa (250 $\mu\text{mol/g}$) and the lowest in the white chocolate (2.0 $\mu\text{mol/g}$). As expected, the largest AOC expressed as trolox equivalent was determined in raw cocoa (207 $\mu\text{mol/g}$), whereas the white chocolate showed negligible AOC (0.2 $\mu\text{mol/g}$). The research also pointed that the content of cocoa in chocolate products strongly influences the TP and AOC (Fig. 2).

4. Conclusions

It can be concluded from the presented studies that all investigated representatives of regularly consumed foods have high levels of various antioxidants and their beneficial properties can be possibly contributed to those components. Nevertheless, it has to be stressed that preparation and processing of all of the natural sources can result in considerable decrease of many antioxidants, so they have to be treated carefully. And nevertheless, the bioavailability studies and study of other (besides antioxidant) potential health effects have to be performed in bigger extend in the future in order to have better insight into the possible effects (positive or negative if consumed in too high dosages) on our health.

Acknowledgements

Financial support for this work was provided by the Slovenian Research Agency (P4-0121). This paper is a result of the NT SMT-LS 2018 conference.

References

1. Benzie, I.F., Choi, S.W.: *Antioxidants in food: Content, measurement, significance, action, cautions, caveats, and research needs*. In: *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research* **71** (2014) p. 1-53.
2. Zhang, C., Suen, C. L., Yang, C., Quek S. Y.: *Antioxidant capacity and major polyphenol composition of teas as affected by geographical location, plantation elevation and leaf grade*. In: *Food Chemistry* **1**, **244** (2018) p. 109-119.
3. Komes, D., Horžić, D., Belščak, A., Kovačević Ganić, K., Vulić, I. *Green tea preparation and its influence on the content of bioactive compounds*. In: *Food Research International* **43** (1) (2009) p. 167-176
4. Baba, R., Amano, Y., Wada, Y., Kumazawa, K. *Characterization of the potent odorants contributing to the characteristic aroma of matcha by gas chromatography-olfactometry techniques*. In: *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* **65** (14) (2017) p. 2984–2989.
5. Yamabe, N., Kang, K. S., Hur, J. M., Yokozawa, T. *Matcha, a powdered green tea, ameliorates the progression of renal and hepatic damage in type 2 diabetic OLETF rats*. In: *Journal of Medicinal Food* **12** (4) (2009) p. 714-721.
6. Aguiar, J., Estevinho, B. N., Santos, L. *Microencapsulation of natural antioxidants for food application: The specific case of coffee antioxidants*. In: *Trends in Food Science & Technology* **58** (2016) p. 21-39.
7. Brezová, V., Šlebodová, A., Staško, A. *Coffee as a source of antioxidants: An EPR study*. In: *Food Chemistry* **114** (2009) p. 859-868.
8. Dasgupta, A., Klein, K.. *Antioxidants in Food, Vitamins aand Supplements: Prevention and Treatment of Disease*. San Diego, Elsevier **1-2** (2014) p. 238-240.
9. Mhd Jalil, A.M., Ismail, A. *Polyphenols in cocoa and cocoa products: Is there a link between antioxidant properties and health?* In: *Molecules* **13** (2008) p. 2190-2219.
10. Singleton, V. L., Rossi, J. A. *Colorimetry of total phenolics with phosphomolybdic-phosphotungstic acid reagents*. In: *Am. J. Enol. Viticul.* **16** (1965) p. 144-153.
11. Bertalanic, L., Kosmerl, T., Poklar Ulrih, N., Cigić, B. *Influence of solvent composition on antioxidant potential of model polyphenols and red wines determined with 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **60** (50) (2012) p 12282-8.
12. Štravs, A.: *Comparison of antioxidant activity and total phenols in green tea and matcha tea: B. Sc. thesis* Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Food Science and Technology, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2018.
13. Cordin, M: *Antioxidants in coffee from South America: B. Sc. thesis* Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Food Science and Technology, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2018.
14. Gotal, V.: *Determination of antioxidants in cocoa and dark chocolate: B. Sc. thesis* Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Food Science and Technology, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2018.

OPTIMIZATION OF TOURISM INDUSTRY PARAMETERS IN RELATION TO LANDSCAPE MANAGEMENT

Eng. C. M. VERDUGO BERNAL MSc. 1, R. GRUIA2*

¹*Escuela Superior Politécnica de Chimborazo, Ecuador*

²*Transilvania University of Brasov - Workstation of CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy; Corresp.Member of Academy of Romanian Scientist;*

*Corresponding author: contact: ecotec@unitbv.ro

Abstract: Territorial planning is the key for tourism, because a correct diagnosis of the territory allows to discover its potential and through various technical tools, organize the areas in order to take advantage of each one, such tourism as a multidisciplinary activity which get dynamizing the local economy, preserve the biodiversity and rescue the host cultures. A consequence of managing this landscape, in which tourism takes place, is a better life and a sustainable development stage.

Keywords: optimization, tourism parameters, landscape management, territorial planning.

1. Introduction

About UNWTO, 2016: the tourist industry is defined as a “set of companies, establishments and other organizations whose main activity is to offer goods and services to tourism”, as a consequence of this offer is really important to define which are the most important and decisive parameters in Tourism.

Verdugo, 2017 says: Offer, demand, basic services, Touristic Infrastructure and stakeholders are relevant as part of the integrated tourism system. Understand all of them is basic in order to manage and improve the quality of them in praxis.

Once identify this important elements in a territory in which tourism can take place, it is really necessary apply some technical tools to validate the feasibility of tourism in that place. Forward, the vocation of that territory to fit tourism activity inside of that landscape which could have many potentials. In this sense, landscape management could be the clue to organize a conflictive territory where not always the activities are compatible with each other (Varone, R. 2002).

2. Objectives

The general objective of the research is *Analyze the factors of optimization of tourism with the help of landscape management*, moreover the

study has specific objectives: a). *review general concepts of the territory-tourism relationship* b). *Analyze the parameters of sustainable tourism* and c) *determine strategies that landscape management uses to optimize the parameters of sustainable tourism*.

3. Material and methods

This study is non-experimental in nature, based on review of secondary, descriptive and analytical sources.

It was achieved through revision of secondary sources with a synchronic analysis method and some interviews were conducted with experts in the practical field of tourism and its emerging modalities in the current globalized world.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Landscape management

A. GENERAL AND CONCEPTIONS

In recent decades, society has realized that technological capacity and demographic pressure have become a threat to many natural and cultural resources. Landscape as an element of environmental quality as well as historical and cultural value, which also represents an economic resource in terms of influencing the location and development of certain activities and the price of land (Zoido, 1998). This character of causal scene, quality, diversity and economic

competitive advantage has been recognized as such by the Council of Europe in the European Landscape Convention approved in 2000, whose purpose is to promote the protection and management of landscapes and organize European cooperation in these aspects.

One of the first characteristics that accompanies the landscape is the semantic in definition that is indistinctly attributed to the term as a synonym of physical environment, environment, and perceived space, exclusively formal element, both in current regulations and in the various methodologies of analysis. Therefore the Convention as a first step, in Chapter I, defines landscape and landscape management. The landscape designates any part of the territory, as perceived by the populations, whose character results from the action of natural and / or human factors and their interrelations.

- Geographers, geologists and ecologists analyze the landscape as the scene resulting from the ecological and territorial system.
- Engineers, architects and landscapers look at the landscape as an exclusively visual scene, where structural character prevails.
- Psychologists, human geographers and sociologists have a subjective appreciation of the landscape, developing surveys techniques.

B. LANDSCAPE

The landscape in the Territorial Ordinance Guidelines is considered as one more element in the General Guidelines regarding the elements and processes of the physical environment and the control of activities. Objectives that are implemented in the Territorial Plans and Subsidiary Rules are:

- Cataloging visual zones, avoiding negative.
- Cataloging the most visually accessible areas.
- Protection of natural and cultural landscape.
- Actions to avoid breaking current landscape.
- Special treatment for Municipal Plans.

The landscape has also been considered to establish the different Categories of Ordination of the Physical Environment for the Non-Urbanisable Land (environmental improvement, forestry, agro-livestock, water protection) and industrial landscape sets for other with specific characteristics.

1. Landscape from Culture

The Theoretical Framework has been constructed by means of the investigation of two concepts fundamental, considered pillars of research: the concept of *landscape from the cultural*

perspective and landscape assessment methods. In order to understand the use of land, it is very important to analyze how territory influences in kind of daily town's life and at the same time how people modify this land. The origins of the term have been investigated from the book "The Morphology of landscape" by Carl Sauer, the normative recognition from statements and regulations of international organizations such as UNESCO (1999), National Park Service (2002) and the European Landscape Convention (2000).

2. Territorial ordering for tourism

According to the public document called PLANDETUR 2020, of the Ecuadorian state; ordering the territory is fundamental when inserting tourism as a complementary activity to the national system of production of goods or services that sustain the economy of a nation. Thus, it mentions that the national tourist defined from the units of tourist interest (zones, areas, sites) that are linked through the tourist corridors, forming the tourist destinations regional, requires a territorial ordering as sustenance for its management from the different levels of decentralized public administration. The planning process and the subsequent administration of the territories should be coordinated with the sectional governments in the logic of the decentralization processes. During the national planning process, the concept of bioregions, tourism potential, poverty rates and the location of cooperation for development will be considered. In this framework, the following activities are proposed:

Activity 1. Consolidate the provincial, cantonal and parochial local strategic plans, with the strategic tourism plans and the Strategic Plan of the National System of Protected Areas.

Activity 2. Prepare the National Plan of Territorial Organization for Sustainable Tourism.

Activity 3. Contracting and Elaboration Tourism Plans in Regional Destinations.

Activity 4. Preparation of zoning plans for community tourism.

2.1 Tourism as a territorial strategy

a). Diagnose the territory to discover its vocation

Territorial planning is key for tourism, because through a correct diagnosis of the territory it can discover its potential and then put in order the vocation of the areas, for instance South America delimits natural areas in many different activities such as: extractive activities (oil and wood),

intangible (that your resources are not touched), use ancestor of the local population (shamanism, family farms, ceremonial sites), buffer zone (tourism, education, research), binational (socio-economic exchange) (Verdugo, C. 2018).

b) Segment the tourist offer

In some countries have segmented the tourist offer in tourist modalities such as ecotourism, adventure, culture and history. The tourists stay more days in these territories, therefore the economic income will be higher and conservation effort also increases against a higher load capacity in tourist sites.

c) Community Participation

Tourism destinations must grow in a planned, responsible and orderly manner without affecting local communities, which is why territorial planning is increasingly necessary (Valenti, L. 2016)

Certain states such as the Ecuadorian have a national policy to segment the territory not only geographically but also administratively for which it is divided into zones grouping similar provinces by their population number, productive activities and geographical proximity, this is reflected in documents called Plans of Territorial Development and Regulation (PDOTs), which carry out a deep diagnosis of the territorial characteristics with the active participation of the local population that knows their needs and their singularities. (SENPLADES, 2016).

d) Increase spending

With a greater offer of tourism, an increase in the average spending of tourists and their stay could be achieved. In order to diversify the offer Government must perform some investments (Torres, L. 2017).

2.2 Territorial Heritage and Development

According to Jose Feria, (2015) about "Territorial heritage and sustainable development: It has been widely accepted for several decades that heritage must be regarded as a resource for societies to develop. However, It is important define and encompass in precise terms what is understood by both heritage and development.

2.3 Tourism and Natural Protected Areas

a) Trends affecting the planning of tourism and protected areas

Planning is a process that involves selecting a desirable future out of a range of plausible alternatives. In this context, the growth of interest in sustainable tourism and ecotourism reflects a rising tide of social concern about the quality of the natural environment and the effects of tourism. Activities closely associated with experiencing natural environments are very popular (Tourism Canada, 1995).

b) Rising educational levels and demand for travel

The average level of formal educational attainment is rising globally, for both males and females. Higher education levels are strongly correlated with demand for outdoor recreation activities, and lead to changes in the patterns of recreation and tourism. (Wight, 2001).

c) Changes in leisure time distribution

For many people, leisure time is increasing due to a shorter working week, increases in the automation of housework and other factors. Yet leisure time is decreasing for others; for example working women who retain household responsibilities. Growth in single parent family numbers increases the leisure time of the absent parent, yet reduces that of the responsible parent.

d) Increasing social and environmental concerns

Across the globe, people express concern about social injustices and environmental problems. They are increasingly aware of the need for low impact tourism which does not harm the environment.

Some tourists are "voting with their feet". They are attracted to destinations that have a positive reputation.

2.4 Globalisation of the economy

In a globalised economy, individual countries and communities are influenced by decisions and economic conditions elsewhere. This linkage between origin and destination communities makes achieving sustainable tourism difficult, since the host country often has a limited ability to influence tourist trends; it also leads to competition between destinations.

2.5 Growth and diversification of market niches

The number of people taking part in many outdoor activities is growing, especially in hiking, cycling and water-based activities such as

sea kayaking or scuba diving. There has also been a huge growth in 'soft' adventure and ecotourism or nature-tourism types of trips. The tourism industry has responded to this range of interests by developing many types of niche market packages.

Chart 1. Potential benefits of tourism in protected areas

Tourism potential benefits in protected areas	
Enhancing economic opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases jobs for local residents • Increases income and diversifies enterprises. • Obtains new markets and improves living standards • Funding for protected areas and local communities
Protecting natural and cultural heritage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conserves biodiversity (species and ecosystems) • Protects cultural values and heritage resources for local and visitors. • Improves local facilities, transportation and communications • Self-financing mechanisms for protected area operations
Enhancing quality of life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotes aesthetic, spiritual, and other values related to well-being • Environmental education for visitors and locals • Intercultural understanding • Culture, crafts and the arts • Learn languages and cultures of foreign tourists.

4.2 TOURISM INDUSTRY

4.2.1. Tourist industry Concepts

The participation of the tourism industry is essential for sustainable tourism to be a success. Tour operators, hotels, cruise ships and recreational activity providers make substantial differences when using environmentally appropriate practices. The tourism industry has many faces and consists of a wide variety of tour operators, hotel operators, cruisers and providers of recreational activities. In order for tourism to be carried out in a sustainable manner, all representatives of these businesses must be contacted and included in the planning process (MANUAL OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY. 2014)

4.2.2. Determining factors of the tourism industry

a. General determining factors

a). Changes in the level of demand, b). The conjuncture, c). Social and political stability and world peace, d). Improvements in means of accommodation and transport and reduction of travel costs, e). Elimination of international obstacles to tourist traffic (Committee of the League of Nations, 1934)

4.3 SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

4.3.1 Characteristics

A common definition of sustainable tourism is the one of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO):

"Sustainable tourism development meets the need of present tourists and host regions while protecting and enhancing opportunity for the future.

It is envisaged as leading to management of all resources in such a way that economic, social, and aesthetic needs can be fulfilled while maintaining cultural integrity, essential ecological processes, biological diversity, and life support system." [WTO 1998: 19]

4.3.2 SUSTAINABILITY AS A PLANNING CRITERION

a. Sustainability a controversial but necessary concept for tourism

The basic idea about sustainability is still quite superficial and contrasts with a state of scientific discussion in which there is still a long way to go: lack of a standardized and reference system of indicators and, above all, the absence of a clear sequence of actions that can take the principles from the declaration phase of good intentions to practice. The concept receives different denominations according to the reference geo-linguistic scope (sustainable development among the Anglo-Saxons, lasting development in the French-speaking world).

4.4 PARAMETERS OF TOURISM FOR QUALITY / OPTIMIZATION

The paradigm of sustainability is today one of the pillars on which tourism activity is based, associated on the one hand with the idea of continuous improvement in the quality of services and on the other with the systems of indicators that allow monitoring these progresses. Regarding the latter, a Tourist Sustainability Indicator System (SIST) consists, above all, in a geostatistical information system in which each

indicator has an analytical expression: the formula, a graphic expression: the trend function, and a cartographic expression: the map showing territorial heterogeneity. (Sanchez, D. 2007. A SYSTEM OF BASIC TOURIST INDICATORS: FIRST APPROACH)

4.4.1 Tourist sustainability of indicators for measurement

In the fifties, the American William Deming (1900-1993) introduced the idea that quality is a strategic weapon, allowing a better positioning in the market because of the prestige it entails and also by reducing costs for compensation.

Tourism is an activity that is usually seen as an opportunity for growth; However, aspects such as the supply of drinking water, the final disposal of waste, the compatibility of land uses, the depletion of natural resources, the spatio-temporal distribution of tourists, the carrying capacities (Ochoa, 2004), etc., must be carefully considered to guarantee its sustainability. The economic benefit is closely related to the preservation of the natural environment and local cultural heritage, which are real resources for destinations, to motivate the interest of the tourists themselves.

Parallel to the efforts and public and private initiatives in the world, the UNWTO advanced in the design of a methodology to establish indicators of sustainable tourism. A working group conducted research in tourist destinations in countries such as the Netherlands, Canada, the United States, Mexico and even Argentina, and from them a set of key indicators was defined, a list of supplementary indicators for specific destinations and a methodology for their preparation. , all of which was published in the Practical Guide for the development and use of sustainable tourism indicators (WTO, 1997).

Based on this experience, UNWTO carried out four continental workshops in order to show the application of the indicators to tourism managers and managers. The first two were organized in Hungary and Mexico in 1999 and the last two in Sri Lanka and Villa Gesell in 2000 (UNWTO, 2000). There are numerous examples regarding the successful application of indicators at different levels of public administration. For example, in Mexico they are used to quantify the environmental impact of tourism services for more than a decade (FONATUR, 1996). Another

case is the Costa Rican Tourism Institute, which has been working for years on a certification system for tourism sustainability (Costa Rica, 1997).

4.4.2 Good indicators and their characteristics

In practice, indicators can only be applied if there is a viable mechanism to measure them.

UNWTO (2005) suggests five criteria for the selection of indicators; however, we believe that good indicators must meet the following characteristics:

Clarity, Rigorousness, Relevance, Feasibility, Credibility, Comparability, Representativeness, Sensitivity, predictive value, Integrity, Applicability.

Tourism is an activity that is usually seen as an opportunity for growth; however, aspects such as the supply of drinking water, the final disposal of waste, the compatibility of land uses, the depletion of natural resources, the spatio-temporal distribution of tourists, the carrying capacities (Ochoa, 2004) , etc., must be carefully considered to guarantee its sustainability.

(Beni, 2001) A system of indicators is much more than a set of indicators; in a system the indicators must be comparable and correlated; for this he must follow a methodological journey that makes it possible. On the other hand, the system is composed of four subsystems or dimensions: Environmental, Sociocultural, Politica-Institutional, Economic, (Coriolano, 2006).

4.5 OPTIMIZE TOURISM FACTORS - GOOD PRACTICES

From the analysis of several authors it is established that among other ways, two are ideal tools to optimize the particularities of tourism spaces in the framework of sustainability and landscape management:

* The generation and use of tourism indicators in the decision making of the public, private and community sectors and

* The use of techniques and instruments for tourism planning of the territory (inventories, tourism potential, carrying capacity, demand analysis, environmental analysis, cartography and GIS to generate tourism plans)

4.5.1 GENERATION OF INDICATORS

As a result of what has been analyzed in the previous section and a global experiences three subsystems have been proposed:

a. Environmental Subsystem

The selected indicators: quality of the natural landscape, protected areas, land uses, water for consumption and sanitation. They give an important weight to the natural environment, and in particular to the quality and tourist potential of the territories.

b. Economic Subsystem

Indicators respond to public income, employment, tourism offer, equipment and infrastructure. There are several works on tourism economics that mention indicators (Arendit, 2000, Lage, 2001, Tribe, 2003).

c. Socio-cultural subsystem

Demography, education, security, housing and poverty. Focus on the social problem, given that the culture is difficult to quantify and at the same time was considered through the political-institutional perspective.

d. Institutional Subsystem

Citizen participation, social policy, cultural policy, health policy and security policy. They put weight on social and cultural policies.

a). Techniques and instruments for territorial analysis

Territorial planning goes beyond the mere delimitation of zones and represents, at present, an indispensable option of social and economic consensus, and an instrument for territorial harmonization and spatial readability.

The planning of the territory raises three basic principles: 1) *The efficiency*. Organize activities in space coherently; 2) *Fairness* linking human activities to the territory; 3) *hierarchy and complementarity*. The integration of different territorial areas in those of superior scope, that is to say, concordance between the local and regional plans and between these and the national ones.

As already said, a territory is ordered to meet predetermined objectives that come together in two large blocks: **territorial equity** and **the rational use of resources**.

Chart 4. *Elements of a territorial plan*

Objectives and Strategies	Systems
Regional Planning Subregional planning	Physical system
	Topography and territorial model, Climate and vegetation, Natural resources, Landscape, Protected spaces, Waste management, Natural risks
	Productive System
	Basic/secondary economic activities, Equipment, Human Resources, Location, Zoning
	Relational System
	Internal structure and articulation, outside Integration, Accessibility, Public transport, Telecommunications
	Urban System
Central places/ hierarchies, Urban systems, Development axes	

Source: Hindenbrand, A. 1996

In summary, the steps to follow in order to determine a technical landscaping management for Tourism are:

1. Inventories,
2. Tourist potential,
3. Load capacity,
4. Demand analysis
5. Environmental analysis and
6. Cartography and GIS to generate tourism plans for the territory

4.6 HOW TO OPTIMIZE SOME TOURISM PARAMETERS IN RELATION WITH LANDSCAPE MANAGEMENT IN ORDER TO RATIONALIZE SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

4.6.1 Guidelines for determining territorial ordering with a focus on the conception of the tourist space

Once an analysis, diagnosis of the study site and its territorial characteristics have been made, the tourist attractions inventoried by the Ministry of Tourism are identified, noting the importance as mentioned before, of updating the inventory of the attractions tourist, as it is evident the presence of several of them that are of interest to tourists and that are developed around these various activities; thus also a revision to the management categories proposed by the PDOT (2015); proposing then an application of the territorial ordering of the tourist space of the Cuenca canton, in favor of the planning of the tourist activities that can be developed in this territory taking refuge in the theories of ordering.

In this context, it is proposed for tourist purposes to order mainly urban territories, but the option to adapt territory units to rural:

Areas, Centres, Sets, Nuclei (Bullon, 2000).

Also on the basis of the experience of several technicians with an understanding of the application of landscape and territory management with tourism, it is proposed to optimize the following parameters as a strategy for responsible management of tourism.

Conclusions

* Most important parameters in Tourism are: Offer, demand, basic services, Touristic Infrastructure and stakeholders are decisive.

* All kind of territory needs to be planned through planning tools in order to development it responsibly and consider human activities and local culture

* Tourism industry shows a faster growing which is good for economy, nevertheless it must be controlled to frame into sustainability of resources and heritage.

* Sustainable Tourism must joint 5 areas to be complete and real: Economy, Environmental, Social, Cultural, Technology, and Politics.

* Sustainable Tourism could be reach using two powerful tools: Landscape management and System of indicators

Acknowledgements

A special recognition to Professor Romulus for his guidance, knowledge and understanding and all local informants from the city of Riobamba in Ecuador who could contribute with relevant information.

References

- Aspects of Tourism. Strategic management for tourism communities
<https://books.google.com.ec/books?hl=es&lr=&id=hjQVFbiIDPgC&oi=fnd&pg=PA1&dq=landscape+management+in+tourism&ots=6m7qNwSp1A&sig=ThR2is3xYrhnydWstJX4csNAz4M#v=onepage&q=landscape%20management%20in%20tourism&f=false>;
- Bolós, M & Gomez, A. Gestión del paisaje / coord. por Jaume Busquets Fàbregas, Albert Cortina Ramos, 2009, ISBN 978-84-344-2890-4, págs. 165-180;
- Bormann, Die Lehre vom Fremdenverkehr, p. 130;
- Busquets, Jaume; Cortina, Albert (2009) Gestión del paisaje: Manual de protección, gestión y ordenación del paisaje. Barcelona: Ariel, 703 páginas ISBN: 978-84-344-2890-4;
- Cf. W. Sombart: *Der Moderne Kapitalismus*, Vol. III, pp. 278 y sig.
- COUNCIL OF EUROPE, 2000. *European Landscape Convention*. Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of Europe.
- DECRETO 28/1997 de Directrices de ordenación Territorial de la Comunidad Autónoma del País Vasco.
- Dictionary of Nacional Biography*, Vol. II, pp. 55 – 58;
- Feria, J (2012). Territorial heritage and development. CRC Press. A Balkema Book. Boca Raton, Florida, USA. Pp.3-5;
- Feria, J. 2015. Territorial heritage and sustainable development- Conceptual basis and methodological issues. University Pablo de Olavide, Seville, Spain, p.3;
- Hernández, M. (2010). Investigaciones geográficas, ISSN 0213-4691, ISSN-e 1989-9890, Nº 51, 2010, págs. 275-276;
- Informe del Economic Comité of de League of Nations. Agosto, 1934. Ver también Haussler: *Der Fremdenverkehr*, pp. 77;
- Landscape Management. Village renewal • land consolidation • land development regionalL, Rural Development in Bavaria. Editorial department: Dr. G. Aulig, N. Bäuml, Central Agency of the Bavarian Rural Development Service. Print: Holzmann Druck, Bad Wörishofen. 2008 Josef Miller ministry of Forestry.
14. Manual de la industria del turismo. Pp.3-7. ESPANA.
https://nmssanctuaries.blob.core.windows.net/sanctuaries/prod/media/archive/management/pdfs/Day7_INDUSTRY_MANUAL_esp.pdf;
- Muño, F. (2009.) Paisajes metropolitanos. Gestión del paisaje / coord. por Jaume Busquets Fàbregas, Albert Cortina Ramos, 2009, ISBN 978-84-344-2890-4, págs. 61-76.
- Plan de desarrollo rural sostenible de la comunidad autónoma del País Vasco (2000-2006). Departamento de Agricultura y Pesca. Gobierno Vasco.
- Robalino, R. 2017. Facultad De Arquitectura Y Urbanismo, Departamento De

- Postgrados, "Ordenación Territorial Del Espacio Turístico. Un Aporte En El Marco Del Plan De Desarrollo Y Ordenamiento Territorial Del Cantón Cuenca 2015-2019". Tesis de grado: Magister en Ordenación Territorial mayo 2017. Pp.15,17,56;
18. Rotger, D. (2012). Gestión del paisaje y ordenamiento territorial: Abordajes conceptuales y metodológicos XI INTI International Conference La Plata. 17 al 20 de octubre 2012. Esta obra está bajo licencia 2.5 de Creative Commons Argentina.
 19. Rowen, I. (2014). Tourism as a territorial strategy: The case of China and Taiwan. *Annals for tourism research*. Pp.-13. Recovery from: <https://cpbus1.wpmucdn.com/blogs.ntu.edu.sg/dist/f/1564/files/2017/12/Rowen-2014-Tourism-as-territorial-strategy-x64350.pdf> ;
 20. Salvador ante clavé y francesc Gonzales reverté. Planificación territorial del turismo p.4 <http://reader.digitalbooks.pro/book/preview/28694/chap1.xhtml/-?1535554410246>
 21. Sánchez, D. (2007). UN SISTEMA DE INDICADORES TURÍSTICOS BÁSICOS: PRIMERA APROXIMACIÓN. Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Instituto Multidisciplinario de Historia y Ciencias Humanas (IMHICIHU), Departamento de Investigaciones Geográficas (DIGEO). Saavedra 15, 5°. Buenos Aires.2007;
 22. Seattle University. Guidelines for Sustainable Landscape Management. May 2009. Prepared by O'Brien & Company 811 First Avenue, Suite 380 Seattle, WA 98104. P.5. USA;
 23. SENPLADES. (2016). Vinculación de participación ciudadana y planificación territorial. Gobierno del Ecuador. <http://www.planificacion.gob.ec/senplades-vincula-participacion-ciudadana-y-planificacion-territorial>;
 24. Soto- Bayó, S. (2009). Documents d'anàlisi geogràfica, ISSN 0212-1573, ISSN-e 2014-4512, N° 55, 2009, págs. 184-187;
 25. Sustainable Tourism Development in UNESCO Designated Sites in South-Eastern Europe Ecological Tourism in Europe – ETE. Koblenzer Str. 65, 53173 Bonn, Germany 2005;
 26. Taboada, J. (2014). <http://www.tysmagazine.com/la-importancia-de-la-gestion-del-paisaje-en-el-desarrollo-sostenible/paisaje:06/02/2014>;
 27. UNESCO. (1999). "The Morphology of landscape" by Carl Sauer, Cultural heritage conference. USA;
 28. COUNCIL OF EUROPE, 2000. *European Landscape Convention*. Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of Europe;
 29. DECRETO 28/1997 de Directrices de ordenación Territorial de la Comunidad Autónoma del País Vasco;
 30. Ferial, J (2012). Territorial heritage and development. CRC Press. A Balkema Book. Boca Raton, Florida, USA. Pp.3-5;
 31. Hernández, M. (2010). Investigaciones geográficas, ISSN 0213-4691, ISSN-e 1989-9890, N° 51, 2010, págs. 275-276;
 32. Informe del Economic Comité of de League of Nations. Agosto, 1934. Ver también Haussler: *Der Fremdenverkehr*, pp. 77;
 33. Landscape Management. Village renewal • land consolidation • land development regionalL, Rural Development in Bavaria. Editorial department: Dr. G. Aulig, N. Bäuml, Central Agency of the Bavarian Rural Development Service. Print: Holzmann Druck, Bad Wörishofen. 2008 Josef Miller ministry of Forestry.
 34. Manual de la industria del turismo. Pp.3-7. ESPAÑA. https://nmssanctuaries.blob.core.windows.net/sanctuaries/prod/media/archive/management/pdfs/Day7_INDUSTRY_MANUAL_esp.pdf.

ROMANIA, DONOR OF FOOD AND DRINKING WATER IN THE 21st CENTURY EUROPE, BY ENGINEERING AND MANAGEMENT

R. GRUIA*

* Transilvania University of Brasov - Workstation of CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy; Corresp. Member of Academy of Romanian Scientist ;
Contact: ecotec@unitbv.ro

Abstract: *Consequently to demographic evolution, natural resource exhaustion and climatic changes from the last decades, in the present moment it becomes a major preoccupation, at international level, to solve the alimentary problem on average and long term. The paper is seeking for a series of solutions linked to the sustainability of the Romanian agri-food system in the future by applying bioeconomy principles, with the transition from Green Economy to Blue Economy, aiming for an inventory of natural resources in order to achieve agri-food renewing models. There are approached aspects regarding the adaptation of production systems, the conservation or reconversion of agro ecosystems and the application of the rules and techniques of circular economy to reuse secondary production, residues and wastes, as well as to make new food sources (as for example synthetic proteins).*

In the situation in which Europe's standard agriculture stagnates and drinking water becomes a problem, the paper objective is to emphasize Romania's role and place in this complicated problem, i.e. to show several helping steps in order to find solutions through which the Romanian agro-zootechnical and natural area may practically become a donor at continental level. It is made a synthesis of the passing towards predictive and integrated phyto-zoo-food systems, so that Romania, by defining such a profile, may become a European zone of interest and of high utility in the integration process, being capable to decisively contribute to the continental alimentary equilibrium in the 21st century.

Keywords: *agriculture, bio economy, circular economy, food, drinking water, phyto-zoo-food systems.*

1. Introduction

In the present, as we know, land, water and energy are more and more precious.

Standard agriculture seems to have reached its limits in certain parts of the globe. At European level, for example, and especially in the western part, the super saturation of land with chemical fertilizers paradoxically leads in the present to stagnation of productivity and quality of agricultural production, with effects upon animal breeding.

From here come worries for a proportional alimentary crisis that might install towards the year 2030 in EU. It is not surprising that financing for agri-food scientific research is generous in the present, but it seems that in the period 2021-2027 too (there is information from different EU documents).

The idea we are suggesting is that Romania, having a particular specificity (geo-climatic, technical and human) may play a part in solving possible food and drinking water crises, of course by approaching certain beneficial and well financed strategies, otherwise also presented at certain national and international events, or of different academies and professional associations (the Romanian Academy, Academy of Romanian Scientists, Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences and other).

In these conditions there are necessary elements that show premises from which one may start solving these problems. Consequently, premises regarding food and how to avoid alimentary problems in the 21st century have, in our opinion, two basic components, namely a series of premises at European level or at the Romanian space one.

As **European premise**, after conveyed scenarios, it appears as predictable a critical

point, namely: *the food crisis*. This approach is based on the dynamics of the natural and social environment: agro-ecosystem exhaustion, climate changes, demographic increase and others. From the perspective of the integrated field of *engineering and management* there may be observed a series of agri-food technological limitations, such as those of saturation by chemification and stagnation at production level. Therefore a technological and managerial regeneration of the field is to be imposed in the future decades.

This reorientation and regeneration may be made by applying the principles, rules and techniques of an integrated concept that aims both economic efficiency and systemic efficacy, that also takes into consideration natural and biologic phenomena (including efficacy, ecosystem productivity and others), namely **the concept of engineering and management** (Bogdan A.T.,2012; Gruia,R.,2016; Abrudan,I., 2018).

Therefore, the collocation „*ENGINEERING AND MANAGEMENT*” represents the unitary concept by which **engineering** is to be found by applying *scientific* knowledge and practical experience necessary to create products, or useful processes, approach that is complementary and in integrated dynamics with **management** or with the activity to *administer* processes, or different organizations, as well as the art to make something together (in team) with other people on line of optimization, productivity, de effectiveness and efficacy. All that has been mentioned may be synthesized as integrated idea in the following defining proposal:

„ENGINEERING AND MANAGEMENT” is a unitary and integrated concept of scientific knowledge and of the technico-organizational management activity of systemic processes and phenomena, of technologic flows and of organizations in their integrality, in view of emergent development on the line of optimization, of efficiency, of economic and systemic efficacy.

As it may be observed, the concept may be applied in all situations and in all fields, so that it also becomes a useful tool for the agro-alimentary branch, from which the approached theme in this paper is derived.

Food and drinking water must be a basic preoccupation for our country, in the previously described context. As **Romanian premises**, we consider that it must be taken account of an

intelligent process to avoid the alimentary crisis. In essence it is necessary to take into consideration the *natural and social environment dynamics* in our country: climate changes, severe demographic decreasing and populating aging, as elements directly linked to phyto-zoo-food production. Likewise, as for assuring the quantitative and qualitative level with drinking water, the *dynamics and “smart” actions by engineering and management* become opportune in order to avoid losses of water and its conservation during drought: - regularization of water streams; - water stream and reservoir desilting; - spring maintenance; - antipollution measures (National report, 2004). Concomitantly, it is absolutely obligatory to totally solve the irrigation system in Romania.

We refind the *Principles of engineering and management* as applicable during drought.

It must be specified that, for our country, there are in fact two opposed scenarios: either nothing constructive is done and we will become food and water dependent, or we find solutions and apply them to this S.O.S. Romania ! We mean to avoid critical points in the stipulated changes from the 21st century, with effect in drought counteraction and demographic and natural environment „desertification” and salvation from exhaustion of the *water table* from aquifer strata (the first water saturated horizon met under soil surface, with level variation influenced by climate conditions).

As a first conclusion: an intelligent strategy becomes urgent for the balanced development of the Romanian agriculture in relation with *nature – food & water – human resource*.

The approached theme is complicated and vast. That is why we concentrate the study objectives on three directions: - to be aware of avoiding „*The big disaster*”: in the future to look for water and food outside Romania, which aims an „*alert*”; - to make a synthesis on „*Engineering and management*” principles through which in the decades to come the Romanian phyto-zoo-food and natural area may become a national resource with reserve potential and attractor for „*food and water*”, which aims a „*clear vision and professionalism*” ; - to find production theoretical and practical solutions concerning the „*Big chances*”: to imagine basic conditions necessary to produce and sell Romanian food and drinking water, with internal destination, but also for exportation, especially to contribute with food and water at the level of EU in the uncertain

future, which aims to capitalize a serious „opportunity”!

2. Methodology and work hypotheses

As a result of the information, it has been made a data processing that aimed to be organized in systematic logics in several steps, as follows:

Step I - Remediation of the standard system of agricultural production; the concept of **engineering and management**, as a method towards an intelligent and phyto-zoo-food integrated system;

Step II - Orientation of the production towards European „oasis”, such as Romania, in order to capitalize the existing **biodiversity**;

Step III - Imposing **bioeconomic** principles and the practice of *circular economy* (capitalization of raw material by recovery, from the 70-80 % “thrown” food products, secondary products, wastes, residues etc.);

Step IV - Passing towards new resources of food, namely towards **synthetic proteins** (reserve of food in conditions of „casualty” of the 21st century: demographic explosion, climate changes and severe reduction of the environment conditions and of the fertile agricultural land and, implicitly, of the agri-food offer);

Step V - Technical and psychological change of the **feeding manner**: *new alimentary directions* and a new *culinary paradigm* by applying vanguards ideas: biocomplexity, personalized and predictive gastronomy and others / biotechnological reconceptualization and others.

3. Results and discussions

Covering the 5 mentioned steps, it is attempted to solve the proposed objectives, so that the idea of active actor may be sustained, i.e. **Romania may be a „donor” in the European food security** in the decades to come. The integration on the axes: *The integration on the axes: man-food & natural environment* is underlined.

3.1. Methodological priorities for the development of the Romanian agri-food system

A first step is, by the **engineering and management** methodology, to support Romania’s priorities in population’s food security. The potential we have entitles us to analyze the possibility to become a real European solution concerning food and drinking water. But

for this the technico-organizational reorientation of the agro-food system is obligatory.

Without having the pretention to use the problem up, we mention among the elements necessary to such a strategy:

- *conservation* of the natural patrimony by the demarche of applied ecology (avoiding the destruction of the agricultural potential, in many regards, there are unwanted aspects of the present !);

- applying the methods and principles of the concept of *engineering and management* in the sustainable development of the agri-food system, having as marks:

- support of agriculture, as *strategic branch* of the national economy =by **engineering** (last generation science and technology)

- adaptation of „*smart*” *criteria* in the country strategic project = by performing **management** („*smart*”/ intelligent, but also managerial acronym of *characteristics*: **s**pecific, **m** measurable, **a**ccessible, **r**elevant and framed in **t**ime)

3.2. Diagnosis concerning natural and cultural potential to support the Romanian agri-food system

Step 2 is important in order to exactly understand the existing situation, i.e. to collect data in order to inventory the natural and cultural-scientific patrimony supporting the Romanian agri-food system.

In the conditions when climate changes already affect the capacity to produce food, the new conceptual approaches undoubtedly lead to finding scientific and technical solutions. Essential seem to be the idea to capitalize local *geo-climate and cultural biodiversity*. These aspects sustain the fact that Romania has the potentiality to become a European solution for food and drinking water.

As for **biodiversity** it is known the fact that in the Romanian space there live numerous species of plants and animals, long ago disappeared in other countries of Europe, or still existing, but in a very reduced number (Cristea, M.D., 2007; 2012; Marușca, T., 2017). In order to illustrate these aspects, we put forwards in synthesis (in table 1 and 2) the main vegetable and animal genetic resources, with phyto-zoo-food economic potential (to which there are naturally added plants from big culture and horticulture too).

Table 1. Genetic resources from Romania, with phyto-food potential

No	GROUP OF RESOURCES	EXEMPLE
1	GROUP OF FOREST FRUITS IN ROMANIA	Strawberries / Fragi (<i>Fragaria vesca</i>)
		Cranberries / Afine (<i>Vaccinium myrtillus L</i>)
		Raspberry / Zmeură (<i>Rubus idaeus</i>)
		Cultured blueberries / Afine de cultură (<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>)
		Buckthorn / Cătină (<i>Hippophaë rhamnoides L.</i>)
		Blackberries / Mure (<i>Rubus fruticosus L.</i>)
		Macies / Măcieș (<i>Rosa canina</i>)
		Cranberry / Merișor (<i>Vaccinium vitis idaea - L.</i>)
		Shock / Socul (<i>Sambucus L.</i>)
		Red currant / Coacăz roșu (<i>Ribes rubrum</i>)
		Gooseberries / Agrișe (<i>Ribes grossularia</i>)
		Strawberries / Căpșuni (<i>Fragaria viridis</i>)
		Hezelnut / Alunul (<i>Corylus avellana</i>)
		Walnut / Nucul (<i>Juglans regia L.</i>)
2	GROUP OF MEDICINAL AND MELLIFEROUS PLANTS FROM ROMANIA	Cornflowers / Albăstrele (<i>Centaurea cyanus</i>)
		Potato / Cartoful (<i>familia Solanaceae / Solanum tuberosum</i>)
		Edible castene / Castanele comestibile (<i>Castanea sativa</i>)
		Artichoke / Anghinarea (<i>Cynara scolymus</i>)
		Cucumber / Castravetele (<i>Cucumis sativus</i>)
		Pepper / Ardei iute (<i>Capsicum annuum</i>)
		Buckthorn / Cătină (<i>Hippophaë rhamnoides L.</i>)
		Onion / Ceapa (<i>Allium cepa</i>)
		„Barba popi” (<i>Filipendula ulmaria</i>)
		Chicory / Cicoarea (<i>Cichorium intybus</i>)
		Tree / Bradul (<i>Abies alba</i>)
		Thyme / Cimbrul (<i>Thymus serpyllum</i>)
		Basil / Busuiocul (<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>)
		Cherry / Cireșul (<i>Cerasus vulgaris</i>)
		Apricot / Caisul (<i>Familia Rosaceae</i>)
		Primrose / Ciuboțica cucului (<i>Primula veris</i>)
		Strawberries / Căpșunul (<i>Familia Rosaceae</i>)
		Mushrooms (edible mushrooms) / Ciupercile (- ciupercile comestibile din <i>regnul Fungi</i> de tip <i>Ascomycota</i> precum <i>Basidiomycota</i> /care au pălărie și picior)

Tabel 2. Genetic resources from Romania, with zoo-food & vestimentary potential

No	GROUP OF RESOURCES	EXEMPLE
1	GENETIC RESOURCES OF FARM MAMIFERES	Pig / Porcul domestic (<i>Sus scrofa domesticus</i> sau <i>Sus domesticus</i>)
		Ruminants , Cow / Vaca subordonului Ruminantia (rumegătoarele), familia Bovidae.
		Hors / Calul (<i>Equus caballus</i>)
		Sheep / Oaia domestică (<i>Ovis aries</i>)
		Goat / Capra domestică (<i>Capra aegagrus hircus</i>)
2	GENETIC RESOURCES OF BIRDS FARM	Chickens / Găini (<i>Gallus gallus domesticus</i>)
		Turkeys / Curci (<i>Meleagris gallopavo</i>)
		Geese / Gâște domestice (<i>Anser cygnoides</i>)
		Ducklings / Rațe de curte (<i>subfamilia Anatinae</i>)
		Quail / Prepelițe (<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>)
		Doves / Porumbei (<i>Columba livia</i>)
		Pheasants / Fazani (<i>Phasianus colchicus</i>)
Peacocks / Păuni (<i>Pavo sp.</i>)		
3	GENETIC RESOURCES OF SMALL ANIMAL FARM	Rabbits / Iepuri (<i>familia Leporidae</i>)
		Chinchilla / Chinchila (<i>familia Chinchillidae</i>)

	Nutria / Nutria (<i>Myocastor coypus</i>)
	Muskkrat / Bizam (<i>Ondatra zibethicus</i>)
	Guinea pig / Porcușor de Guineea (<i>subfamilia Caviinae</i>)
	Polecat, or ferret / Dihor (<i>Mustela putorius</i>)
	Mink / Nurca (<i>Mustela vison</i>)
	Polar fox / Vulpe polară (<i>Vulpes lagopus</i>)

In the above and following tables there are enumerated species belonging to agro-biodiversity field, in order to have an image of the present production and of the diversification potential through new species with economic potential and new food sorts. It is observed that Romania is one of the few European countries where *traditional agro-systems* represent significant reservoirs from the point of view of genetic diversity both for plant culture (phyto culture), and for animal breeding (zoo culture), that have been conserved at their formation and development place (*in situ*). (Drăgănescu, C., 1984; Gruia, R., 2016).

But information is much more detailed in a series of papers and documents, from which we mention:

- ❖ THE CATALOGUE OF PLANT VARIETIES (sorts) that are cultivated on Romania's territory, identifying a number of 2118 sorts of plants.
- ❖ THE CATALOGUE OF DOMESTIC MAMMALS – there are included 79 de races (out of which 26 are still active, 19 in

potential danger and 34 disappeared). Although, there must be marked that many local races (*Țurcană, Țigaie, Carpathian Goat etc.*) have a reproduction system in local communities (reproductive isolation over a certain area, without genealogic register and production official control, the selection being made after the owners' preference).

Concerning geo-climate and cultural diversity, the diagnosis may be grouped in the following typological aspects: - diversity of biodiversity geo resources (flora, fauna); - diversity of agrotouring geo resources (touring villages / cultural products and elements of the local community) and – diversity of drinking water geo resources (water as „food”).

Linked to biodiversity, in table 3 there are mentioned, in synthesis (Cristea, M.D., 2012; Gruia, R., 2017), from current documents of specialty literature, a series of information that demonstrate the existence of a real potential that may guarantee the work basis for food reserve in the future.

Table 3. Geo resources from Romania's biodiversity

Romania's flora	Romania's fauna
<p>Over Romania's territory there have been identified 3700 species of plants out of which, in the present, 23 have been declared natural monuments, 74 disappeared, 39 in danger, 171 vulnerable and 1253 are considered rare. The three large vegetation zones are the alpine zone, the forest zone and the steppe zone in Romania.</p> <p>Vegetation is storiedly distributed, in concordance with the soil and climate characteristics, but also in function of altitude, as follows: oak, „gârnița”, lime tree, ash tree (in steppe zones and low hills); beech, holm-oak (between 500 and 1200 de meters); spruce, fir tree, pine (between 1200 and 1800 meters); juniper, savin and dwarf trees (between 1800 and 2000 meters); alpine lawns formed of small herbs (over 2000 meters). Over large valleys, due to persistent wetness, there appears meadow specific vegetation, with thatch, rush, carex and often with bunches of willows, poplars and alders. In the Danube Delta swamp vegetation predominates.</p>	<p>It is one of the richest and varied from Europe, containing rare or even unique on the continent species. In Romania there live 732 vertebrate species and subspecies and numerous (some thousands) non-vertebrate species. Vertebrates are represented in Romania's fauna by: cyclostomes (4 species), fish (184 species and subspecies), amphibians (20 species and subspecies), reptiles (31 species and subspecies), birds (382 species and subspecies) and mammals (110 species and subspecies). Among the mentioned groups, in the Romanian space there live approximately 4000 butterfly species (from which approx. 25 % on the Tâmpa Mountain/ Brașov). Among mammals, one is in imminent extinction danger (the sea cow), one in danger (the mink), 13 vulnerable and 4 threatened.</p>

What may encourage the optimistic idea of the future alimentation from Romania are **geo resources of drinking water**, all this because,

after a series of predictions, drinking water may become more precious than oil in the 21st century. There already are certain signals in this

direction, situation that will worsen if this trend of climate and demographic changes continues without imposing serious remediating solutions.

We consider that it becomes more than opportune in Romania to approach a **strategy** with a clear financing at its basis, so that the present quantities of fresh water may be maintained, regenerated, as well as to develop the capitalization capacities of drinking water. All

these especially that it mustn't be forgotten the fact that Romania owns 60 % from the reserves of Europe's mineral water (mediafax.ro). Therefore, within the principles of the mentioned strategy, we should NOT sell the right of this resource property (neither of other resources and raw materials), but we should capitalize only obtained and assortimentally diversified productions (fig.1).

Fig. 1. Geo resources of drinking water from Romania

3.3. Application of bioeconomy principles for sustainable development of the phyto-zoo-food system

Analyzing the third step, as it is known, **bioeconomy** indicates an economic theory that inevitably leads to a sustainable development from ecologic and social perspective. Methodologically, there are taken into consideration the Material / Substance (S) and Energy (E) that enter an economic processes with relatively low entropy and come out with another degree of entropy, which imposes to take into consideration the thermodynamics principles in the context of the more and more precarious offer of natural resources (Georgescu-Roegen, N., 1979). After the year 2012, the European economy focalizes towards a more important and sustainable use of renewable resources. That is to say, taking into consideration that there is dramatically accentuated the paradox between demographic growth and finite natural resources, Europe needs renewable biological resources for secure and healthy food and fodder for animals, as well as for materials, energy and other corresponding products. That is why it is considered to pass from standard agriculture to

modular and precision agriculture (Gruia, R., 2010).

Without entering into details, bioeconomy brings into discussion man's role in anthropic ecosystems, the negative energetic account in case of excessive consumers of raw materials and the lack of perspectives for future generations (Bogdan, A.T., and others, 2011). We speak about an economy that refers to *the second thermodynamics law*, being well in with the **entropy concept**, or with the disorder created during a thermodynamic process. In principle „green economy” offers such processes a solution to harmonize them.

Green economy, based on „bio-eco-economy green power” (implicitly sustainable), is part of the integration in the *green revolution*, next to ecologic management, green energy and afferent „green” affairs: solar energy, wind energy, bio fuels, hydro energy, thermal energy and, last but not least, the green power of the agri-food system (Bogdan A.T and Comşa, Dana, 2011). A natural consequence is the decisive step in professional formation. We speak about „eco-bio-economic engineering”, but also about the „bioeconomy management” (Gruia, R., 2013).

Practically nowadays and at the present level nobody can afford an ample extending of the green economy, so that there have appeared developing models based on the principles of this type of economy, but with new dimensions. This is about considerably enlarging the systemic coverage towards *social aspects* (taking into consideration that there is higher unemployment, situations of loss of national capital, lack of chances for young people and others), enlargement towards innovation and technologic rethought, especially on *circular model*, all these finally leading towards the „blue economy” model (Pauli, 2010).

Blue economy is first of all based on scientific analyses that identify the best innovations. These

ones lead to the creation of a new social capital that, at its turn will allow having the best products, *cheaper ones*, the healthiest products, *cheaper ones*, and will stimulate *entrepreneurship*. There are stipulated solutions to redesign make processes in nonpolluting and cheap systems. This economic model offers private entrepreneurs instruments capable to sustain the creation of jobs, men’s prosperity, their, but also the environment’s health (being in fact aimed *eco-health generating*, especially the direction of getting food). We are talking about the process of *ecosanogenesis*, which also has the interpretation of „one health” in figure 2 (sursa: [Elsevier FoodScience @ELSfoodscience](https://www.elsevier.com/locate/ELS)).

Fig.2. Interconnection of bioeconomic components relevant to animal, human and environmental health, based on the phyto-zoo-food system

In the future decades, passing from green economy to blue economy may lead to **secure the Romanian economy**, and in the agriculture field the change of the managerial paradigm also presupposes, among others, the following elements: - agro-ecosystem reconversion (application of friendly technologies with natural environment); - circular economy (with reuses of the secondary agri-food production, of wastes and residues); - reorientation of the formation of human resource in the field (new educational approaches on bioeconomic and sustainable development direction).

The concept of circular economy is defining in order to harmonize mankind’s needs of sustainable development on long term. Practically it is necessary to optimize resource consumptions so that not to waste and reuse them as much as possible. To this effect (from Eurostat data), Europe loses at present, every year, approximately 600 millions of tons of materials contained in wastes, that might be recycled or reused. Meanwhile, the growth of food product demand, the limited availability of arable land, energetic poverty, the increase of fresh water need, together with the impact of climate

changes, all these constrain us to modify our linear economy. Europe's economy must „close the loop”, an action that might bring net economies of 600 billions € - or 8% from the annual turnover – from enterprises from EU, and will stimulate the creation of jobs, more than 170.000 direct jobs, as well as created potential

in Europe until 2030. Such an economy, as it is shown in fig.3, functions in a **loop**, having as objective to produce goods and services, while it limits very much consumption and waste of raw materials and sources of non renewable energy (Pillet, G., 1993, Gruia, R., 1998, Pauli, G., 2010).

Fig. 3. Block diagram of circular economy

Economic units on circular flow will allow the creation of revenues by: - purification systems of worn-out waters with biogas production and cost reduction; - systems of biogas production as profitable investment. Technologies already are relatively advanced, so that systems may be turnkey, personalized, made with robust techniques and modern technologies equipment, that aim to diminish costs and maximize biogas and nutrient production from worn-out water and animal wastes. These systems have been successfully implemented at slaughter houses, processing factories and animal farms from Europe (for instance, Colsen Group - Van den Hul from Holland is preoccupied to bring into use a purification system of worn-out waters at big slaughter houses). There is a deepening of the understanding from the „linear economy” to the „circular economy”, but the reality is more complex and there is the hypothesis that a „non-linear economy” could be decoded, which means a completely different approach with unpredictable effects.

3.4. Finding new food resources in order to counteract the potential of alimentary crises

In a fourth step of analyses there may be observed the historic evolution of the feeding manner and food production. Thus, mankind

needed almost 10.000 years of agriculture to develop the cultures and animal effectives we are consuming today. There have been necessary only a few centuries to develop agricultural tools that culminated with mechanized agriculture at a large and efficient scale and with today's biotechnology equipment.

There have been necessary only decades to harmonize science with aliments, to connect food and health, allowing us to directly manipulate genetic constructions of the aliments we are consuming.

In the future, as almost 75% from the world's population is affected by the lack of different types of aliments, the next frontier is our ability to produce aliments from molecular components and to replace the need of practices to develop aliments that consume resources, often non ethical, personalized, health generating systems etc. A possibility that agro-alimentary research develops in the present refers to **synthetic foods** that are created through combination of alimentary substances (in fact they are natural raw materials) and submission of these substances at different modern processes in order to get the desired food product.

Although they are artificial food products, they contain complete proteins that have been derived from natural aliments. It must be mentioned that there exists a much reduced

quantity of aliments that contain complete proteins (all the aminoacids that are not produced by the organism). The technique of making food products is ready, but are we ready? That is why,

in order to have an overall, we try to answer this question by a SWOT analyze (*Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats*), i.e. a 2x2 matrix.

SWOT Analysis - Synthetic Food

	<i>Beneficial aspects to attain objectives</i>	<i>Aspects that put into danger attaining objectives</i>
Internal source (organization)	<p>STRONG POINTS</p> <p>Science progresses: progresses in the fields of molecular biology, physical chemistry, physics, biochemistry and colloidal chemistry have enabled to produce synthetic foods out of chemical products (derived including as extracts of natural products).</p>	<p>WEAK POINTS</p> <p>The perception that synthetic foods may be harmful for health. But in fact, when „deconstructing” food products at their molecular components and reassemble them molecule after molecule, we have the luxury not to add certain components that present a risk for the human health.</p>
External source (external environment)	<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p> <p>Having total control upon synthetic food molecular construction, there will be obtained a generalized positive impact upon the food chain. There will be open a future where any desired food may be available at a given moment, by touching a button.</p>	<p>MENACES</p> <p>Avoiding alimentary crisis and risks. Synthetic foods are as safe as or safer than their natural counterparts (pesticides, pollutants, contaminated bacteria etc. are avoided).</p>

3.5. Alimentary education as a resource for understanding the paradigmatic feeding level

We cannot solve any food crisis unless we put, in a fifth step, the problem of men's permanent education in the more and more accelerated conditions of science and technique development. The engineering and management effort to solve the problem of food crisis in the future (it also includes the drinking water one) shows us the problem amplitude, especially from the perspective of population information and formation to understand certain new paradigms linked to the feeding manner. There is aimed a feeding manner where aliments may cumulate both *energo-nutritive* contribution and the health-generating and psychi-senzorial one. These are well fundamental aspects in getting food supplements (based on certain ingredients), functional aliments (with innovative fortifying components), nutraceuticals and others. As for culinary production, among the new paradigms we may remind predictive alimentation and personalized gastronomy.

To pass towards new alimentary habits is not simple, but it becomes more and more opportune. **Predictive alimentation** refers to passing from empiric or mystic predictions to algorithms and predictive modeling, including on biocomplexity principles.

Personalized gastronomy is based on the idea that men differently respond concerning

alimentary habits and behaviors, both due to certain environmental factors and to the influence of genetic variants concerning absorption, metabolism and utilization of nutritive components from food. Genotype particularities are important in maintaining the *metabolic balance*, which in the future imposes orientation towards personalized gastronomy.

This one will beneficially influence organism and longevity by increased productivity and the efficiency of the alimentary consumption. These are desiderata we also have in developing the agri-food branch from Romania, being a field that may define the country profile and, implicitly, the European interest.

Conclusions

1. As Europe's agriculture seems to stagnate and water (as an aliment) becomes a problem in the context of climatic modifications, **the paradigm change** is the solution of the food act regeneration through which one may pass: from standard agriculture to modular and precision agriculture, to predictive alimentation / preventive and personalized one, but also to synthetic food (approach on knowledge direction: *science and technology*)

2. **Engineering and management**, by optimizing the resource use and rethought of agri-food production systems, Romania may have the chance to preserve and develop in the future a

phyto-zoo-food area with natural and renewable potential in assuring food security (approach on direction of: *professionalism and performance*): - the **Carpathian mountains** may become a real food reserve, with adapted vegetable and animal resources, with offer of qualitative drinking water; - Romania's plains may become secure and consistent producers, but only if they are provided with completely irrigated agro-modules; - the priority of the research in the field is obligatory.

3. Having a pretty potential of georesources, in the obligatory conditions of applying the new concepts of food production (on bioeconomy, biodiversity and geoclimatic diversity direction) harmonized in a country consequent strategy, one may benefit by a great *opportunity*: **Romania may be a food and water reserve and contributor in Europe, in the decades to come.**

References

1. Abrudan, I., (2018): In search of performance, Review of Management and Economic Engineering, AMIER, Vol.17, nr.1(67), 5-12.
2. Bogdan A.T. et al. (2011): E-banking products and services for agribusiness based eco-economy, with ways "from the farm to the fork" în forecasting for developed and developing countries on period 2020-2050 2100, WSEAS, Recent Research in Business Administration, Finance and Product Management, ISBN: 978-960-474-265-3, p. 100-105.
3. Bogdan, A.T. (2012): [Despre ecoeconomie și economie verde în România. Referat științific.](#) Școala Postdoctorală de Biodiversitate Zootehnică și Biotehnologii Alimentare, INCE/CSCBA - Academia Română, Proiect 89/1.5/S/63258, 2007-2013;
4. Bogdan, A.T., Comșa, Dana (2011): Eco-Bio-Economia o noua paradigmă, în Soluții eco-bioeconomice bazate pe biodiversitate agrosilvică pentru asigurarea independenței și suveranității agroalimentare durabile a României europene și euroatlantice, Ed. Libris Danubiu, București, p. 34-38;
5. Cristea, M.D., 2007: Biodiversitatea, Ed. Ceres București, ISBN: 973-40-0748-3
6. Cristea, M.D., 2012: Biotehnologia și biodiversitatea, Ed. Academiei Române București, ISBN : 978-973-272-095-0;
7. Drăgănescu, C., 1984: Zootehnia, ecologie aplicată, Ed Ceres, București.
8. Georgescu-Roegen, N. (1979): Legea entropiei, Ed. Politică, București;
9. Gruia, R. (1998): Managementul ecofermelor, Ed. Ceres, București, p. 41-50;
10. Gruia, R. (2010): Modular agriculture – paradigm of globalization dynamics within the context of climatic and scientific changes, în Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, "Gheorghe Asachi" Technical University Iasi, ISSN 1582-9596, vol. 9, nr. 12, p. 1601-1606;
11. Gruia, R. (2013): Bazele managementului și direcțiile viitoare de evoluție, Editura Lux Libris, Brașov, ISBN: 978-973-131-230-9, p. 140-143;
12. Gruia, R., (2016): Zootehnia bioeconomică, Ed. Lux Libris Brașov, ISBN 978-973-131-357-3, 27-42;
13. Gruia, R., (2017): Resurse genetice în fermele agroturistice, Editura Clarion Brașov, ISBN 978-606-94470-0-0, 189-242;
14. Marușca, T., 2017: Elemente de gradientică și ecologie montană, Ed. Universității Transilvanis Brasov, ISBN 978-606-19-0892-9 ;
15. Pauli, G., (2010): Economia albastră : 10 ani, 100 de inovatii, 100 de milioane de locuri de munca / Ed. Paideia București, ISBN 978-973-596638-6;
16. Pillet, G. (1993): Economie écologique – introduction à l'économie de l'environnement et des ressources naturelles, Georg Editeur SA, Geneva, 153-211;
17. XXX - (2004): Planurile de Management ale Bazinelor Hidrografice – Raport Național 2004 <https://ro.wikipedia.org/>
18. XXX - Statistici Eurostat, 2016, 2017.
19. XXX - <http://www.mediafax.ro/>